

A Compendium of Biosolids Land Application Regulations

2nd Edition

Produced by the Sustainable Phosphorus Alliance and STEPS

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NOTE: Regulations are “living” data in that they are always being updated. While we will do our best to update the database when we have resources available, some data may not be up to date. Additionally, as we improve the quality assurance of the existing data, the compendium may be updated.

Preface

Probably the earliest example of circular economic thinking is that of applying animal wastes to grow crops that become food for animals. We have used human waste as a fertilizer for millennia, though we in the United States do so now under regulatory regimes that prohibit the use of raw sewage in agriculture and, instead, prescribe the use of sewage that has been treated to standards that reduce pathogens, organic and metal contaminants, and other pollutants.

Biosolids—a term used to describe the solid organic matter that results from this treatment of domestic sewage—provide farmers with rich sources of carbon and nutrients, including phosphorus and nitrogen. Title 40, Part 503 of the US Code of Federal Regulations establishes a set of minimum regulations that govern all land application of biosolids in the United States. These regulations constrain not just what is applied to land, but how it is applied. In doing so, they help protect our health and that of America's waters while setting the ground rules that enable nutrient recycling.

States are free to implement regulations that are more stringent than the federal Part 503 regulations, and some do. In fact, states don't all agree on the definition of biosolids or classes of biosolids. The result is a patchwork of regulations that can be difficult to navigate.

This compendium provides a state-by-state overview of these state-level regulations as they apply to the land application of biosolids. It is meant to provide regulators, biosolids producers, purveyors of biosolids products, researchers, and others with a handy regulatory guide that might be used in scenario development and comparative analysis exercises. This is version 2 of a compendium that was first produced in 2019. We have tried to obtain updates to the regulations from the relevant state agencies, and those updates are reflected here. However, about half of the states did not respond to our multiple requests for updates. We have listed the latest update date within the state tables presented in this document.

Our focus here is on regulations that directly affect nutrient flows through the environment as a result of land application. We are specifically interested in what agronomic practices are prescribed and what limits are placed on the use of the various classes of biosolids. We deliberately chose not to address regulations that deal with administrative details of biosolids programs, including monitoring and permitting requirements, labeling and reporting requirements, and other aspects of the regulations that are more about the bureaucracy of biosolids management than the application of biosolids. However, we do provide reference to the appropriate regulations to guide more trenchant research.

We also do not recapitulate the federal regulations within the state summaries. Readers should keep in mind that regulations presented here are those that extend beyond those listed in 40 CFR 503. To facilitate state-to-state comparisons, we do note where elements of state regulations are directly derived from 40 CFR 503, then indicate the pertinent state regulation. We also provide a summary sheet of the federal regulations as the first table in this report.

The summary documents are each divided into three sections. The first provides details about the regulations and regulators. The second provides key definitions that states have adopted, focusing primarily on how classes of biosolids and agronomic rates of application are defined. The third section

contains the state-level regulations of land application that extend beyond 40 CFR 503. A brief key to the row headers in this third part of the table follows.

Setbacks	State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.
Weather and Seasonal Regulations	State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.
Agronomic Regulations	State regulations that restrict the type of land to which biosolids are applied, the rates at which they are applied, or how or when application is to take place.
Composition Testing Regulations	State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.
Time Restriction Regulations	Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access
Operational Standard Regulations	State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time
Vector Regulations	State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids
Pollutant Regulations	State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids
Transfer Regulations	State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting
Nutrient Management Plans	State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program
Incineration Regulations	Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative
Other Land Application Regulations	Additional restrictions for land application of biosolids
Other Biosolids Regulations	Additional information on the regulation of land application of biosolids

Finally, while we have done our best to provide a faithful and, as of January 2025, up-to-date account of these state regulations, we make no guarantee of accuracy. As mentioned above, roughly half of the states that we contacted for updates since 2019 did not provide them and, as a result, some of the data below can only be confirmed as correct as of March 2019. Clearly, this document should not be used to determine the legality of any practice.

This compendium is a companion to our Compendium of Manure Land Application Regulations. We hope that these guides provides a resource that ultimately helps increase the *sustainable* reuse of organic residuals.

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It should be noted that the authors of the report are solely responsible for the content and responsibility should not be assigned to any of the aforementioned organizations.

U.S. FEDERAL REGULATIONS FROM 40 CFR 503

Regulator	
Regulating Agency	US Environmental Protection Agency
Regulation Links	US Code of Federal Regulations, Chapter 40 Part 503: https://www.ecfr.gov/cgi-bin/retrieveECFR?gp=2&SID=3ba5c96eb4bfc5bfdfa86764a30e9901&ty=HTML&h=L&n=pt40.30.503&r=PART
Delegated for Biosolids	NA
Other Regulatory Details	These regulations pertain to all US states
Definitions	
Biosolids Definition	Biosolids are not defined at the federal level, rather “sewage sludge” is used. Sewage sludge is solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works. Sewage sludge includes, but is not limited to, domestic septage; scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes; and a material derived from sewage sludge. Sewage sludge does not include ash generated during the firing of sewage sludge in a sewage sludge incinerator or grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works.
Biosolids Class Definition	<p>Class A. The requirement in §503.32(a)(2) and the requirements in either §503.32(a)(3), (a)(4), (a)(5), (a)(6), (a)(7), or (a)(8) must be met for a sewage sludge to be classified Class A with respect to pathogens. The requirements establish 6 different alternative methods for establishing Class A status and specifies that pathogen reduction must be achieved before or at the same time as vector reduction.</p> <p>Class B. The requirements in either §503.32(b)(2), (b)(3), or (b)(4) must be met for a sewage sludge to be classified Class B with respect to pathogens. Three different alternative methods are provided for establishing Class B status.</p>
Other Definitions	<p><i>Agronomic rate</i> is the whole sludge application rate (dry weight basis) designed:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> (1) To provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop, or vegetation grown on the land; and (2) To minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the ground water. <p><i>Land application</i> is the spraying or spreading of sewage sludge onto the land surface; the injection of sewage sludge below the land surface; or the incorporation of sewage sludge into the soil so that the sewage sludge can either condition the soil or fertilize crops or vegetation grown in the soil.</p> <p><i>Domestic septage</i> is either liquid or solid material removed from a septic tank, cesspool, portable toilet, Type III marine sanitation device, or similar treatment works that receives only domestic sewage. Domestic septage does not include</p>

	liquid or solid material removed from a septic tank, cesspool, or similar treatment works that receives either commercial wastewater or industrial wastewater and does not include grease removed from a grease trap at a restaurant.
Regulatory Details	
Setbacks Regulations	<p>The following regulation does not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8).</p> <p>Bulk sewage sludge may not be applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site that is 10 meters or less from waters of the United States, as defined in 40 CFR 122.2, unless otherwise specified by the permitting authority.</p>
Weather and Seasonal Regulations	<p>The following regulation does not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8).</p> <p>Bulk sewage sludge may not be applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site that is flooded, frozen, or snow-covered so that the bulk sewage sludge enters a wetland or other waters of the United States, as defined in 40 CFR 122.2, except as provided in a permit issued pursuant to section 402 or 404 of the CWA.</p>
Agronomic Regulations	<p>The following regulation does not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8).</p> <p>Bulk sewage sludge must be applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site at a whole sludge application rate that is equal to or less than the agronomic rate for the bulk sewage sludge, unless, in the case of a reclamation site, otherwise specified by the permitting authority.</p>
Composition Testing Regulations	<p>The following regulations do not apply when a bulk material derived from sewage sludge is applied to land or a material derived from sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the sewage sludge from which the material is derived meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8).</p> <p>The frequency of monitoring for the pollutants listed in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 of §503.13; the pathogen density requirements in §503.32(a) and §503.32(b)(2); and the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(4) and §503.33 (b)(7) through (b)(8) must be:</p> <p>Yearly, if amount of bulk sewage sludge applied to the land or the amount of sewage sludge prepared for sale or give-away in a bag or other container for</p>

	<p>application to the land is greater than zero but less than 290 metric tons per 365 day period</p> <p>Once per quarter, if amount of bulk sewage sludge applied to the land or the amount of sewage sludge prepared for sale or give-away in a bag or other container for application to the land is equal to or greater than 290 but less than 1,500 metric tons per 365 day period</p> <p>Once per 60 days, if amount of bulk sewage sludge applied to the land or the amount of sewage sludge prepared for sale or give-away in a bag or other container for application to the land is equal to or greater than 1,500 but less than 15,000 metric tons per 365 day period</p> <p>Once per month, if amount of bulk sewage sludge applied to the land or the amount of sewage sludge prepared for sale or give-away in a bag or other container for application to the land is equal to or greater than 15,000 metric tons per 365 day period</p> <p>After the sewage sludge has been monitored for two years at the frequency in Table 1 of §503.16, the permitting authority may reduce the frequency of monitoring for pollutant concentrations and for the pathogen density requirements in §503.32(a)(5)(ii) and (a)(5)(iii).</p> <p>Domestic septage. If either the pathogen requirements in §503.32(c)(2) or the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(12) are met when domestic septage is applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site, each container of domestic septage applied to the land must be monitored for compliance with those requirements.</p> <p>As part of recordkeeping requirements, the following quantities must be known: concentration of each pollutant listed in Table 3 of §503.13,</p>
<p>Time Restriction Regulations</p>	<p>The following regulations apply to Class B sewage sludge and domestic septage:</p> <p>Food crops with harvested parts that touch the sewage sludge/soil mixture and are totally above the land surface must not be harvested for 14 months after application of sewage sludge.</p> <p>Food crops with harvested parts below the surface of the land must not be harvested for 20 months after application of sewage sludge when the sewage sludge remains on the land surface for four months or longer prior to incorporation into the soil.</p> <p>Food crops with harvested parts below the surface of the land must not be harvested for 38 months after application of sewage sludge when the sewage sludge remains on the land surface for less than four months prior to incorporation into the soil.</p> <p>Food crops, feed crops, and fiber crops must not be harvested for 30 days after application of sewage sludge.</p> <p>Animals must not be grazed on the land for 30 days after application of sewage sludge.</p> <p>Turf grown on land where sewage sludge is applied must not be harvested for one year after application of the sewage sludge when the harvested turf is placed on either land with a high potential for public exposure or a lawn, unless otherwise specified by the permitting authority.</p> <p>Public access to land with a high potential for public exposure must be restricted for one year after application of sewage sludge.</p> <p>Public access to land with a low potential for public exposure must be restricted for 30 days after application of sewage sludge.</p>

	<p>The pH of domestic septage applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site must be raised to 12 or higher by alkali addition and, without the addition of more alkali, must remain at 12 or higher for 30 minutes and the site restrictions in §503.32 (b)(5)(i) through (b)(5)(iv) must be met.</p>
Operational Standard Regulations	<p>The Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to a lawn or a home garden.</p> <p>The Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a) must be met when sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land.</p> <p>The requirements in either §503.32 (c)(1) or (c)(2) must be met when domestic septage is applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site.</p> <p>One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(10) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site.</p> <p>One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(8) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to a lawn or a home garden.</p> <p>One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(8) must be met when sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land.</p> <p>The vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(9), (b)(10), or (b)(12) must be met when domestic septage is applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site.</p> <p>The following regulation does not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8).</p> <p>Bulk sewage sludge may not be applied to the land if it is likely to adversely affect a threatened or endangered species listed under section 4 of the Endangered Species Act or its designated critical habitat.</p>
Vector Regulations	<p>One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(10) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site.</p> <p>One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(8) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to a lawn or a home garden or when sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land.</p> <p>One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(9), (b)(10), or (b)(12) must be met when domestic septage is applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site.</p>
Pollutant Regulations	<p>Bulk sewage sludge or sewage sludge sold or given away in a bag or other container may not be applied to the land if the concentration of any pollutant in the sewage sludge exceeds the ceiling concentration for the pollutant in Table 1 of §503.13.</p> <p>If bulk sewage sludge is applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site, either:</p>

The cumulative loading rate for each pollutant may not exceed the cumulative pollutant loading rate for the pollutant in Table 2 of §503.13; or
The concentration of each pollutant in the sewage sludge may not exceed the concentration for the pollutant in Table 3 of §503.13.
If bulk sewage sludge is applied to a lawn or a home garden, the concentration of each pollutant in the sewage sludge may not exceed the concentration for the pollutant in Table 3 of §503.13.
If sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land, either:
The concentration of each pollutant in the sewage sludge may not exceed the concentration for the pollutant in Table 3 of §503.13; or
The product of the concentration of each pollutant in the sewage sludge and the annual whole sludge application rate for the sewage sludge may not cause the annual pollutant loading rate for the pollutant in Table 4 of §503.13 to be exceeded.
The procedure used to determine the annual whole sludge application rate is presented in appendix A of 40 CFR 503 Part B.

The following regulations do not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8).

No application of bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site if any of the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has been reached.

No application of domestic septage to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site during a 365 day period if the annual application rate in §503.13(c) has been reached during that period.

Before bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) is applied to the land, a determination must be made by the state permitting authority to determine whether bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has been applied to the site since July 20, 1993.

(ii) If bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has not been applied to the site since July 20, 1993, the cumulative amount for each pollutant listed in Table 2 of §503.13 may be applied to the site in accordance with §503.13(a)(2)(i).

(iii) If bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has been applied to the site since July 20, 1993, and the cumulative amount of each pollutant applied to the site in the bulk sewage sludge since that date is known, the cumulative amount of each pollutant applied to the site must be used to determine the additional amount of each pollutant that can be applied to the site in accordance with §503.13(a)(2)(i).

(iv) If bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has been applied to the site since July 20, 1993, and the cumulative

	amount of each pollutant applied to the site in the bulk sewage sludge since that date is not known, an additional amount of each pollutant must not be applied to the site in accordance with §503.13(a)(2)(i).
Transfer Regulations	None
Nutrient Management Plans	None required federally
Incineration Regulations	Varies by state
Other Land Application Regulations	None
Other Biosolids Regulations	None

Alabama Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Alabama State Board of Health
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Health
Links to regulations	Alabama Administrative Code, Chapter 335-13-16-.05: https://admincode.legislature.state.al.us/administrative-code/335-13-16-.05
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No

Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Unknown
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	The land application of sewage sludge or similar waste from sewage treatment plants is prohibited by the state as per 420-3-6-.07. Septage may be applied.
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions	No

<p>(e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Alaska	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Alaska Department of Environmental Conservation (ADEC)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Alaska Administrative Code:_ https://www.akleg.gov/basis/aac.asp
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	Alaska's biosolids regulations are not more restrictive than the federal_ Part 503 rule. As per 18 AAC 60.510, a land application of biosolids solid waste permit application is required to be submitted to the Alaska Department of Environmental Conservation (DEC), unless the generator demonstrates to the department's satisfaction that the material:_ (1) meets 40 CFR 503.32(a) Class A pathogen requirements,_ (2) meets one of the vector requirements of 40 CFR 503.33(b)(1-8),_ (3) meets pollutant concentration limits specified in 18 AAC 60.510 Table H, and_ (4) is free of excessive dust or strong odor
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means sewage solids or septage that is treated to reduce pathogens and vector attraction for application to the land as a fertilizer or soil amendment
Biosolids classes	Same as 40 CFR 503
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	* Only exceptional quality sludge may be applied to lawns and home gardens. Owing to tighter state restrictions on metals, this is more restrictive than 40 CFR 503._ * Bagged sludge given away or sold must meet Class EQ pathogen and vector reduction requirements, and either the high quality pollutant concentration limits in Table 2._

	– For Class B sites, many requirements including detailed soils work is required for permitting a specific application field (Section 119).
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Has a Chromium limit
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	Yes
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	Details required in the application for a Land Application of Biosolids Permit - http://dec.alaska.gov/eh/solid-waste/permitapps/
General Assessment Questions	

<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>Yes. New regulations for permitting all treatment facilities for sewage solids or septage. Removed the former exemption for facilities treating less than 5 tons per day. 18 AAC 60.200(a)(10).</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>Yes. Matanuska-Sustina Borough has banned the land application of biosolids in the Borough.</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Septage, included in 18 AAC 60.500.</p>

Arizona	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Arizona Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	* ARS Title 49 Chapter 2 Article 3.1: Arizona Pollutant Discharge Elimination System Program_ https://www.azleg.gov/arsDetail/?title=49_ * Arizona Administrative Code: 18 AAC 9 Art 10 - AZPDES, Disposal Use and Transportation of Biosolids_ http://legacy.azdeq.gov/envIRON/water/permits/download/brules.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means sewage sludge, including exceptional quality biosolids, that is placed on, or applied to the land to use the beneficial properties of the material as a soil amendment, conditioner, or fertilizer. Biosolids do not include hazardous sludge, sludge with PCBs > 50 mg/kg (dw), grit, sludge from drinking water, septage, and special wastes defined by A.R.S. Title 49, Chapter 4, Article 9
Biosolids classes	Exceptional quality: certified as meeting specified monthly average pollutant concentrations, Class A pathogen reduction requirements (below), and one of 8 vector attraction reduction requirements designated in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8)_ The term Class A and B and used in accordance with 40 CFR 503
Other Definitions	"Reclamation" means the use of biosolids to restore or repair construction sites, active or closed mining sites, landfill caps, or other drastically disturbed land _ – "Domestic septage" means the liquid or solid material removed from a septic tank, cesspool, portable toilet, marine sanitation device, or similar system or device that receives only domestic sewage. "Domestic septage" does not include commercial or industrial wastewater or restaurant grease-trap wastes._
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application</i>	Non-EQ:_ 1. Must apply > 32.8 ft from navigable waters_ 2. Must store or apply > 25 ft from public right-of-way or private property line unless the applicator receives permission_

<p><i>and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>3. Must apply and store > 1000 ft from dwelling unless injected/incorporated within 10 hours, unless granted permission by owner/lessee_</p> <p>4. Must store or apply at least 1000 feet from a public or semi-public drinking water supply well, unless approved, and at least 250 feet from any other water well_</p> <p>5. Class A_</p> <p>a. Depth to groundwater > 5 feet_</p> <p>6. Class B_</p> <p>a. Depth to groundwater > 10 feet or_</p> <p>b. > 40 feet if applied to gravel, coarse or medium sands, or sands with less than 15% coarse fragments</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>State regs same as 40 CFR 503.14 (b), but exempts EQ: Cannot apply non-EQ biosolids to land that is flooded, frozen, or snow-covered, so that the bulk biosolids enter a wetland or other navigable waters, unless permitted under CWA or by AZPDES</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>Non-EQ biosolids: _</p> <p>1. Cannot be applied to soil with pH < 6.5 unless treated by certain procedures or used for reclamation_</p> <p>2. Cannot be applied to land with > 6% slope, unless permitted or runoff doesn't reach navigable waters _</p> <p>3. Application rate cannot application rate be greater than the agronomic rate of the vegetation or crop grown on the site_</p> <p>4. Cannot apply domestic septage or any other bulk biosolids with less than 10% solids at a rate that exceeds the annual application rate; can't apply bulk biosolids of <10% solids to reclamation sites _</p> <p>5. Cannot apply any additional bulk biosolids before a crop is grown on the site if the site has received biosolids containing nitrogen at the equivalent of the agronomic rate appropriate for that crop_</p> <p>6. Cannot exceed the irrigation needs of the crop of an application site_</p> <p>7. pH of soil/biosolids mixture must be 5.0 or higher immediately after application to reclaimed sites_</p> <p>8. When applied to reclamation sites, cannot exceed 150 dry tons/acre at any portion of site.</p>
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?</p>	<p>No</p>

Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Biosolids must be sampled and tested for pollutants, pathogen reduction, organic and ammonium nitrogen, and vector attraction reduction according to 40 CFR 503.8 from annually to monthly, depending on the mass prepared, and retain records for at least 5 years.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Only Class EQ Biosolids can be sold or given away in a bag or other container for land application or applied on a lawn or home garden.
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects,</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Cannot apply biosolids with pollutant concentrations that exceed any of the ceiling concentrations established in Ceiling Concentrations Table in AAC Title 18, Chapter 9, Article 10, R18-9-1005. These are the same as Table 1 of 40 CFR 503.13, but add an additional limit for chromium._ - Cannot apply non-EQ biosolids sold or given away in a bag or other container to a site if any annual pollutant loading rate in Annual Pollutant Loading Rates Table 4 of 40 CFR 503.13 will be exceeded_ - Cannot apply non-EQ biosolids to a site if pollutant concentrations exceed Monthly Average Pollution Concentration Table levels or if any cumulative pollutant loading rate exceeds Cumulative Pollutant Loading Rates Table, both in 40 CFR 503.13.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	Yes
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Regulations on how to transport and report spills, but not on where cargo can go. For larger facilities, the amount of biosolids distributed must be reported to the Department.
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Not Permitted
Other regulatory details	No other information

<p><i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Arkansas	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Arkansas Department of Energy and Environment, Division of Environmental Quality (DEQ)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	State adopts 40 CFR 503. The DEQ has technical requirements for land application/storage of biosolids, but these are not prescribed by regulation, thus not addressed here. The website is located here: https://www.adeq.state.ar.us/water/permits/nodischarge/individual/ . The permitting application requires additional regulations on setbacks and slope: https://www.adeq.state.ar.us/water/permits/pdfs/waste-storage_-land-application-application-and-instructions.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	State adopts definitions of 40 CFR 503
Biosolids classes	State adopts definitions of 40 CFR 504
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 100 feet from streams including intermittent streams, ponds, lakes, springs, sinkholes, rock outcrops, wells and water supplies_ * 300 feet from extraordinary resource waters_ * 50 feet from property lines unless waived_ * 500 feet from existing neighboring occupied buildings unless waived
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Land application prohibited when soils are saturated; frozen; covered with ice or snow; during precipitation events; or when precipitation is imminent (greater than 50% chance of precipitation predicted by the nearest National Weather Service station) within a 24-hour period. Phosphorus limited in nutrient surplus areas.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No

Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	No
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	No
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	No
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	Only in Nutrient Surplus Areas.
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	Permitted
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these</p>	Undetermined

<p>regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Industrial Waste is regulated by DEQ. The AR Department of Health regulates septage. The AR Department of Agriculture regulates soil amendments and fertilizers.</p>

California	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	* California State Water Resources Control Board (land application)_ * California Department of Food and Agriculture (fertilizer regulation)_ * California Department of Resources Recycling and Recovery (composting)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Links to regulations	* Water Quality Order No. 2004-0012-DWQ (General Order):_ https://casaweb.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/01/Biosolids-General-Order-2004-0012-DWQ-.pdf _ * Section 13274 of the California Water Code:_ https://law.justia.com/codes/california/2011/wat/division-7/13260-13275/13274/
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage sludge" that has been treated and tested and shown to be capable of being beneficially and legally used as a soil amendment for agriculture, silviculture, horticulture, and land reclamation activities as specified under 40 CFR Part 503. "Septage" is not included in the land application General Order.
Biosolids classes	* Exceptional Quality biosolids (Class EQ) meet metals standards, Class A pathogen reduction standards, and vector attraction reduction standards contained in 40 CFR Part 503.13 (Table 3), 40 CFR Part 503.32, and 40 CFR Part 503.33, respectively._ * Class A biosolids meet the vector attraction and pollution concentration limits specified in 40 CFR Part 503 and pathogen reduction standards specified in 40 CFR Part 503.32(a). Only Class A biosolids not meeting the requirements contained in Table 3 of 40 CFR Part 503.13 are covered by the General Order._ * Class B biosolids meet the vector attraction and meeting pollution concentration limits specified in 40 CFR Part 503 and pathogen reduction standards specified in 40 CFR Part 503.32(b).
Other Definitions	Agronomic Rate: The nitrogen requirements of a plant needed for optimal growth and production, as cited in professional publications for California or recommended by the County Agricultural Commissioner, a Certified Agronomist or Certified Soil Scientist.
State Regulatory Details	

<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No discharge of biosolids from the storage or application areas to adjacent land areas not regulated by the General Order, to surface waters, or to surface water drainage courses_ * Irrigation water runoff from the permitted side is prohibited for 30 days after application of biosolids if vegetation in the application area and along the path of runoff does not provide 33 feet of unmowed grass or similar vegetation to prevent the movement of biosolids from the application site_ * 10 feet from property lines, waiver possible_ * 500 feet from domestic water supply wells, partial waiver possible_ * 100 feet from non-domestic water supply wells, partial waiver possible_ * 50 feet from public roads and occupied onsite residences, _ * 100 feet from surface waters, including wetlands, creeks, ponds, lakes, underground aqueducts, and marshes, _ * 33 feet from primary agricultural drainage ways, _ * 500 feet from occupied non-agricultural buildings and off-site residences, partial waiver possible_ * 400 feet from a domestic water supply reservoir, _ * 200 feet from a primary tributary to a domestic water supply, _ * 2,500 feet from any domestic surface water supply intake, and _ * 500 feet from enclosed water bodies that could be occupied by pupfish_ * No application of Class B biosolids within an area defined in the General Order as having a high potential for public exposure unless the biosolids are injected into the soil
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The application of biosolids to water-saturated or frozen ground or during periods of precipitation that induces runoff from the permitted site is prohibited_ * Biosolids less than 75% moisture must not be applied during periods when the surface wind speed exceeds 25 miles per hour as determined by the nearest calibrated regional weather station (e.g., airport, CIMS)_ * As part of the pre-application, an adverse weather and alternative plan must be submitted that details when biosolids can't be applied due to adverse weather or other conditions
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Application of biosolids at rates in excess of the nitrogen requirements of the vegetation or at rates that would degrade ground water is prohibited except in certain soil reclamation projects, as determined on a case-by-case basis, or for biosolids research projects_ * The application of Class B biosolids containing a moisture content of less than 50 percent is prohibited _

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The application of biosolids in areas where biosolids are subject to gully erosion or washout off site is prohibited_ * The application of biosolids to slopes exceeding 25 percent is prohibited_ * If biosolids are applied to a site where the soil will be tilled, biosolids must be incorporated within 24 hours after application in arid areas and in non-arid areas during the time period beginning May 1 and ending October 31 and within 48 hours in non-arid areas during the remaining time period _ * If biosolids are applied to ground surfaces having a slope greater than ten percent (10%) or if required by the RWQCB Executive Officer, a report, including an erosion control plan, has to be prepared and complied with._ * Structures conveying tail water must be designed and maintained to minimize any field erosion. Tail water structures must be boarded and wrapped with plastic prior to any biosolids application but removed after biosolids incorporation into the soil._ * The discharge of tail water or field runoff is prohibited within 30 days _ <p>after application of Class B biosolids for areas where biosolids have not been incorporated into the soil and where there is not a minimum of 33 feet of unmowed grass or similar vegetation bordering the application area and along the path of runoff to prevent movement of biosolids particles from the application site. For sites where the topography slopes are greater than 10 percent, the minimum width of vegetative border will be suggested by the mandatory erosion plan._</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The permit pre-application requires an erosion hazard report to determine whether soils could be degraded or land productivity reduced._ * The permit pre-application also requires a report from a certified soil scientist or a certified agronomist which evaluates the potential effects including potential nutrient imbalances, metals phytotoxicity, and excessive salinity on land productivity, with recommendations.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No

Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	* Required as part of the pre-application report submitted for each application area and includes metals, pH, salinity, Total NPK, total solids, fecal coliform, Ammonia N, etc.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	* Grazing of domesticated animals must be deferred for at least 60 days after application of biosolids in areas with average daily (daytime) air temperatures exceeding 50°F or be deferred for at least 90 days after land application where such conditions are not met_ * Grazing of milking animals used for producing unpasteurized milk for human consumption is prevented for 12 months after Class B application if the field is used as pasture
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	Yes
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	* Mixtures that contain biosolids used as a soil amendment to continuous fields/plots greater than 20 acres for agricultural, silvicultural, horticultural, and land reclamation activities and where the said fields/plots are owned or operated by the same person, company, or partnership are regulated under the general order so long as either 1) greater than or equal to 50% (dw) of the mixture is EQ and is applied at more than 10 dry-tons per acre per year or 2) less than 50% (dw) of the mixture is EQ and is applied at more than 20 dry-tons per acre per year. More generally, the General Order can be applied to EQ on a case-by-case basis.
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects,</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	* Discharges cannot cause or threaten to cause pollution, as defined in CWC section 13050 nor can they violate Health and Safety Code section 25249.5_ * Biosolids can't be applied in amounts exceeding the Risk Assessment Acceptable Soil Concentration as described below: _ BC= RP- 1.8(BS) _ Where: _ BC=Background Cumulative Adjusted Loading Rate(Lbs./Acre) _ RP=40 CFR Part 503 Cumulative Pollutant Loading Rate (Lbs./Acre) _ _ BS=Actual Site Background Site Soil Concentration (mg/Kg) _ and values for RP on a pollutant-specific basis are specified by Discharge Specification 5 in the General Order.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	The discharger must avoid the use of haul routes near residential land uses to the extent possible. If the use of haul routes near residential land uses cannot be avoided, project-related truck traffic is restricted to daylight hours
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	* The General Order is not applicable to areas that have been defined in the State law and the CCR as jurisdictional waters or preserves or have been addressed through acts specifically intended to preserve and manage the resource_

	<p>* If human remains of Native American origin are discovered during project activities, the discharger must comply with State laws relating to the disposition of Native American burials, which are under the jurisdiction of the Native American Heritage Commission (Pub. Res. Code Section 5097)_</p> <p>* Application of biosolids at rates in excess of the nitrogen requirements of the vegetation may be allowed for soil reclamation projects</p>
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General Assessment Questions

<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Colorado Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Colorado Department of Public Health and Environment
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	* Colorado Water Quality Control Act:_ https://cdphe.colorado.gov/wqcc-regulations-and-policies_ * Code of Colorado Regulations, 5 CCR 1002-64:_ http://www.sos.state.co.us/CCR/GenerateRulePdf.do?ruleVersionId=5757&file Name=5%20CCR%201002-64
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means the accumulated treated residual product resulting from a domestic wastewater treatment works. Biosolids does not include grit or screenings from a wastewater treatment works, commercial or industrial sludges (regardless of whether the sludges are combined with domestic sewage), sludge generated during treatment of drinking water, or domestic or industrial septage.
Biosolids classes	* Class A is as defined in accordance with 40 CFR 503 Subpart D_ * Class B is as defined in accordance with 40 CFR 503 Subpart D_ * Colorado does recognize Class A and Class B biosolids in relation to pathogen destruction
Other Definitions	"Agronomic Rate" means the rate at which biosolids are applied to land such that the amount of nitrogen required by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop or vegetation grown on the land is supplied over a defined growth period, and such that the amount of nitrogen in the biosolids which passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown to groundwater is minimized.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much</i>	* No application of biosolids for beneficial use on land located upgradient, and within one linear mile, of a point at which surface waters are diverted for use in a public water system, unless either runoff from within the application site does not drain into the body of water which is diverted or a site operating plan is

<p><i>distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>submitted that describes measures that prevent runoff during any storm event of greater frequency than the 10 year 24 hour storm event from the application site into the body of water which is diverted_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No application upgradient and within 300 feet of a reservoir classified for Class I Recreational Use by the Water Quality Control Commission_ * No application within 200 feet of any body of surface water, including intermittent streambeds when standing or running water is present in the streambed, unless application is made by either subsurface injection, or by surface application which is followed by immediate incorporation, or a site operating plan is prepared, and submitted with the Letter of Intent to Use or Distribute Biosolids which describes measures which prevent runoff from the application site into the body of water_ * No application within 50 feet of any water body or perennial streambed, or any intermittent streambed when standing or running water is present in the streambed_ * No application within 33 feet of any dry streambed (excludes cultivated land)_ * No application within 100 feet of a private domestic water supply well or within 300 feet of a community supply well when applied to agricultural land_ * No application within 300 feet of a private domestic water supply well or within 1,500 feet upgradient of a community supply well when applied for reclamation of disturbed land_ * No application land which is underlain by groundwater where the annual high groundwater table is within five feet of the surface of the land.
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Application of biosolids to frozen, ice-covered, or snow-covered sites where the slope of the site exceeds six percent is prohibited._ * Application to frozen, ice-covered, or snow-covered land where the slope of such land is greater than three percent and is less than or equal to six percent is prohibited unless there is 80 percent vegetative ground cover or approval is obtained via a runoff containment plan.
<p>Agronomic/L and-related State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</p>	<p>For Agricultural Land_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No application on agricultural land on slopes in excess of 15 percent_ * If biosolids are less than 6% solids and slope is between 5-9%, then they must be incorporated within 24 hours, subsurface injected, or a site operating plan must be approved. _ * If biosolids are less than 6% solids and slope is 9% to 15%, then they must be subsurface injected or a site operating plan must be approved. _ * If biosolids are 6% or greater solids and slope is 9% to 15%, then they can be surface applied if vegetative cover is established or a uniform crop residue covers greater than 60%, or a site operating plan must be approved. _

	<p>For Reclamation on Disturbed Land_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No application for reclamation on disturbed land which exhibits slopes in excess of 30 percent_ * Application of biosolids with 6% or greater solids content requires incorporation within 24 hours or an approved site operating plan if the slope is 9% to 15%_ * Application of biosolids with <6% solids content is prohibited if slope is greater than 16%_ * Application of biosolids with <6% solids content requires subsurface injection or an approved site operating plan if the slope is between 9-15%_ * Application of biosolids with <6% solids content requires immediate incorporation, subsurface injection, or an approved site operating plan if the slope is between 5-9%_ <p>_</p> <p>Soils_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Application requires that soil is pH 6 or greater when biosolids are being applied for beneficial use for food crops_ * For irrigated ag land, the depth of suitable soil must be at least 3 feet_ * For agricultural land cultivated in dryland crops, or for rangeland, the depth of suitable soil must be a minimum of eighteen (18) inches_ * For reclamation of disturbed land the depth of suitable soil is a minimum of twelve (12) inches_ <p>_</p> <p>Nutrient Management_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Nitrogen application to ag land can't exceed the agronomic rate (defined in 5 CCR 1002-64.15 H(4)) for the crop or vegetation cultivated, as determined in a manner acceptable to the Division_ * Nitrogen application to reclaimed/disturbed land can't exceed the agronomic rate (defined in 5 CCR 1002-64.15 H(4)) for the vegetation established, except that such application rate may be based upon an aggregate agronomic need representing the initial five years after application occurs or as justified in an operational plan approved by the Division. The Division can apply more stringent restrictions in the latter case._ * If soil pH > 6.5, available phosphorus content of the soil must not exceed 80 ppm, if using a sodium bicarbonate extraction, or 40 ppm, if using an AB-DTPA extraction, unless otherwise approved by the Division _ * If soil pH is 6.5 or less, available phosphorus content of the soil must not exceed 120 ppm, if using Bray P1, or 200 ppm, if using Mehlich 3, unless otherwise approved by the Division
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids</p>	<p>No</p>

can be applied?	
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	Yes
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/l and application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on</i>	<p>* Required yearly if annual production is less than 319 dry short tons/yr, quarterly if between 319 and 1650 dst/yr, every two months if between 1650 and 16500 dst/yr, and monthly if 16500 or more dst/yr_</p> <p>* Analysis must include total solids, pH, total P, total K, metals, volatile solids, and organic nitrogen, total ammonia and nitrate as N.</p>

<i>biosolids before application.</i>	
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	<p>* Land application requires that biosolids meet Table 1 Ceiling Concentration Limits, meet at least one of the vector attraction reduction criteria that are enumerated in 40 CFR 503.33 (b), and either 1) are Class A for pathogens if applied to a public contact site or 2) are Class B for pathogens if applied to agricultural or disturbed land_</p> <p>* Biosolids can only be marketed to the public for unrestricted use if they meet Table 3 Pollutant Concentration Limits, Class A pathogen requirements, and at least one of the vector attraction reduction criteria that are enumerated in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8)_</p> <p>* Biosolids can only be marketed to the public for restricted use if they meet Table 1 Pollutant Concentration Limits, Class A pathogen requirements and at least one of the vector attraction reduction criteria that are enumerated in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8)</p>
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503.33

<p><i>beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503.32</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location</i></p>	<p>None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows</p>

<p><i>to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>No formal plan required</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Not Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>Biosolids may not be stored for a period of more than two years before removed for use or distributed</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>

<p>or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>Yes. Counties may regulate.</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not</p>	<p>No</p>

biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.

Connecticut Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Connecticut Department of Environmental Protection
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Connecticut relies on 40 CFR 503 regulations. Almost all of the wastewater solids produced in CT are incinerated
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No

Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions	No

<p>(e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Delaware Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Delaware Department of Natural Resources and Environmental Control (DNREC)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	7 DE Admin. Code 7103, The Regulations Governing the Land Treatment of Waste (Starting at section 100): http://regulations.delaware.gov/AdminCode/title7/7000/7100/7103.pdf – Delaware Nutrient Management Law: http://delcode.delaware.gov/title3/c022/ _ Delaware Regulations on nutrient management: http://regulations.delaware.gov/AdminCode/title3/1200/ _ Biosolids application is mainly exempt from the nutrient management law; however, we mirror many requirements from the nutrition management regulations
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	* "Sewage" means water-carried human or animal wastes from septic tanks, water closets, residences, buildings, industrial establishments, or other places, together with such groundwater infiltration, subsurface water, admixture of industrial wastes or other wastes as may be present._ * "Sewage sludge" means sludges which derives in whole or in part from sewage._ * "Sludge" means the accumulated semi-liquid suspension, settled solids, or dried residue of these solids that is deposited from (a) liquid waste in a municipal or industrial treatment plant.
Biosolids classes	"Exceptional Quality (EQ) Sludge" sludge that has been stabilized (as per Subsection 603) by a Further Reduction Pathogens, meets one of the Vector Attraction Reduction Requirements specified in Subsection 604(88.1-8) and contains lower metal concentrations than the allowable Pollutant Concentration specified Table 402-3, which is more restrictive than 40 CFR 503._ Class A must conform to the requirements Section 134, which is the same as 40 CFR 503.32_ Class B but must conform to the requirements in Section 133, which is the same as 40 CFR 503.32
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" is the whole sludge application rate (dry weight basis) designed: _

	<p>1. To provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop, or vegetation grown on the land; and_</p> <p>2. To minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage _</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Domestic septage" is either liquid or solid material removed from a septic tank, cesspool, portable toilet, Type III marine sanitation device, or similar treatment works that receives only domestic sewage. Domestic septage does not include liquid or solid material removed from a septic tank, cesspool, holding tank, or similar treatment works that receives either commercial wastewater or industrial wastewater and does not include grease removed from a grease trap at a restaurant.</p>
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State Regulatory Details

<p>Setbacks</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>Unless treated by Process To Further Reduce Pathogens (40 CFR 503, Appendix B), sewage sludge may not be land applied within the following buffer zones:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 200 feet of an occupied off-site dwelling, if surface applied, or 100 feet if surface injected._ * 100 feet of an occupied on-site dwelling, if surface applied, or 50 feet, if surface injected_ * 100 feet of potable wells or 25 feet of non-potable wells or drainage ditches_ * 25 feet of public roads, if surface applied, or 15 feet, if surface injected_ * 50 feet of property lines, bedrock outcrops, streams, tidal waters, or other water bodies if surface applied, or 25 feet (this should be 33 feet as required in the 503 regulations but our regulations need to be amended to make the correction. Our regulations do currently state 25 feet), if surface injected_ <p>The Department may require increased buffer distances or may reduce buffer distances, and may set buffer zones between sludge boundaries and other land uses such as wetlands. _</p> <p>No sludge application to a site unless the site complies with all of the following:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The soils must have a minimum depth from surface to impermeable strata of 20 inches._ * The site must have a minimum depth from surface to seasonal high water table of 20 inches. The operator may establish this minimum depth through the use of a tile drain system. An NPDES permit will be required for the discharge from the tile drain. Sites where the minimum depth from surface to seasonal high water table is less than 20 inches but no less than 12 inches may be considered if application to the soil is restricted to:_ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o May, June, July or August and appropriate vegetation is established and harvested as practicable_ o Those periods when actual water table depth is at least 20 inches below the maximum depth of tillage to be used for the vegetation._
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Slopes to be utilized for sludge application may not exceed 15 percent, except that the Department may allow slopes of up to 30 percent for forest systems in the permit._ o Soil pH is to be adjusted to values of 6.2 or above unless the natural climatic conditions and soil chemistry preclude such values. In these cases, lime additions suitable to the vegetation used are to be applied in conjunction with annual metal monitoring of that vegetation._ o For silvicultural application the soil may remain at ambient pH provided sufficient litter exist on the forest tract floor as determined by the Department._ o If the site is planted with nursery crops that require a pH of less than 6.2, the Department may approve a soil pH of 5.8 or greater in the permit
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>No sludge application when the ground is frozen, unless the Department has approved such application in the permit and all of the following conditions exist:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The slopes at the site do not exceed three percent._ * The site contains sufficient vegetation or a well-established cover crop to prevent runoff of sludge_ * No sludge storage capacity or other means of storage or disposal exists at the generating facility._ * No run-off.
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sludge must be spread evenly over the site using conventional agronomic equipment such as manure spreaders, spray equipment, or other applicators, or by commercial equipment specifically designed for sludge application on agricultural land._ * Sludge or products derived from sewage sludge must be applied to the soil surface or incorporated in a manner that prevents unreasonable nuisance or odor conditions._ * The sludge applied must be incorporated into the soil as required in Section 600 or by the end of each working day except under the following circumstances when liquid sludge is surface sprayed, odors and nuisances are controlled, and the Department determines that there will be no adverse impact on the environment or public health; or site management plans such as no till farming or the presence of an established crop precludes sludge incorporation, adequate site features exist to preclude sludge migration from the site, odors and nuisances are controlled, and the Department determines that there will be no adverse impact on the environment or public health._ * For the surface application of sludge for top or side dressing on hayfields, for pastures, for cover crops, in forests or for no-till crops when the previous no-till crop was harvested for grain in a manner that left adequate crop residue, the Department may either approve a

	greater than 24 hour time period for incorporating sludge into the soil as part of the permit, or not require incorporation as part of the permit.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	Yes
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Monitoring frequency is the same as 40 CFR 503, subject to Departmental discretion. Transportation of sludge requires a reporting of percent solids, pH, dry weight, concentration of total nitrogen, ammonium, nitrate, total phosphorous, total potassium, and metals including chromium and molybdenum (all 10 metals from the original 503).
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No

<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>* Only exceptional quality sludge may be applied to lawns and home gardens. Owing to tighter state restrictions on metals, this is more restrictive than 40 CFR 503._ * Bagged sludge given away or sold must meet Class EQ pathogen and vector reduction requirements, and either the high quality pollutant concentration limits in Table 2._ — For Class B sites, many requirements including detailed soils work is required for permitting a specific application field (Section 119).</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>* Sludges containing more than 10 ppm of PCB's must be incorporated into the soil upon application, and sludges containing more than 50 ppm of PCBs are subject to TOSCA requirements. _ * See metals limits in Section 116.2. Notably, the state sets limits on chromium and molybdenum and has more stringent monthly average limits on selenium than 40 CFR 503.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a</i></p>	<p>* Nutrients in Class B sludge must be applied in accordance with section 138. Additionally, phosphorus is managed Fields with "high" phosphorus soil levels as defined by Title 3, Chapter 22 of the Delaware Code (the Nutrient Management Law) and the Delaw</p>

<i>biosolids application program</i>	
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Not Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	Land application permits are required to apply nonsanitary sludge (land treatable waste products such as dissolved air flotation solids, brewery wastewater, grease trap waste, etc.).
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	No
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your	Yes. Septage is similar to the 503 but more stringent_ Composts that do not contain sewage sludge are regulated under a different regulation than Delaware's sludge regulations but are regulated.

state? If so, please briefly describe.	
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Federal Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	EPA
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Other
Links to regulations	US Code of Federal Regulations, Chapter 40 Part 503: https://www.ecfr.gov/current/title-40/chapter-I/subchapter-O/part-503
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Not Applicable
Other regulator info	These regulations pertain to all US states
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" are not defined at the federal level, rather "sewage sludge" is used. "Sewage sludge" is solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works. "Sewage sludge" includes, but is not limited to, domestic septage; scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes; and a material derived from "sewage sludge". "Sewage sludge" does not include ash generated during the firing of "sewage sludge" in a "sewage sludge" incinerator or grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic "sewage" in a treatment works.
Biosolids classes	Not Applicable
Other Definitions	<p>Agronomic rate is the whole sludge application rate (dry weight basis) designed: <u></u></p> <p>(1) To provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop, or vegetation grown on the land; and <u></u></p> <p>(2) To minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the ground water. <u></u></p> <p>–</p> <p>Land application is the spraying or spreading of sewage sludge onto the land surface; the injection of sewage sludge below the land surface; or the incorporation of sewage sludge into the soil so that the sewage sludge can either condition the soil or fertilize crops or vegetation grown in the soil. <u></u></p> <p>–</p> <p>Domestic septage is either liquid or solid material removed from a septic tank, cesspool, portable toilet, Type III marine sanitation device, or similar treatment works that receives only domestic sewage. Domestic septage does not include liquid or solid material removed from a septic tank, cesspool, or similar treatment works that receives either commercial wastewater or industrial</p>

	wastewater and does not include grease removed from a grease trap at a restaurant.
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>The following regulation does not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8). * Bulk sewage sludge may not be applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site that is 10 meters or less from waters of the United States, as defined in 40 CFR 122.2, unless otherwise specified by the permitting authority.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	No
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>The following regulation does not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8). Bulk sewage sludge may not be applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site that is flooded, frozen, or snow-covered so that the bulk sewage sludge enters a wetland or other waters of the United States, as defined in 40 CFR 122.2, except as provided in a permit issued pursuant to section 402 or 404 of the CWA.</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>The following regulation does not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8). * Bulk sewage sludge must be applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site at a whole sludge application rate that is equal to or less than the agronomic rate for the bulk sewage sludge, unless, in the case of a reclamation site, otherwise specified by the permitting authority.</p>
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	No
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?</p>	No

Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	<p>The following regulations do not apply when a bulk material derived from sewage sludge is applied to land or a material derived from sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the sewage sludge from which the material is derived meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8)._</p> <p>* The frequency of monitoring for the pollutants listed in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4 of §503.13; the pathogen density requirements in §503.32(a) and §503.32(b)(2); and the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(4) and §503.33 (b)(7) through (b)(8) must be:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Yearly, if amount of bulk sewage sludge applied to the land or the amount of sewage sludge prepared for sale or give-away in a bag or other container for application to the land is greater than zero but less than 290 metric tons per 365 day period_ o Once per quarter, if amount of bulk sewage sludge applied to the land or the amount of sewage sludge prepared for sale or give-away in a bag or other container for application to the land is equal to or greater than 290 but less than 1,500 metric tons per 365 day period_ o Once per 60 days, if amount of bulk sewage sludge applied to the land or the amount of sewage sludge prepared for sale or give-away in a bag or other container for application to the land is equal to or greater than 1,500 but less than 15,000 metric tons per 365 day period_ o Once per month, if amount of bulk sewage sludge applied to the land or the amount of sewage sludge prepared for sale or give-away in a bag or other container for application to the land is equal to or greater than 15,000 metric tons per 365 day period_

	<p>* After the sewage sludge has been monitored for two years at the frequency in Table 1 of §503.16, the permitting authority may reduce the frequency of monitoring for pollutant concentrations and for the pathogen density requirements in §503.32(a)(5)(ii) and (a)(5)(iii)._</p> <p>* Domestic septage. If either the pathogen requirements in §503.32(c)(2) or the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(12) are met when domestic septage is applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site, each container of domestic septage applied to the land must be monitored for compliance with those requirements._</p> <p>* As part of recordkeeping requirements, the following quantities must be known: concentration of each pollutant listed in Table 3 of §503.13</p>
<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<p>The following regulations apply to Class B sewage sludge and domestic septage:_</p> <p>* Food crops with harvested parts that touch the sewage sludge/soil mixture and are totally above the land surface must not be harvested for 14 months after application of sewage sludge._</p> <p>* Food crops with harvested parts below the surface of the land must not be harvested for 20 months after application of sewage sludge when the sewage sludge remains on the land surface for four months or longer prior to incorporation into the soil._</p> <p>* Food crops with harvested parts below the surface of the land must not be harvested for 38 months after application of sewage sludge when the sewage sludge remains on the land surface for less than four months prior to incorporation into the soil._</p> <p>* Food crops, feed crops, and fiber crops must not be harvested for 30 days after application of sewage sludge._</p> <p>* Animals must not be grazed on the land for 30 days after application of sewage sludge._</p> <p>* Turf grown on land where sewage sludge is applied must not be harvested for one year after application of the sewage sludge when the harvested turf is placed on either land with a high potential for public exposure or a lawn, unless otherwise specified by the permitting authority._</p> <p>* Public access to land with a high potential for public exposure must be restricted for one year after application of sewage sludge._</p> <p>* Public access to land with a low potential for public exposure must be restricted for 30 days after application of sewage sludge._</p> <p>* The pH of domestic septage applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site must be raised to 12 or higher by alkali addition and, without the addition of more alkali, must remain at 12 or higher for 30 minutes and the site restrictions in §503.32 (b)(5)(i) through (b)(5)(iv) must be met.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>between application and harvesting crops?</p>	
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to a lawn or a home garden._ * The Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a) must be met when sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land._ * The requirements in either §503.32 (c)(1) or (c)(2) must be met when domestic septage is applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site._ * One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(10) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site._ * One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(8) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to a lawn or a home garden._ * One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(8) must be met when sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land._ The vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(9), (b)(10), or (b)(12) must be met when domestic septage is applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site._ <p>—</p> <p>The following regulation does not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8)._</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Bulk sewage sludge may not be applied to the land if it is likely to adversely affect a threatened or endangered species listed under section 4 of the Endangered Species Act or its designated critical habitat.
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(10) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site._ * One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(8) must be met when bulk sewage sludge is applied to a lawn or a home garden or when sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land._ * One of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33 (b)(9), (b)(10), or (b)(12) must be met when domestic septage is applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site.

<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>* Bulk sewage sludge or sewage sludge sold or given away in a bag or other container may not be applied to the land if the concentration of any pollutant in the sewage sludge exceeds the ceiling concentration for the pollutant in Table 1 of §503.13._</p> <p>* If bulk sewage sludge is applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site, either:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The cumulative loading rate for each pollutant may not exceed the cumulative pollutant loading rate for the pollutant in Table 2 of §503.13; or_ o The concentration of each pollutant in the sewage sludge may not exceed the concentration for the pollutant in Table 3 of §503.13._ <p>* If bulk sewage sludge is applied to a lawn or a home garden, the concentration of each pollutant in the sewage sludge may not exceed the concentration for the pollutant in Table 3 of §503.13._</p> <p>* If sewage sludge is sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land, either:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The concentration of each pollutant in the sewage sludge may not exceed the concentration for the pollutant in Table 3 of §503.13; or_ o The product of the concentration of each pollutant in the sewage sludge and the annual whole sludge application rate for the sewage sludge may not cause the annual pollutant loading rate for the pollutant in Table 4 of §503.13 to be exceeded. The procedure used to determine the annual whole sludge application rate is presented in appendix A of 40 CFR 503 Part B._ <p>_</p> <p>The following regulations do not apply to sewage sludge or material derived from sewage sludge, whether either is provided in bulk or sold or given away in a bag or other container, if the product meets the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in §503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8)._</p> <p>_</p> <p>* No application of bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site if any of the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has been reached._</p> <p>* No application of domestic septage to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site during a 365 day period if the annual application rate in §503.13(c) has been reached during that period._</p> <p>* Before bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) is applied to the land, a determination must be made by the state permitting authority to determine whether bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant</p>

	<p>loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has been applied to the site since July 20, 1993._</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o (ii) If bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has not been applied to the site since July 20, 1993, the cumulative amount for each pollutant listed in Table 2 of §503.13 may be applied to the site in accordance with §503.13(a)(2)(i)._ o (iii) If bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has been applied to the site since July 20, 1993, and the cumulative amount of each pollutant applied to the site in the bulk sewage sludge since that date is known, the cumulative amount of each pollutant applied to the site must be used to determine the additional amount of each pollutant that can be applied to the site in accordance with §503.13(a)(2)(i)._ o (iv) If bulk sewage sludge subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in §503.13(b)(2) has been applied to the site since July 20, 1993, and the cumulative amount of each pollutant applied to the site in the bulk sewage sludge since that date is not known, an additional amount of each pollutant must not be applied to the site in accordance with §503.13(a)(2)(i)._ <p>– o</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>None</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>No formal plan required</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Varies by state</p>
<p>Other regulatory details</p>	<p>No other information</p>

<p><i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Florida	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Florida Department of Environmental Protection
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Florida Administrative Code, Chapter 62-640: https://www.flrules.org/gateway/readFile.asp?sid=0&tid=0&cno=62-640&caid=484920&type=4&file=62-640.doc
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means the solid, semisolid, or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic wastewater in a domestic wastewater treatment facility, formerly known as "domestic wastewater residuals" or "residuals." Not included is the treated effluent or reclaimed water from a domestic wastewater treatment plant. Also not included are solids removed from pump stations and lift stations, screenings and grit removed from the preliminary treatment components of domestic wastewater treatment facilities, other solids as defined in subsection 62-640.200(31), F.A.C., and ash generated during the incineration of biosolids. Biosolids include products and treated material from biosolids treatment facilities and septage management facilities regulated by the Department.
Biosolids classes	"Class A biosolids" means biosolids that meet the Class A pathogen reduction requirements of paragraph 62-640.600(1)(a), F.A.C., the vector attraction reduction requirements of paragraph 62-640.600(2)(a), F.A.C., and the parameter concentrations of paragraph 62-640.700(5)(a), F.A.C. The pathogen reduction requirements are the same as 40 CFR 503.32a, except alternative 4 is excluded and alternative 3 is only permitted with restrictions. "Class AA biosolids" means biosolids that meet the Class AA pathogen reduction requirements of paragraph 62-640.600(1)(a), F.A.C., the vector attraction reduction requirements of paragraph 62-640.600(2)(b), F.A.C., and the parameter concentrations of paragraphs 62-640.700(5)(a) and (b), F.A.C. The pathogen reduction requirements are the same as 40 CFR 503.32a, except alternative 4 is excluded and alternative 3 is only permitted with restrictions. The vector treatment requirements are the same as 40 CFR 503.33, except only methods 503.33(b)(1) through (8) are permitted.

	"Class B biosolids" means biosolids that meet the Class B pathogen reduction requirements of paragraph 62-640.600(1)(b), F.A.C., the vector attraction reduction requirements of paragraph 62-640.600(2)(a), F.A.C., and the parameter concentrations of paragraph 62-640.700(5)(a), F.A.C.
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	<p>For Class A and B biosolids: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * biosolids treated by alkaline addition must be applied by the best management practice of incorporation or injection unless the application area is located at a distance greater than one-quarter mile from the application site property line. Property owner permission can adjust this. _ * no application closer than 1,000 feet to any Class I water body, Outstanding Florida Water or Outstanding National Resource Water, or 200 feet from any other surface water of the state, with exceptions. The setback area must be vegetated. The 200 foot setback distance from surface waters can be reduced to 100 feet if the biosolids are injected or incorporated into the soil. _ * no application closer than 300 feet from any private drinking water supply well or 500 feet from any public drinking water supply well. _ * the land application zone and an area 200 feet wide adjacent to the application zone must contain no visible evidence of subsurface fractures, solution cavities, sink holes, excavation core holes, abandoned wells or any other natural or man-made conduits that could allow direct contamination of ground water. _ * A minimum unsaturated soil depth of two feet is required between the depth of biosolids placement and the water table level at the time the Class A or Class B biosolids are applied to the soil. _ <p>For Class B biosolids: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * no application within 300 feet of a building occupied by the general public. This distance can be reduced to 100 feet if biosolids are injected into the soil or if written permission is obtained from the building owner. _ * no application within 75 feet from property lines, unless applied to the medians or roadway shoulders of restricted public access roads.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	No application of biosolids during rain events that cause ponding or sheet flow, when ponding exists, or when surface soils are saturated
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Biosolids must be uniformly applied on a site_ * Topographic grades of the land application zone must be eight percent or less. If application site slopes exceed three percent in one or more application zones, biosolids must be injected or incorporated, unless otherwise permitted_ * no application on soils having a flooding frequency class of "frequent"² or "very frequent"², or on soils having a flooding duration class of "long"² or

	"very long," as given in soil surveys and as defined by the NRCS in Section 618.27 of the National Soil Survey Handbook, as of October 2009
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	Yes
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on</i>	* Testing required for total nitrogen/potassium/phosphorus, metals, pH, total solids, and calcium carbonate equivalent, if treated by alkaline addition. Frequency of testing depends on amount generated. Molybdenum must be measured with metals.

<p><i>biosolids before application.</i></p>	
<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Class A and Class B biosolids treated by alkaline addition must be land applied within 24 hours of delivery to the site_ * Plant nursery use of Class B biosolids is limited to plants which will not be sold to the public for 12 months after the last application of biosolids_ * Also have the other Class B grazing and harvesting restrictions that match Part 503_ * Public access restricted for one year
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Land application of biosolids cannot violate Florida surface water quality standards pursuant to Chapter 62-302, F.A.C., or ground water standards pursuant to Chapter 62-520, F.A.C._ * The treatment, management, transportation, use, land application, or disposal of biosolids cannot cause a violation of the odor prohibition in subsection 62-296.320(2), F.A.C._ * Land application of Class A and Class B biosolids is prohibited within the primary and secondary protection zones of the Wekiva Study Area in accordance with Rule 62-600.550, F.A.C. Application of Class AA biosolids that are distributed and marketed in accordance with Rule 62-640.850, F.A.C., is permissible._ * The land application of biosolids will not be authorized in the Lake Okeechobee watershed as defined in Section 373.4595(2)(j), F.S., unless the applicant for a site permit affirmatively demonstrates that the phosphorus in the biosolids will not add to phosphorus loadings in Lake Okeechobee or its tributaries. This prohibition does not apply to Class AA biosolids that are marketed and distributed as fertilizer products in accordance with Rule 62-640.850, F.A.C._ * The land application of biosolids will not be authorized in the Caloosahatchee River and St. Lucie River watersheds as defined in Sections 373.4595(2)(b) and (p), F.S., unless the applicant for a site permit affirmatively demonstrates that the nitrogen and phosphorus in the biosolids will not add to nitrogen and phosphorus loadings in the watershed. This prohibition does not apply to Class AA biosolids that are marketed and distributed as fertilizer products in accordance with Rule 62-640.850, F.A.C._ * If the biosolids must be blended with other materials to meet the Class AA criteria of paragraph 62-640.700(5)(b), F.A.C., the blending must be conducted by a Department permitted domestic wastewater treatment

	<p>facility or biosolids treatment facility before the biosolids are distributed or marketed._</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The pH of the biosolids soil mixture must be 5.0 or greater at the time Class A or Class B biosolids are applied_ * Application of Class B biosolids on roadway shoulders and medians is limited to restricted public access roads_ * The maximum application quantity of biosolids for land reclamation projects is limited to 50 dry tons/acre with such one-time reclamation project to be accomplished within a one-year period on any acre of a land reclamation site. When composted biosolids or biosolids blended with other soil amendment materials are used, only the biosolids portion of the blended product counts toward the 50 dry tons/acre limitation._ * Non-AA biosolids must incorporated into the soil within the same day as application to a reclamation site._ * Distributed and marketed biosolids must be Class AA and marketed as a fertilizer. Outside of the Lake Okeechobee, St. Lucie River, and Caloosahatchee River watersheds, Class AA composts can be enrolled and certified under the U.S. Composting Council's (USCC) Seal of Testing Assurance (STA) program instead of being a "fertilizer"²
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>State has slightly tighter restrictions on vector reduction for class AA biosolids than 40 CFR 503.33, but is otherwise the same</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>There is a notification requirement at the end of Rule 62-640.650. Must notify DEP and owners of grazing animals if cumulative molybdenum at a land application site exceeds 35.7 lbs. per acre.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>No</p>

Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Biosolids or biosolids products which are generated outside of Florida but imported to Florida are subject to the same provisions_ * Transportation of biosolids is regulated by the Florida Department of Transportation_ * Treatment of biosolids or septag
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	<p>Nutrient management plans are required or conservation plans in specific instances. Among other requirements NMPs must:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * be prepared and signed by a person certified by the NRCS for nutrient management planning
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Septage is generally regulated the same way, with exceptions_ * Biosolids co-composted with yard trash, wood chips or similar bulking agents are regulated as biosolids_ * Biosolids blended or mixed with other wastes are regulated as biosolids_ * No person can have more than one dry ton of unapplied Class AA biosolids or biosolids products distributed and marketed under Rule 62-640.850, F.A.C., on their property for more than seven days unless stored to prevent runoff of biosolids or stormwater that has been in contact with biosolids, violation of the odor prohibition in subsection 62-296.320(2), F.A.C., and vector attraction._ * no storage or stockpiling of Class A or B biosolids at a land application site within 1,320 feet of a building occupied by the general public, unless authorized
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate	Undetermined

<p>changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>Yes. Sec. 373.4595, F.S., but reflected in Ch. 62-640, F.A.C._ BMAPs for Priority Focus Areas (PFAs) of Outstanding Florida Springs (OFSs): search for "biosolids" (several times) in https://floridadep.gov/sites/default/files/Homosassa%20Chassahowitzka%20</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>Yes. Many counties do. Refer to department website map.</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Septage can be applied as biosolids under Chapter 62-640, F.A.C._ Biosolids composts are regulated under Ch. 62-640._ Solid waste composts and organics are regulated under Ch. 62-709 (solid waste regulations)._ Industrial wastewater sludges can be ap</p>

Georgia Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Georgia Department of Natural Resources, Environmental Protection Division (EPD)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Natural Resources
Links to regulations	*Rules and Regulations of the State of Georgia:_ http://rules.sos.state.ga.us/GAC/391-3-6 _ *Dept of Natural Resources, Environmental Protection:_ 391-3-6. Water Quality Control_ Rule 391-3-6-.17 Sewage Sludge (Biosolids) Requirements_ https://rules.sos.ga.gov/GAC/391-3-6-.17
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means any sewage sludge that fulfills all requirements under OGCA 391-3-6 and is used in a beneficial manner. This is greated sludge that meets Part 503 requirements for land application and is typically intended to be land applied as a soil amendment or fertilizer.
Biosolids classes	"Exceptional quality sludge" is sewage sludge that meets the pollutant concentrations in 40 CFR 503.13 Table 3, one of the Class A pathogen requirements in 40 CFR 503.32 and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8)._ Class A Sewage Sludge. To be classified as Class A with respect to pathogens the sewage sludge must meet the requirements in 40 CFR 503.32. The Class A pathogen requirements must be met either before or at the same time the vector attraction reduction requirements are met, with the exception of the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(6-8)._ Class B is used in accordance with 40 CFR 503.32
Other Definitions	"Sewage sludge" means solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic sewage or a combination of domestic sewage and industrial wastewater in a treatment works. Sewage sludge includes, but is not limited to domestic septage; scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes; any material derived from sewage sludge. Sewage sludge does not include ash generated during the firing of sewage sludge incinerator, grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works, treated effluent, or materials excluded from definition of "sewage sludge" by O.C.G.A. § 12-5-30-.3(a)(1)._ _

	<p>– "Agronomic rate" is the sludge application rate based on a dry weight basis determined: _</p> <p>1. to provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop or vegetation grown on the land; and_ 2. to minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the groundwater._</p> <p>– "Land application" or "applied to the land" means the spraying or spreading of sewage sludge on the land surface; the injection of sewage sludge below the land surface; or the incorporation of sewage sludge into the soil at agronomic rates for the purpose of soil conditioning or fertilization of crops or vegetation grown in the soil.</p>
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State Regulatory Details

<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>Site restrictions, buffer areas, and any additional EPD requirements defined in permits may apply to the land application of bulk sewage sludge. Reduction of buffer areas on sites where exceptional quality sludge is land applied will be considered by the EPD upon written request. However, in no case may bulk sewage sludge be applied to areas located 35 feet or less from waters of the State of Georgia.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>* Before bulk sewage sludge is land applied, the applier must contact the EPD to determine whether bulk sewage sludge has been previously applied to the site. If bulk sewage sludge has been previously applied to the site, the amount of mineralized nitrogen from previous sewage sludge applications that is available for crop uptake, as well as the amount of nitrogen from other sources that is available for crop uptake, must be taken into account in determining the agronomic loading rate.</p>
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?</p>	<p>Yes</p>

Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Representative sewage sludge samples must be analyzed in accordance with the methods contained in 40 CFR 503.8. Test methods used to determine toxicity, such as the Toxicity Characteristic Leachate Procedure, may be used to determine whether sewage sludge is hazardous, but must not be used for the purpose of determining compliance with any of the inorganic pollutant requirements contained in this paragraph.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants	* Biosolids from more than 1 source or septage cannot be applied to the same site within the same crop year (bulk EQ biosolids exempt).

<i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	No
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No

<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Hawaii	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	State of Hawaii, Department of Health Wastewater Branch
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Health
Links to regulations	Hawaii Administrative Rules - HAR 11-62-41-48: https://health.hawaii.gov/wastewater/files/2014/08/11-62_draft.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	Domestic septage has separate regulations under this section, including regulations on annual application rate. In 11-62-44
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	<p>* "Sewage sludge" means any solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue removed during the treatment of municipal wastewater or domestic sewage. Sewage sludge includes, but is not limited to, solids removed during primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment, scum, septage, portable toilet pumping, Type III Marine Sanitation device pumpings (33 Code of Federal Regulations Part 159), and sewage sludge products. Sewage sludge does not include grit, screenings, or ash generated during the incineration of sewage sludge.</p> <p>* "Wastewater sludge" has the same meaning as "sewage sludge".</p> <p>"Sewage" means wastewater.</p>
Biosolids classes	<p>"Exceptional quality sludge" means wastewater sludge that has been treated to a level specified in [these rules] this chapter in which it may be used with little or no restrictions for land application.</p> <p>The terms Class A and B are used in accordance with 40 CFR 503, except:</p> <p>HAR 11-62-46 has eliminated Alternative 3 for Class A and has restricted Alternative 4.</p> <p>"Non-exceptional quality wastewater sludge" means wastewater sludge that is not exceptional quality wastewater sludge. The Class A pathogen requirements in section 11-62-46(a) or the Class B pathogen requirements in 40 CFR §503.32(b) must be met for non-exceptional quality wastewater sludge.</p>
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some</i>	<p>For non-EQ sludge: _</p> <p>* No application within 50 ft of property lines or Waters of the United States, state waters, the ocean at the vegetation line, or any other surface water body_</p> <p>* No application within 500 ft of occupied building or dwelling_</p>

<i>feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	* No application within 1000 ft of potable water source serving public water systems_ * The land application of wastewater sludge must be at least five feet above the seasonal high groundwater table.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Exceptional quality sludge must be applied to the land at a rate that is less than ten dry tons per acre and equal to or less than the agronomic rate.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	To determine compliance with section 11-62- 42(a)(2), exceptional quality wastewater sludge must be monitored not more than sixty days before land application or being bagged for distribution unless otherwise specified by the director. _ _ Other tests follow 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event,</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>such as harvest or public access</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Limits are more restrictive as in Appendix D, Table IV. Chromium and molybdenum limits are set.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	Yes
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	Individual Wastewater Management Permit for Land Application of Bulk WW Sludge is required to submit a Nutrient Management Plan under the provisions of HAR Section 11-62-54.01(9), unless: WW Sludge is EQ and applied at < 10 dry metric tons; WW Sludge is
Incineration	Permitted

<p><i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>Currently approximately 39% of State of Hawaii's biosolids are utilized for beneficial reuse. The portion not direct beneficial reused is landfilled or taken to H-Power (Island of Oahu only) for energy generation.</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Idaho	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Idaho Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	The Environmental Protection and Health Act (EPHA), Idaho Code §§ 39-101, et seq., charges DEQ with protecting human health and the environment. Under the authority granted DEQ in the EPHA, and in accordance with the Idaho Administrative Procedures Act (Idaho Code §§ 67- 5200, et seq.), DEQ has adopted rules and published guidance. IDAPA 58.01.16, Wastewater Rules, and IDAPA 58.01.25, Idaho Pollutant Discharge Elimination System Rules, implement portions of the EPHA and include provisions for the protection of human health and the environment from contamination by the land application of municipal biosolids. In particular, IDAPA 58.01.16.650 regulates the use of sludge for soil augmentation and requires a DEQ-approved sludge disposal plan or a biosolids management plan. IDAPA 58.01.25 incorporates the Code of Federal Regulations (CFR), Title 40, Part 503, Standards for the Use or Disposal of Sewage Sludge. Together they establish standards and rules for the application of biosolids to the land.
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	“Sewage Sludge” is a solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue removed during municipal wastewater or domestic sewage treatment. Sewage sludge includes, but is not limited to, solids removed during primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment; scum; septage; portable toilet pumpings; type III marine sanitation device pumpings (33 CFR Part 159); and sewage sludge products. Sewage sludge does not include grit or screenings, or ash generated during sewage sludge incineration. (IDAPA 58.01.25.010.82)
Biosolids classes	Biosolids must meet either Class A or B pathogen requirements (per 40 CFR 503) for land application.
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	IDAPA 58.01.25 requires, via its reference to 40 CFR 503, a 10-meter buffer from waters of the US for Class B biosolids. No other buffer zones are specified in state regulations. DEQ’s Guidance for Land Application of Municipal Biosolids provides recommended buffer zones.

Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 504
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 505
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing	No

between application and harvesting crops?	
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	No
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Incineration is an option that is not being used within the state.

<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>A biosolids management plan is required that describes soil, geography, geology, climate, and procedures to prevent reduction of soil productivity, percolation of excess nutrients, and possible adverse health effects.</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Septage: The land application of domestic septage must be done in accordance with federal regulations (40 CFR Part 503) and Idaho rules (IDAPA 58.01.03 – Individual/Subsurface Sewage Disposal Rules and Rules for Cleaning of Septic Tanks) to ensure p</p>

Illinois Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Illinois Environmental Protection Agency (IEPA)_ Illinois Pollution Control Board
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Links to regulations	IL Administrative Rules - Title 35, Subtitle C, Chapter 2, Part 391:_ https://pcb.illinois.gov/slr/ipcbandiepaenvironmentalregulationstitle35#:~:text=Part%20391:%20Design%20Criteria%20For,III%20Northeastern%20Illinois%20Planning%20Commission
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulation or info	In 2015, the Illinois Legislature adopted legislation which recognized the Exceptional Quality biosolids criteria. The IEPA has not been delegated the authority over this legislation and therefore, EQ biosolids are not currently regulated under the IEPA Part 391 regulations
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Stabilized Sludge" is the product of biological, chemical, heat or other type of sludge treatment that results in a relatively nonputrescible and inoffensive material
Biosolids classes	Exceptional Quality biosolids is defined in the IL Environmental Protection Act as meeting the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of 40 CFR §503.13 and the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of §503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in

	§503.32(a); and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in §503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8).
Other Definitions	"Agronomic Rates for Sludge Application": An application rate of sludge sufficient to supply that quantity of plant nutrients that can reasonably be expected to be utilized by agricultural crops as determined pursuant to Section 391.410.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sludge application with immediate incorporation or injection must not be done closer than 100 feet from any occupied dwelling or 10 feet from the closest edge of traveled portions of a public road or outside roadway fence lines. _ * Sludge application with no immediate incorporation must not be done closer than 200 feet from any occupied dwelling or 20 feet from the closet edge of traveled portions of a primary and secondary public roads or 10 feet from the closest edge of lesser utilized public roads or outside roadway fence lines. _ * Sludge application by ridge and furrow must not be done closer than 200 feet from any occupied dwelling or the closest edge of traveled portions of a public road or outside roadway fence lines. _ * Sludge must not be applied on land which lies within 150 feet from wells used to supply potable water or other potable water supplies and 200 feet from surface waters or intermittent streams; or within one-fourth of a mile of any potable water supply wells located in consolidated bedrock such as limestone or sinkhole areas unless a 50 foot depth of non-sandy or non-gravelly unconsolidated material exists. _ * Sludge must not be applied or discharged to streams, waterways which are grassed or otherwise, or those flood plains having a return frequency more often than a 10 year frequency. _ * Sludge application by low pressure spray irrigation systems (less than 50 psi) must not be done closer than 200 feet from any occupied dwelling, closest edge of traveled portion of public road, surface waters, waterways or floodplains as measured from the outer boundary of the spray pattern. The wind velocity must be less than 15 mph during spray irrigation periods. _ * Sludge application by high pressure spray irrigation systems (>50 psi) must not be done closer than 1000 feet from any occupied dwelling, closest edge of traveled portion of public road, surface waters, waterways or floodplains as measured from the outer boundary of the spray pattern. The wind velocity must be less than 15 mph during spray irrigation periods.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes

<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sludge must not be applied on land: during precipitation or when precipitation is imminent; on land that has received greater than ¼ inch rainfall within the 24 hour period preceding the intended application time._ * Sludge must be incorporated within 48 hours or prior to any rainfall after application whichever is more restrictive._ * Wind direction and velocity, humidity and the day of the week must also be considered prior to sludge transport and applications with respect to neighboring activities._ * Frozen ground which is not ice or snow covered and has a slope of 5% or less may be used for winter spreading providing a 200 feet grassy area exists between the sludge applied land and any surface water or potable water supply well. _ * Sludge may be applied on ice or snow covered ground during emergency situations pursuant to an Agency permit only under the following conditions: _ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The treatment plant site does not have adequate storage facilities or sufficient springtime application period and the effluent may cause violations of their NPDES limits; _ o Sludge application site must not be fall plowed by mold board plow unless a 200 foot grassy area exists between the application site and any swale, waterway, surface water, or potable water supply well; _ o Slope of the application site does not exceed 5%; _ o Runoff control measures such as vegetative fence rows around the site, contour farming, terracing, catchment basins and buffer areas in the direction of surface runoff; _ o Site is isolated from habitation; _ o No landfill is accessible, no feasible alternative is available, and other alternatives will be pursued by the generator, as appropriate.
<p>Agronomic/Land-related State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sludge utilization permit applications must include agronomic calculation, including calculating the necessary nitrogen or phosphorus agronomic rate. The applicants must use Sections 391.411, 391.412 and 391.413 for determining the nutrient loading._ * Unless surface application is allowed by Section 391.404(a) or specified in a permit, sludge must be incorporated as soon as possible after application to prevent odor emission and runoff potential_ * It is recommended that the available phosphorus content in soils and total phosphorus in the sludge be analyzed every 2 years. _ * After five years of sludge application the phosphorus level in the soil must be monitored and sludge application must cease if the plant available phosphorus content in the soil exceeds 400 pounds per acre for sandy soils or 800 pounds for non-sandy soils._ * Sludge applied to nitric soils must be incorporated. _ * Sludge must be applied at or below the annual nitrogen or phosphorus agronomic rate as calculated using the nutrient loading criteria pursuant to Section 391.410 for the crops grown or the heavy metal loading criteria pursuant to Section 391.420_ * Sludge must not be applied to sites used for growing of commercial truck gardening fruits and vegetables that are grown and sold for direct human consumption. For public distribution programs, it is not recommended that sludge be applied to sites for individual use that may grow leafy (lettuce, spinach, Swiss chard, etc.) or root (potatoes, carrots, horseradish, etc.) vegetables unless specified conditions are met._

	<p>* Sludge must not be surface applied without incorporation to farm land having greater than 5% slope. If the slope does exceed 5%, surface application can be used providing the annual soil loss does not exceed 5 tons/acre._</p> <p>* Sludge may be incorporated on lands having slopes up to 8%, irrespective of soil loss. If the slope exceeds 8%, incorporation methods may be used providing the annual soil loss does not exceed five tons per acre as calculated by the Universal Soil Loss Equation. _</p> <p>* For sludge applied soils having the following infiltration rates as determined by standard percolation tests or from information contained in soil surveys, the listed minimum soil depth to the mean annual water table must be adhered to: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Greater than 2 inches/hour - 10 feet; _ o Less than or equal to 2 inches/hour - 5 feet. _ <p>* Unless otherwise allowed by Section 391.450, sludge applied land must have a background soil pH of 6.5 or greater or liming of the land is required prior to sludge application to raise the soil pH to a minimum of 6.5. _</p> <p>* Sludge amended land must have a crop grown and harvested according to normal agricultural practice. Application rates must be based upon the nitrogen or phosphorus requirements for the crops grown taking into account the soil nutrient level determined by soil testing. _</p> <p>* Horticultural, silvicultural, nursery, sod farm, highway median or right-of-way or other beneficial uses of sludge on land will be reviewed on a case-by-case determination. _</p> <p>* Soils having a cation exchange capacity in the range from 5 to 15 meq/100gm are acceptable for sludge utilization providing sludge application rates do not result in heavy metals being applied to land in excess of those amounts listed in Table II of Section 391.420c. Application to land with a low soil CEC (<5 meq/100g) should be avoided. If a sludge management plan includes sludge application in these areas, the sludge generator or user must apply only half of the heavy metal loading rates set forth in Table II. Permits may be issued which allow application of double the amounts listed in Table II providing it is demonstrated that the soil CEC is greater than 15 meq/100g.</p>
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be</p>	<p>No</p>

applied ?	
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more	Yes

<p>stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?</p>	
<p>Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>Permit applications must provide analyses for % total solids, % volatile solids, pH, volatile acids (if anaerobic digestion is used), total Kjeldahl nitrogen, ammonia nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, and metals.</p>
<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of</i></p>	<p>Pasture or hay ground that has received surface applied sludge must not be harvested or used for livestock grazing for a period of at least one month after sludge application or until precipitation of sufficient duration and intensity has occurred and washed all sludge from the area of the plant which can be ingested by an animal, whichever time period is greater.</p>

<p><i>applicati on and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	
<p>Are regulati ons more stringe nt than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing betwee n applica tion and harvesti ng crops?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Operati onal standar ds <i>State regulatio ns that govern which classes of biosolid s can be used for what purpose s and at what time</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Vectors</p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>

<p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Maximum acceptable heavy metal loading rates over the life of a project site (pounds per acre): Pb 1000, Mn 900, Zn 500, Cu 250, Ni 100, Cd 10._ * If the Agency determines that metals other than those in Table II of Section 391.420c should restrict the proposed application rate, the following loading rates must be utilized for the land application project. See Table III of Section 391.420f. _ * PCBs: Sludge containing concentrations of Polychlorinated Biphenyls (PCBs) equal to or greater than 10 mg/kg (dry weight basis) must be incorporated into the soil when applied to land used for producing animal feed, including pasture crops for animals raised for milk. Incorporation of the sludge into the soil is not required if it is assured that the PCB content is less than 0.2 mg/kg (actual weight) in animal feed or less than 1.5 mg/kg (fat basis) in milk. _ * If sludge concentrations of molybdenum and/or selenium exceed 4.0 mg/kg (dry weight basis) the Agency must restrict the crops to be grown on land receiving applications of that sludge or must restrict the use of crops for livestock forage as necessary to prevent toxicity to livestock._

<p><i>nants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>* The Agency will consider allowing loading rates greater than those specified in the code provided the generator or user addresses certain issues</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and</p>	<p>Sludge must be applied as soon as possible after transport to the application site, unless storage is provided in compliance with the sludge storage criteria.</p>

<i>reporting</i>	
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application</i>	No other information

<p>on of biosolid s</p>	
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If</p>	<p>Yes. Section 22.56 was added to the Illinois Environmental Protection Act, effective August 25, 2011.</p>

<p>yes, please describ e or provide links.</p>	
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdic tions (e.g., cities, countie s, watersh eds) that regulat e land applica tion of biosolid s beyond state- level regulati ons? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land applica tion of septage , compo sts, digestat</p>	<p>Yes. Land application of contaminated waste material would be regulated.</p>

<p>es, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	
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Indiana	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Indiana Department of Environmental Management (IDEM)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Indiana Administrative Rule: _ http://iac.iga.in.gov/iac//T03270/A00061.PDF _ Article 6.1. Land Application of Biosolid, Industrial Waste, and Pollutant-bearing water.
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolid" means solid, semisolid, or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works. Examples of biosolid include, but are not limited to, the following: (1) Scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes. (2) A material derived from biosolid. (3) An industrial waste product that contains domestic sewage or material under subdivision (1) or (2) of the code. Biosolid does not include ash generated during the firing of biosolid in a biosolid incinerator or grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works.
Biosolids classes	The terms Class A and B are used in accordance with 40 CFR 503
Other Definitions	"Biosolid containing an industrial waste product" means a biosolid where one of the following conditions apply: (1) The industrial waste product contains domestic sewage or material described under section 7(a)(1) or 7(a)(2) and is generated from one source or generator. (2) The industrial waste product contains blends of industrial waste products and biosolids from different sources or generators.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	* Surface application of biosolids is prohibited within 300 feet of a residence, surface waters, or surface conduit to a subsurface feature; within 50 feet of any well or of the property line of public building or school; and within 200 feet of any potable well or drinking water spring._ * Injection of biosolids is prohibited within 33 feet of surface waters or surface conduit to a subsurface feature; within the property line of a residence; within 50 feet of a well or of the property line of public building, or school; and within 200 feet of any potable well or drinking water spring._

	<p>* Incorporation by end of day is prohibited within 33 feet of surface waters or surface conduit to a subsurface feature, within 300 feet of a residence, within 50 feet of a well, within 200 feet of a portable well or drinking water spring, and within 50 feet of the property line of any public building or school._</p> <p>* Waivers are available.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>A biosolid or industrial waste product may only be applied to land that is frozen or snow-covered if the biosolid or industrial waste product does not enter surface waters or ground water; and a management plan has been submitted and approved by the commissioner including setback distances, application rates, site characteristics, and supervision and operational oversight.</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>* No land application on slopes greater than:_ o 6%: liquid surface, liquid incorporation_ o 12%: dewatered surface_ o 18%: liquid injection, dewatered incorporation_ * No application to any site if any of the cumulative pollutant loading rates in Table 2 of 40 CFR 503.13 are exceeded (same as 327 IAC 6.1-4-9b)_ * When land application site and the cumulative amount of each pollutant is known, the cumulative amount must be used to determine the additional amount of each pollutant that can be applied to the land application site in accordance with Table 2 in section 9(b)._ * If a biosolid, industrial waste product, or pollutant-bearing water has been applied to the land application site and the cumulative amount of each pollutant is not documented, application of any additional biosolid, industrial waste product, or pollutant-bearing water is prohibited._ * Biosolid or industrial waste product must not be applied to land unless there is a minimum depth of twenty (20) inches of soil overlying bedrock._ * The soil pH must be 5.5 or greater at the time of land application for industrial waste products or biosolids containing an industrial waste product with a cadmium concentration of two milligrams per kilogram or less._ * The soil pH must be 6.5 or greater at the time of land application for industrial waste products or biosolids containing industrial waste products with a cadmium concentration greater than two milligrams per kilogram._ * Application of biosolid or industrial waste product is prohibited if the moisture holding capacity of the soil is exceeded_ * Biosolid or industrial waste product must not be applied to the land in violation of historic preservation requirements under IC 14-21-1._</p>

	<p>* Section 6.1-4-10 contains loading rate limits, specifically for plant available nitrogen (PAN) loading for crop production_</p> <p>- Sometimes, if the permittee meets vector attraction reduction by injection or incorporation the permit is written to prohibit surface application. Application rates are not based on pH, land application is prohibited if the soil pH is <5.5. Application rates are not based on slope, land application is either allowed or prohibited based on slope.</p>
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
<p>Composition testing</p> <p><i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>The nine pollutant metals that must be tested for are arsenic, cadmium, copper, lead, mercury, molybdenum, nickel, selenium and zinc. In Indiana, biosolids are also tested for percent solids, total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), ammonia nitrogen, nitrate nitrogen, total phosphorus and total potassium. The frequency of testing for metals is based on the annual biosolids generation. Nutrients are sampled only when land application is occurring. If a pollutant is found above an approved level, or one of concern is found, IDEM will revise the analytical program and require investigation of the origin of the pollutant. Details of monitoring and analysis are found in 327 IAC 6.1-4-16</p>
<p>Time restrictions</p> <p><i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event,</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>such as harvest or public access</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	<p>* Table 2 Cumulative Pollutant Loading rates all the same metals but slightly more restrictive than 40 CFR 503 on each. _</p> <p>* Table 3 Pollutant concentrations all the same as 40 CFR 503 but include molybdenum at 75mg/kg (which is the same as the ceiling)_</p> <p>* Table 4 annual pollutant loading rates all the same as 40 CFR 503, except concentrations are slightly more restrictive on each._</p> <p>* Land application of a biosolid or industrial waste product containing concentrations of polychlorinated biphenyls at two milligrams per kilogram or greater on a dry weight basis is prohibited. 75 mg/kg is set for Table 1 (ceiling limit) and Table 3 (EQ limit). If the molybdenum is >40 mg/kg - application to pasture where animals feed is prohibited .</p>
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Any person who applies a biosolid or industrial waste product that was not generated in Indiana to land in Indiana must: (1) be in compliance with IC 13-18-14-1; and (2) obtain a permit under section 4, 5, or 5.5 from the commissioner.

<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>No formal plan required</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>Nitrogen is the basis for the agronomic loading rate for land application, unless the metal concentrations are high, then application rates are based on metal annual loading rates.</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>Yes. Some counties try to prohibit biosolids generated out of county to be land applied in that county.</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Septage is regulated under 327 IAC 7.1. _ Compost generated from biosolids and/or industrial waste products are regulated under 327 IAC 6.1_ Compost generated from yard waste, food waste, and manure (when not on the farm) are regulated under IC 13-20</p>

Iowa	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Iowa Department of Natural Resources (IDNR). IDNR consists of natural resource division and environmental service division. Biosolids regulation is under the environmental service division.
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	* Iowa Administrative Code:_ https://www.legis.iowa.gov/docs/iac/chapter/567.67.pdf * Iowa Code: _ https://www.legis.iowa.gov/law/iowaCode/chapters?title=XI&year=2025 _ Title XI, Chapter 455B Jurisdiction of Department of Natural Resources
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage sludge" is solid, semisolid, or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works. Sewage sludge does not include the grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment.
Biosolids classes	Class I/EQ_ Pollutants: must not exceed concentrations provided in Pollutant Concentrations in 40 CFR 503.13_ One of the monitoring and one of the analytical and treatment processes below must be met (Similar to 503.32 Class A Alternative 4)_ *Monitoring:_ o The density of fecal coliform in the sewage sludge must be less than 1000 Most Probable Number per gram of total solids (dry weight basis) or _ o the density of Salmonella sp. bacteria in the sewage sludge must be less than three Most Probable Number per four grams of total solids (dry weight basis). _ *Analytical/treatment:_ o The density of enteric viruses in the sewage sludge must be less than one Plaque-forming Unit per four grams of total solids (dry weight basis) or _ o the density of viable helminth ova in the sewage sludge must be less than one per four grams of total solids (dry weight basis), or_ o Sewage sludge must be treated in one of the Processes to Further Reduce Pathogens (PFRP) described in Appendix B to 40 CFR 503, or_ o Sewage sludge must be treated in a process that is equivalent to a Process to Further Reduce Pathogens (PFRP), as determined by the department._

	<p>* Vectors: One of 8 vector attractor reduction requirements outlined in IAC Title 4, Chapter 67.7 must be met. These are similar to, but not the same as, requirements for Class A in 40 CFR 503.33_</p> <p>Class II _</p> <p>* Pollutants: Cannot exceed Ceiling Pollutant Concentrations in 40 CFR 503.13_</p> <p>* Pathogens: The geometric mean of the density of fecal coliform for seven samples must be less than 2,000,000 Most Probable Number per gram of total solids (dry weight basis) or one of a number of processes to reduce pathogens, or their equivalent (as determined by the department) must be employed._</p> <p>* Vectors: One of 8 vector attractor reduction requirements outlined in IAC Title 4, Chapter 67.8 must be met. These are similar to, but not the same as, requirements for Class B in 40 CFR 503.33_</p> <p>Class III: Sludge that doesn't meet Class I or II criteria</p>
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" is the whole sludge application rate designed to provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the crop grown on the land and to minimize the amount of nitrogen that passes to the groundwater.
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>Class I & II_</p> <p>Application must be >35 feet from open waterway_</p> <p>_</p> <p>Class II_</p> <p>* If applied within 200 feet, but no closer than 35 feet, of a stream, lake, sinkhole or tile line surface intake located downgradient of the land application site, it must be injected or applied to the surface and mechanically incorporated into the soil within 48 hours of application unless approved by the department_</p> <p>* Application must be >200 feet from an occupied residence or any well unless reduced to a minimum of 35 feet after agreement with owner and occupant and an approved farm management plan</p>
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	<p>Class II_</p> <p>* Must be injected or applied to the surface and mechanically incorporated into the soil within 48 hours if applied to land subject to flooding more frequently than once in 10 years._</p> <p>* Application on frozen or snow-covered ground should be avoided, unless special precautions are taken and must be limited to land areas of less than 5 percent slope unless approved by the department.</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>Class II_</p> <p>* Sites must have pH > 6.0, unless certain conditions apply_</p> <p>* Slope cannot be greater than 9% unless approved</p>

Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	Yes
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	Yes
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Samples must be classified as Class I, II, or III and tested for potentially hazardous chemicals or other toxic substances. A sludge sampling schedule and procedures must form part of a program plan required for land application. Analysis records must be kept for 5 years and must include analysis in accordance with CFR 503.8
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Class II restrictions are similar to, but not the same as, those on Class B under 40 CFR 503.32_ * Food crops with harvested parts that touch the sewage sludge/soil mixture must not be harvested for 38 months after application._ * Food crops, feed crops and fiber crops must not be harvested for 30 days after application._ * Animals can't graze on the land for 30 days after application._ * Turf grown on land where sewage sludge is applied can't be harvested for one year after application when the harvested turf is placed on either land with a high potential for public exposure or a lawn, unless otherwise specified by the department._ * Public access to land with a high potential for public exposure must be restricted for one year after application._ * Public access to land with a low potential for public exposure must be restricted for 30 days after application.

Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	Yes
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Class I is the only class that can be applied to lawns and gardens_ _ Class II _ * Cannot be applied to the land if it is likely to adversely affect a threatened or endangered species listed under section 4 of the Endangered Species Act or its designated critical habitat_ * Cannot be applied to sand, loamy sand or silt soils, as defined by USDA_ * Can only be applied throughout the top 5 feet of soil profile_ * Must be injected on contour or mechanically incorporated within 48 hours if applied to land on which the soil loss exceeds soil loss limits established by county soil conservation district_ _ Class III must be surface disposed or incinerated as per 40 CFR Part 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	One of 8 vector attractor reduction requirements outlined in IAC Title 4, Chapter 67 must be met for Class I and II. These are very similar to, but not exactly the same as, those outlined in 40 CFR 503.33(b)
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	Yes
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Class II application to sites not meeting pollutant concentrations Pollutant Concentrations Table are subject to Cumulative Pollutant Loading Rates Table 2 in 40 CFR 503.13
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows

<i>location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	On a case-by-case basis, this department may impose requirements for the land application of sewage sludge in addition to or more stringent than the requirements in this chapter when necessary to protect public health and the environment from any adverse effect of a pollutant in the sewage sludge.
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	Yes. A complete rule review and reissuance is ongoing for State of Iowa agencies.
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that	No. There are no biosolids land application regulation below the state level regulation.

<p>regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Iowa law requires that all manure from an animal feeding operation must be land applied according to Chapter 65 of the Iowa Administrative Code.</p>

Kansas	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Kansas Department of Health and Environment
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	None provided
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No

Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate	No

land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No

Kentucky Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Department for Environmental Protection_ Division of Waste Management
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	KY Administrative Code:_ https://apps.legislature.ky.gov/law/kar/titles/ _ 401 KAR Chapter 45 Sections 105, 100 and 070_ https://apps.legislature.ky.gov/law/kar/titles/401/045/105/ _ https://apps.legislature.ky.gov/law/kar/titles/401/045/070/ _ https://apps.legislature.ky.gov/law/kar/titles/401/045/100/
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	For Chapter 45, Section105: This administrative regulation establishes the standards and requirements for the application of biosolids, in accordance with 40 C.F.R. Part 503 and as required by KRS 224.50-765 from the treatment of domestic sewage or sewage sludge from a treatment facility. This administrative regulation is no more stringent than the corresponding federal rules but in order to comply with KRS 224.50-765(3), does have additional requirements that are not in 40 C.F.R. Part 503 related to a permitting program and siting criteria._ For Chapter 45, Section100: This administrative regulation establishes requirements for special waste landfarming sites or facilities and special waste composting sites or facilities but does not include landfarming of biosolids.
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Per KRS 224.50-765, Biosolids -- Designation as special waste -- Administrative regulations for siting and permitting of biosolids disposal. _ (1) As used in this section, "biosolids" means nutrient-rich, organic, residual material that results from the treatment of domestic sewage or sewage sludge in a treatment facility and can be recycled and applied as a fertilizer to improve and maintain productive soils. _

	(2) Notwithstanding any provision of law to the contrary, when biosolids are generated from wastewater treatment at a publicly owned treatment works, the biosolids shall be: _ (a) Designated a special waste; and _ (b) Regulated in conformance with the most recent version of 40 C.F.R. pt. 503.
Biosolids classes	Per 40 C.F.R. pt. 503
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	All biosolid land application facilities shall maintain the following buffer zones:_ *at least 200 ft from residences and occupied buildings_ *at least 200 ft from water wells_ *at least 100 ft from surface water, including perennial streams_ *at least 100 ft from karst features_ *at least 50 ft from intermittent streams_ *at least 30 ft from ephemeral streams_ *at least 30 ft from property lines and public roads_ Measurement guidance is provided in 401 KAR 45:105 Section 5, 4b
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic /Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application</i>	Section 5. Siting Criteria for Land Application of Biosolids. The land application of biosolids shall comply with the siting criteria in subsections (1) through (4) of this section._ (1) Biosolids shall not be applied in the 100-year floodplain._ (2) (a) An applicant shall use the Kentucky Energy and Environment Cabinet Basics of Groundwater and Kentucky Aquifers document to determine aquifer type._

<i>under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	(b) A minimum of four (4) feet of soil between the soil surface and the seasonal high-water table shall be maintained for land application in areas comprised of the Granular-unconsolidated, karst, and alluvial (Ohio River Alluvium) aquifers._ (3) A land application unit shall not be located on land with a slope greater than fifteen (15) percent.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent	Yes

<p>than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic /land application restrictions?</p>	
<p>Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>Waste must be analyzed for arsenic, cadmium, copper, lead, mercury, molybdenum, nickel, selenium, and zinc. The Director of the Division of Waste Management may require additional analytes if determined necessary to protect public health and the environment from any adverse effects from a pollutant or contaminant in the biosolids.</p>
<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>A biosolids generator may give away biosolids pursuant to 401 KAR 45:105, 401 KAR 45:070, and 401 KAR 45:100.</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>The Director of the Division of Waste Management may require additional analytes if determined necessary to protect public health and the environment from any adverse effects from a pollutant or contaminant in the biosolids.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans</p>	<p>No formal plan required under waste regulations. NMPs can be referenced in waste permits.</p>

<p><i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted. None in operation.</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>Application form available at:_ https://eec.ky.gov/Environmental-Protection/Forms%20Library/DEP%204505%20Application%20for%20a%20Biosolids%20Landfarming%20Facility%20Permit.pdf _ Annual report form available at:_ https://eec.ky.gov/Environmental-Protection/Forms%20Library/DEP%204506%20Annual%20Biosolids%20Landfarming%20Report.pdf</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may</p>	<p>No</p>

potentially change	
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	Yes. Kentucky has a regulation called "Environmental Performance Standards" that affects all waste management facilities. https://apps.legislature.ky.gov/law/kar/titles/401/030/031/
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	Undetermined. Local ordinances may apply which are administered by county and city governments.
4. Is the land applicatio	Yes. Septage is regulated in Kentucky by the Cabinet for Health and Family Services. Composting is regulated under solid waste and special waste chapters,

<p>n of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>depending on the source of the material to be composted. Other organic residuals may be land applied</p>
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Louisiana	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Louisiana Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Louisiana Administrative Code, Title 33, Part 9, Subpart 3, Chapter 73:_ https://www.deq.louisiana.gov/assets/docs/Water/33v09-201102.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage sludge", or material derived from sewage sludge, that is nonhazardous, has a PCB concentration of less than 50 mg/kg of total solids (dry weight), and is prepared to meet one of the pollutant requirements of 40 CFR 503.13, one of the pathogen requirements in 40 CFR 503.32, and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33.
Biosolids classes	Class EQ biosolids are nonhazardous and meet the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of 40 CFR 503.13, the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of 40 CFR 503.13, the Class A pathogen requirements in 40 CFR 503.32, and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8), and that have a PCB concentration of less than 10 mg/kg of total solids (dry weight)._ _ Class A biosolids are not defined by state but regulations adopt 40 CFR 503.32 terminology_ _ Class B biosolids do not meet one or more of the following requirements:_ o the pollutant concentrations in Table 3 of 40 CFR 503.13;_ o the Class A pathogen requirements in 40 CFR 503.32;_ o one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8); and/or_ o a PCB concentration of less than 10 mg/kg of total solids (dry weight basis).
Other Definitions	"Agronomic Rate"_ a. the whole biosolids application rate (dry weight basis) designed:_ * to provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop, or vegetation grown on the land; and_

	<p>* to minimize the amount of nitrogen in the biosolids that are not utilized by the crop or vegetation grown on the land and either passes below the root zone to the groundwater or gets into surface waters during storm events;_</p> <p>b. agronomic rate may be extended to include phosphorus to application sites that are located within the drainage basin of water bodies that have been determined by the administrative authority to be impaired by phosphorus._</p>
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>For Non-EQ biosolids:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No application within 300 ft of a private potable water supply well, _ * No application within 300 ft of a public potable water supply well, surface water intake, treatment plant, or public potable water supply elevated or ground storage tank, unless permitted by the Department of Health and Hospitals_ * No application within 100 ft of a property boundary, unless permitted_ * For new or first-time-permitted sites, no application within 1000 feet of an established institution or 500 feet of an occupied residential home or structure, unless permitted, in which case no application within 200 feet._ * No application to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site during the months when the water table is less than or at 2 feet below the soil surface_ * Bulk biosolids must not be applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site that is 33 feet (10 meters) or less from any waters of the state, as defined in LAC 33:IX.2313, unless otherwise specified by the permitting authority. (This is similar to 40 CFR 503, but extends to waters of the state.)_ * No application to the land if it would affect a property that either is listed on, or is eligible for listing on, the National Historic Register.
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>Non-EQ bulk biosolids cannot be applied to agricultural land, forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site that is flooded, frozen, or snow-covered so that the bulk biosolids enter a wetland or other waters of the state, as defined in LAC 33:IX.2313, except as provided in a permit. (This is similar to 40 CFR 503, but extends to waters of the state.)</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Non-EQ biosolids must be applied to the land in accordance with the slope requirements in Table 1 of LAC 33:IX.7303.D_ * Biosolids having a concentration of PCBs equal to or greater than 10 mg/kg of total solids (dry wt.) must be incorporated into the soil regardless of slope

Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	EQ analysis requires analysis of metals, percent dry solids, percent ammonia nitrogen, percent nitrate, percent nitrite, percent nitrogen, percent phosphorus, percent potassium, and percent organic matter, pH and PCBs
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	* No application of bulk biosolids subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in Table 2 of 40 CFR 503.13 to the land without first contacting the administrative authority to determine if bulk biosolids subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates in Table 2 of 40 CFR 503.13 have been applied to the land since July 20, 1993._

	* Class A biosolids pathogen requirements in 40 CFR 503.32 must be met when biosolids are applied to a lawn or a home garden or when biosolids are sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land
<p>Vectors</p> <p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
<p>Pollutants</p> <p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>* Non-EQ biosolids sold or given away in a bag or other container cannot be applied to the land at a rate that would cause any of the annual pollutant loading rates in Table 4 of 40 CFR 503.12 to be exceeded_</p> <p>* Biosolids with concentration of PCBs greater than or equal to 10 mg/kg of total solids (dry wt.) cannot be applied to a lawn or home garden or sold or given away in a bag or other container for land application</p>
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
<p>Transportation</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
<p>Nutrient management plans</p> <p><i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>The person who applies non-EQ biosolids to agricultural or forest land must:_</p> <p>a. receive approval for a full nutrient management plan developed by the Natural Resource Conservation Service, a certified soil scientist, a certified crop advisor, or a local</p>
<p>Incineration</p> <p><i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	Permitted

<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>* A person who applies bulk biosolids to the land, if the biosolids were obtained from a facility that is permitted to treat sewage sludge to an Exceptional Quality biosolids level, is exempted from obtaining a permit._ * Administrative authorities have substantial authority to regulate various aspects of land application on a case-by-case basis_ * There are requirements, not restrictions, for the method of applying bulk biosolids, LCA 33:7303</p>
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General Assessment Questions

<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Only land application of biosolids are regulated under the water regulations. However, other land application possibilities may be possible under the solid waste program.</p>

Maine Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Maine Department of Environmental Protection
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Maine 130 - HP 1417 – LD 1911; An Act to Prevent the Further Contamination of the Soils and Waters of the State with So-called Forever Chemicals
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sludge" means non-hazardous solid, semi-solid or liquid waste generated from a municipal, commercial or industrial wastewater treatment plant, water supply treatment plant, or wet process air pollution control facility or any other such waste having similar characteristics and effect. The term does not include industrial discharges that are point sources subject to permits under section 402 of the Federal Water Pollution Control Act, as amended._ "Type II residual" means a residual from a known source that does not contain hazardous substances above risk based standards in 06-096 CMR 418 Appendix A and that may contain human pathogens, such as sewage sludge, dewatered septage and disposable diapers.
Biosolids classes	In 06-096 C.M.R. ch. 419 § 4(l) describes classes: Type II Residuals are residuals that may contain human pathogens, such as sewage sludge, or solids from dewatered septage. Pathogen containing residuals must be treated prior to utilization. Pathogens are microorganisms that cause diseases. The degree to which the residual is treated for pathogens and vector attraction determines its class. When residuals are treated to Class A standards, in which pathogens are reduced to ambient soil concentrations, no additional siting standards apply to utilization of that residual. When residuals are treated to Class B standards, in which pathogens are reduced by about 90%, additional siting and operational standards apply to utilization of that residual.
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means an application rate of plant nutrients that is recommended to provide the optimum plant growth and be utilized by the crop._ _ "Agronomic utilization" or "utilization" means the land application of residuals in a controlled manner in order to:_

	<p>(1) Increase the nutrient content of the soil at a rate commensurate with the nutritional needs of the crop to be grown and the assimilative capacity of the soil;_</p> <p>(2) Otherwise improve agricultural soil conditions; or_</p> <p>(3) Provide some other horticultural benefit.</p>
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	Application not permitted
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Application not permitted
Weather-related and seasonal	Application not permitted
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	Application not permitted
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Application not permitted
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	Application not permitted
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	Application not permitted
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Application not permitted
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Application not permitted
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Application not permitted
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Application not permitted
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Application not permitted
<p>Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical</i></p>	Application not permitted

tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.	
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Application not permitted
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	Application not permitted
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Application not permitted
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Application not permitted
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	Application not permitted
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Application not permitted
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Application not permitted
Is there a chromium limit set?	Application not permitted
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of</i>	Application not permitted

<i>transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	Application not permitted
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Unknown
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	No other information
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	No
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If	Yes. All except septage are regulated under the Solid Waste Management Rules: Agronomic Utilization of Residuals, 06-096 C.M.R. Ch. 419, the same as sludge/biosolids. Septage is regulated pursuant to the Septage Management Rules, 06-096 C.M.R. Ch. 420.

so, please briefly
describe.

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Maryland Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Maryland Department of the Environment (MDE)_ Maryland Department of Agriculture (MDA)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Links to regulations	Code of Maryland Regulations (COMAR), 26.04.06:_ https://mde.maryland.gov/programs/land/Documents/sewage%20sludge%20regulations%2026%2004%2006.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" are defined as "treated sewage sludge that meets the standards for Class A or B sewage sludge." Biosolids does not include grit and screenings collected at a wastewater treatment plant or ash generated by the incineration of sewage sludge. Sewage sludge is defined as "any thickened liquid, suspension, settled solid, or dried residue that a sewage treatment plant extracts from sewage."
Biosolids classes	Class A and Class B biosolids conform to the definitions in 40 CFR 503.32
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means the sewage sludge application rate, in dry weight basis, based on the nitrogen or phosphorus requirement of the crop or vegetation to be grown, whichever is determined to be the most limiting nutrient, that is designed to minimize the amount of the limiting nutrient in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation_ grown on the land to the groundwater. _ _ "Bulk sewage sludge" is sewage sludge that is not sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land._ _ "Sewage sludge generator" is a person who owns or operates a facility that receives and processes sewage in this State or produces sewage sludge to be

	utilized in this State. The definition does not include the owner or operator of a septic system._
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Minimum buffer or setback distances for agricultural land application are noted in COMAR 26.04.06.37 in Section D(2)(b), Table 1. Generally, buffers are classified based on the type of application (surface applied vs. application using incorporation or injection). Buffers for surface (no incorporation) are more stringent than those practiced using incorporation.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Material cannot be applied when the soil is saturated, or the ground is flooded, ponded, frozen, or snow covered. MDA's Nutrient Management regulations prohibit all commercial fertilizer and organic nutrient applications in the winter (December 16th through February 28th) except for potash and liming materials.
Agronomic/ Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	* Bulk biosolids may not be applied on sites with slopes > 15 %._ * The pH of the soil must be 6.0 or greater at the time initial of bulk application and maintained at a pH > 6.0 thereafter.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which	No

biosolids can be applied?	
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/l and application restrictions ?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that</i>	All sludges regardless of whether they meet pathogen or vector attraction reduction (VAR) requirements, must be analyzed for certain required parameters, which includes pH, total solids, nutrients, heavy metals, PCBs and CaCO ₃ equivalence (for lime treated or amended material). Monitoring frequency follows 40 CFR 503.16.

<i>must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	* Only Class A material may be applied to lawns and home gardens_ * Bagged sludge given away or sold must meet Class A pathogen reduction and vector attraction reduction requirements, and the high quality pollutant concentration limits in Table 3 of 40 CFR 503.13.
Vectors	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>* Biosolids which has a PCB concentration greater than 10 mg/kg (dry weight) may not be applied. _ * If bulk biosolids are applied to land and the material does not meet the pollutant concentration limits in Table 3, then the limits in 40 CFR 503.13 Table 2 apply. Bulk biosolids that does not meet the Table 3 concentration limits may not be applied to sites where the cumulative pollutant loading limits in Table 2 have been reached. _ * When sludge is not high quality, annual application rates need to be lower than a calculated rate as per Table 4, 40 CFR 503.13.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the</i></p>	<p>A site-specific permit is required for all transportation activities conducted in the State. This includes transporting sludge from one treatment plant to another, to an out-of-state site, or to a landfill. This permit is also required of out-of-state sou</p>

<p><i>movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	
<p>Nutrient management plans State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</p>	<p>Application rates for agricultural operations are based on a Nutrient Management Plan (NMP) prepared by a certified consultant. The rate may be nitrogen (N) based, or phosphorus (P) based. Soil tests are used to determine if P based rates are needed. If t</p>
<p>Incineration Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</p>	<p>* Composting facilities require a separate, site specific permit to operate in Maryland. _ * The quantity of material sold or given away in a bag or other container by the permittee to either commercial or domestic users both in? state and out-of-state must be reported.</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>

<p>two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>4. Is the land</p>	<p>Yes. Septage is regulated by MDE's Water and Science Administration. Composts (not sure) but composting facilities are regulated by our program but by another</p>

<p>application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>division. Organic residuals must be tested and registered by MDA's office of the State Lab Chemi</p>
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Massachusetts	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Massachusetts Department of Environmental Protection
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Mass Administrative Code: https://www.mass.gov/regulations/310-CMR-3200-land-application-of-sludge-and-septage
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	Mass DEP's program that oversees wastewater treatment sludge and biosolids is called the Residuals Management Program
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sludge" means the solid, semi-solid, and liquid residue that results from a process of wastewater treatment or drinking water treatment. This residue does not include grit, screening, or grease and oil which are removed at the headworks of a facility. For the purpose of 310 CMR 32.00, the term "sewage" as used in M.G.L. c. 111, § 150A and 310 CMR 19.00 includes wastewater treatment plant sludge which is not hazardous waste pursuant to 310 CMR 30.000. Storage means containment or stockpiling prior to or during selling or distributing or reuse.
Biosolids classes	The Department classifies sludge and septage in accordance with the criteria in 310 CMR 32.12(2) as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Type I - Sludge approved by the Department pursuant to 310 CMR 32.00 which may be used, sold, or distributed or offered for use, sale, or distribution on any site without further approval of the Department, and which may be used for growing any vegetation. Septage not be eligible for Type I classification. o Type II - Sludge and septage approved by the Department pursuant to 310 CMR 32.00 which may be used, sold, or distributed or offered for use, sale, or distribution on a site only with prior approval of the Department, and which may be used for growing any vegetation. o Type III - Sludge and septage approved by the Department pursuant to 310 CMR 32.00 which may be used, sold, or distributed or offered for use, sale, or distribution for land application on a site only with prior approval of the Department, which may be used for growing any vegetation not including direct food chain crops, and whose land application to a site must be recorded in the registry of deeds in the chain of title for such site.
Other Definitions	"Land application" means fertilizing or amending soil by:

	(a) applying to the surface of soil by spreading, spraying, or other similar means, and/or (b) mixing or working into the soil or beneath the surface of the soil within the root zone of the crop by harrowing, plowing, rototilling, injecting, or other similar means.
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No Type II or Type III sludge or septage land applied anywhere within a radius of 2,500 feet of a well used as a source of drinking water supply by a public water system or the high water mark of any Class A water unless approved by Department._ * No application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage anywhere within a radius of 300 feet of a private drinking water supply well._ * The Department may on a case-by-case basis establish a distance between the location of the land application site and surface water to which 310 CMR 32.22(1) does not apply for the purpose of preventing adverse impacts on the use or quality of that surface water._ * No application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage within the high water mark of field depressions or ditches through which water flows during snow melts or heavy rainfall._ * Required minimum of three feet between the lowest point of land application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage and the maximum high groundwater table. The Department may require a greater distance if sludge or septage is, or is intended to be, land applied over an existing, planned, or potential groundwater public water supply._ * Required minimum distance of three feet between bedrock and the lowest point of land application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage. The Department may require a greater distance between the lowest point of land application and bedrock if the location in question is over an aquifer whose groundwater supplies a bedrock well.
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>No application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage during periods of rain, _ when the soil is frozen, when the soil is covered with snow or ice, or when the soil is saturated with water.</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage on any land within Massachusetts unless such land application is in compliance with 310 CMR 32.20 and 310 CMR 32.21 through 32.29._ * Land application of sludge or septage must be in accordance with good agricultural practices as recommended by the Cooperative Extension Service or the Soil Conservation Service._ * Type II or Type III sludge or septage may be land applied only on land where the surface soil meets the criteria for certain soil textural classes as designated by the USDA and specified in 32.21. The

	<p>Department may also grant approval for land application on land whose soil has coarse sand._</p> <p>* No land application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage permitted on any site where the soil, when moist, has within three feet of the ground surface:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o mottles with a Munsell color notation chroma of 2 or less over 5% or more of the observed soil horizon surface, or_ o dominant colors in the matrix with a Munsell color notation chroma of one or less if any mottles present in the observed soil horizon surface do not cover more than 5% of the observed soil horizon surface, or if there are no mottles present in the observed soil horizon surface._ <p>* No application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage at a site where the pH of the surface soil is below 6.5 at the time of land application or would go below 6.5 as a result of mixing the soil with the sludge or septage._</p> <p>* Type II or Type III sludge or septage must at all times be confined to the site of land application. Land application of such sludge or septage must be in accordance with soil conservation practices which minimize run-off and soil loss through erosion. The Department may require that measures such as run-off prevention or erosion control methods be instituted at a land application site._</p> <p>* No application of Type II or Type III sludge or septage on any land whose slope exceeds 8% from the horizontal plane without Department approval._</p> <p>* Type II or Type III sludge or septage must be land applied at a rate which must not exceed the nitrogen requirements of the crop grown or intended to be grown at the site of such land application.</p>
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503	Yes

with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Type I and II and III: Sampling and analysis required for pH, % solids, % nitrogen, % ammonium nitrogen, % nitrogen nitrate, % phosphorus, % potassium, metals (including chromium and boron), and PCBs _ _ Table 32.13 lists the Minimum Frequency of Sampling Period and Analysis
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	No more than 48 hours may elapse between the time Type II or Type III sludge or septage is first land applied to the surface of the soil and the time the sludge or septage is mixed into the soil or beneath the surface of the soil, unless using sludge or septage which has been stabilized by a process deemed acceptable to the Department and which is not putrescible.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	Yes
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	* Type II or Type III sludge or septage may be land applied to the surface of land on which hay is grown or is intended to be grown, or to the surface of pasture land, only if 310 CMR 32.23(2) is complied with and such land application occurs prior to the growth or regrowth of a crop on that land._ * Only Type I sludge, or Type II or Type III sludge or septage which has been stabilized by a process deemed acceptable to the Department pursuant to 310 CMR 32.12(1)(b) may be land applied at a site if crops for direct human consumption are, or are intended to be, planted on that site within 24 months of land application, and there will be direct contact between the edible portion of such crops and the sludge or septage.
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing</i>	* More restrictive than 40 CFR 503, including limits on chromium, boron, and molybdenum_ * Type II or Type III sludge or septage must be land applied at a rate which does not exceed the pollutant constraints of Section 32.23(1)

<i>chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	Yes
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions	No

<p>(e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Michigan Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Michigan Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Michigan Natural Resources and Environmental Protection Act, Act 451 of 1994, Part 31, Section 324.3133:_ http://www.legislature.mi.gov _ Michigan Administrative Rules, Part 24, R 323.2401-2418:_ https://www.michigan.gov/egle/about/organization/water-resources/biosolids/laws-and-rules
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" are the solid, semisolid, or liquid residues generated during the treatment of sanitary sewage or domestic sewage in a treatment works. This includes, but is not limited to, scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes and a derivative of the removed scum or solids.
Biosolids classes	"Exceptional quality" or "EQ" means biosolids or a derivative that meets all of the following criteria:_ o Pollutant ceiling concentrations in 40 CFR Part 503.13 Table 1_ o Pollutant concentrations in 40 CFR Part 503.13 Table 3_ o One of the vector attraction reduction options in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(8) and 1 of the class A pathogen reduction alternatives in 40 CFR 503.32(a)._ _ Class A and B defined in accordance with 40 CFR 503
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means the calculated biosolids application rate (dry weight basis) which provides the amount of plant-available nitrogen (PAN) needed by the crop or vegetation grown on the land; which minimizes the amount of nitrogen that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown; and which considers the amounts of phosphate (P2O5) and potash (K2O) added by the biosolids as part of the total nutrient management plan.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	* At least 30-inches must separate the soil surface and groundwater at time of biosolids application._ _ * Isolation distance requirements for surface applied without incorporation:_ o Municipal wells = 2000ft_

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Noncommunity public water supply = 800 ft_ o Domestic wells, homes, commercial buildings = 100 ft_ o Surface waters = 50 feet (does not include grassed or tilled and planted drainage ways)_ <p>–</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Isolation distance requirements for injected or surface applied with incorporation:_ o Municipal wells = 2000ft_ o Noncommunity public water supply = 800 ft_ o Domestic wells, homes, commercial buildings = 150 ft_ o Surface waters = 150 feet (does not include grassed or tilled and planted drainage ways)
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	* No surface application of non-EQ biosolids to frozen or snow-covered ground, unless approved, but subsurface injection of bulk biosolids to such ground is permitted as long as there is substantial soil coverage of the biosolids. Bulk EQ biosolids are exempt.
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No application of non-EQ bulk biosolids on lands having a slope of more than 6% for surface application or more than 12% for subsurface injected biosolids, unless approved. Bulk EQ biosolids are exempt._ * For agricultural land, if the Bray P1 soil test level exceeds 300 pounds (P) per acre (150ppm), or if the Mehlich 3 soil test level exceeds 340 pounds (P) per acre (170 ppm), then no application until the soil P test level decreases to less than 1 of these values. _ * For silvicultural land, agronomic rates are determined based on annual plant-available nitrogen, but if the Bray P1 soil test level exceeds 200 pounds (P) per acre (100 ppm) or the Mehlich 3 soil test level exceeds 220 pounds (P) per acre (110ppm), then no application until the soil P test level decreases to less than one of these values._ * Soil fertility tests are required before initial biosolids application and within 2 years of subsequent applications_ * Rates for wastewater biosolids application in Michigan forests are defined in Table 5 of R 323.2410
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes

Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Methods of collection and analysis are prescribed in R323.2406.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	* When bulk biosolids are applied to agricultural land, a forest, a public contact site, or a reclamation site, 1) class A pathogen requirements or class B pathogen requirements and site restrictions must be met and 2) one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in CFR 503.33 (b)(1) through (b)(8) OR the vector attraction reduction requirements in CFR 503.33 (b)(9) or (10) must be met
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No

<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>* Non-EQ bulk biosolids can't be applied if any of the cumulative pollutant loading rates specified in 40 CFR Part 503.13 have been reached. State exempts EQ bulk biosolids from this 503 restriction via rule 323.2407(1), but also retains the right to impose it upon EQ on a case-by-case basis._ * Biosolids from more than one source or septage cannot be applied to the same site within the same crop year (bulk EQ biosolids exempt). Biosolids subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates cannot be applied to land which has received biosolids since July 20, 1993, unless the cumulative amounts of each pollutant applied to the site since that date are known. If they are known, the additional amount of each pollutant that can be applied must be calculated based on those data.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>No formal plan required</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>Many of these regulations do not apply to non-bulk biosolids/derivatives of exceptional quality, as per R 323.2407 (2). Domestic septage is not covered by the same regulations, but 40 CFR 503 would still apply.</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>

details that may potentially change	
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	Yes. Its possible future PFAs regulations could impact the biosolids land application program.
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	No
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	Yes. Land application of septage, industrial by Products and manure from certain permitted facilities are each regulated separately.

Minnesota	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Minnesota Pollution Control Agency (MPCA)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	MN Administrative Code - Chapter 7041, Sewage Sludge Management: https://www.revisor.mn.gov/rules/7041/
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage sludge" means solid, semisolid, or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works. Sewage sludge includes but is not limited to, scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes; and a material derived from sewage sludge. Sewage sludge does not include ash generated during the firing of sewage sludge in a sewage sludge incinerator or grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works. Sewage sludge that is acceptable and beneficial for recycling on land as a soil conditioner and nutrient source is also known as biosolids.
Biosolids classes	"Exceptional quality sewage sludge" means sewage sludge that has been prepared to meet one of the Class A pathogen reduction requirements in part 7041.1300, subpart 2; the pollutant concentrations in part 7041.1100, subpart 4, item C; and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in part 7041.1400, subpart 2, items A to H.
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means the sewage sludge application rate (dry weight basis) designed to: A. provide the amount of nitrogen which can be utilized by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop, or vegetation grown on the land; and B. minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the groundwater.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some</i>	The following apply to non-EQ bulk sewage sludge applied to the land: —

<p><i>feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * At least 3 ft must separate application site from bedrock, seasonal high water table, or drain tile for surface applied, incorporated or injected biosolids._ * At least 200ft must separate application site from private wells, no matter the type of application_ * At least 1000ft must separate application site from public wells, no matter the type of application_ * At least 50 ft must separate application site from irrigation wells, if surface applied, and 25 ft, if incorporated with 48 hours or injected_ * At least 200 ft must separate application site from residences, if surface applied or incorporated within 48 hours, or 100 ft if injected_ * At least 600 ft must separate application site from residential development and public contact, if surface applied or incorporated within 48 hours, or 300 ft if injected _ <p>–</p> <p>The following apply to non-EQ bulk sewage sludge applied to the land that lies upgradient of lakes, rivers, streams, type 3/4/5 wetlands, sinkholes, or tile inlets connected to these waters:–</p> <p>–</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * If the slope is 0-6%, no application within 200 ft if surface applied, 50 ft if incorporated within 48 hours, or 50 ft if injected._ * If the slope is >6-12%, no surface application and no application within 100 ft if incorporated within 48 hours or 100 ft if injected._ * For grassed waterways, no application within 33 ft, on any slope, when incorporated or injected, no application within 100 ft if surface applied on a slope of 0-6%, and no surface application on slopes greater than 6%._ <p>–</p> <p>Variances to these setbacks apply in certain circumstances outlined in 7041.1200, subpart 3</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>The following apply to non-EQ bulk sewage sludge applied to the land:–</p> <p>–</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Land application of dewatered or liquid bulk sewage sludge to frozen or snow covered ground is restricted to land with zero to two percent slopes the hydraulic loading rate is resitricted to 15,000 gallons per acre, and must maintain a 600-foot setback from downgradient surface waters._ * Bulk sewage sludge must be injected or incorporated within 48 hours of surface application on ground which is subject to flooding unless specified otherwise in a site approval.
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application</i></p>	<p>The following apply to non-EQ bulk sewage sludge applied to the land:–</p>

<p><i>under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Bulk sewage sludge application rates, combined with other known sources of nitrogen such as manure, carry-over nitrogen from previous sewage sludge applications, or fertilizer, must supply no more available nitrogen than the rates as described in subitems (1) to (5) of 7041.1200._ * Suitable soil conditions are as follows:_ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o the soil texture, United States Department of Agriculture classification, at the zone of sewage sludge application must be fine sand, loamy sand, sandy loam, loam, silt, silt loam, sandy clay loam, clay loam, sandy clay, silty clay loam, silty clay, or clay;_ o the pH of the soil must be 5.5 or greater;_ o bulk sewage sludge application to a site must be suspended when the soil extractable phosphorus content determined by the Brays P-1 test exceeds 200 parts per million (400 pounds per acre) in the surface six inches of soil unless waived by an approved management plan;_ o bulk sewage sludge application to a site must be suspended when the electrical conductivity of the saturation extract of the soil exceeds four millimhos per centimeter as determined by the soluble salt test;_ o soil samples must be collected and analyzed for parameters in part 7041.0800, subpart 2, item C, at a minimum of once in the three-year time period prior to the land application of bulk sewage sludge unless stipulated otherwise in a site approval;_ o organic soils or peat soils must not be used for bulk sewage sludge application unless subsurface drainage is provided by a system designed according to or equivalent to Natural Resources Conservation Service engineering criteria._ * No application in June, July and August unless crop is seeded within fourteen days following the application_ * Bulk sewage sludge must not be applied on areas ponded with water or sewage sludge._ * Bulk sewage sludge must not be applied or run onto adjoining property, roads, and the shoulders and drainage ditches alongside a road._ * Bulk sewage sludge must be applied to land in such a manner as to provide uniform application._ * Bulk sewage sludge must not be disposed of or placed into any cave, or sinkhole. Except as part of a reclamation project, sewage sludge must not be disposed of or placed on any mine or quarry._ * Must supply no more available N than the calculated rates based on realistic goal, soil organic matter content, and previously grown crops_ * Must not be applied on fallow land with less than 25% vegetative cover_ * Must be applied in uniform application_ * When applied to highly permeable soils_
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	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The minimum separation distance between the zone of bulk sewage sludge application and the seasonal high water table and bedrock is five feet._ o Bulk sewage sludge must not be applied to the land during the months of June, July, August, or September unless a crop is growing on the land or a crop is seeded within 14 days following the bulk sewage sludge application._ o Bulk sewage sludge applied in October must be surface applied or applied with a nitrification stabilizer which extends the time the nitrogen component remains in the soil in the ammoniacal form.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	Yes
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	Yes
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
<p>Composition testing</p> <p><i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>Samples must be analyzed for % total solids, % volatile solids, pH, Kjeldahl nitrogen, ammonia nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium, metals and PCBs on the same schedule set forth in MN 7041.1500 Monitoring Requirements._</p> <p>Minnesota is currently working on a strategy for addressing PFAS in Biosolids.</p>
<p>Time restrictions</p> <p><i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503	No

with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted

<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>No. Once EPA establishes any additional requirements regarding PFAS and biosolids the state will evaluate the need to update the state regulation.</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>Yes. MN R. 7048 requires Type IV certified operators to oversee land application of both biosolids and industrial by-products. https://www.revisor.mn.gov/rules/7048/</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Here are some links to additional information. The land application of industrial by-products (IBP) is regulated in MN. IBP land application also require a Type IV certified operator. The requirements are similar to the land application of biosolids.</p>

Mississippi	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Mississippi Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Mississippi Administrative Code, Title 11, Part 4, Chapter 1: https://www.mdeq.ms.gov/about-mdeq/regulations/nonhazardous-solid-waste-management-regulations/
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	"Sewage Sludge" means the solid, semi-solid or liquid residue generated during treatment of municipal wastewater in a treatment works. Sewage sludge includes, but is not limited to, domestic septage; scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes; and a material derived from sewage sludge. Sewage sludge does not include ash generated during the firing of sewage sludge in a sewage sludge incinerator or grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Owners of land application sites located within the 100-year floodplain must demonstrate to the Department that the facility will not restrict the flow of the 100-year flood, reduce the temporary water storage capacity of the floodplain, or result in washout of solid waste so as to pose a hazard to human health or the environment._ * No new land application site, or lateral expansion, shall be located such that an active or inactive hydrocarbon well or an active or inactive water well would be present beneath the actual disposal area, unless the well has been adequately plugged._ * No land application within 0.5 mile of a public water supply intake structure in a surface water body. If the runoff from the site would enter the water body upgradient of the intake structure, this distance is increased to at least ten (10) miles._ * No land application within 1000 feet of any existing public water supply well, or 0.5 mile if the proposed facility is hydraulically upgradient of any existing public water supply well._

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No land application within 0.5 mile of the banks of any section of a river, stream, lake or reservoir, or coastal water classified by the Commission as recreational or shellfish harvesting_ * No land application within 250 feet of the banks of any river, stream, lake or reservoir, or coastal water_ * No land application within 0.5 mile of a national, state, county, or city park or an outdoor recreational area owned by a city, county, or public agency_ * No land application within 0.5 mile of any licensed school, licensed day-care center, licensed hospital, or licensed nursing home, unless approved by state_ * No land application within 1000 feet of any church, unless approved by state_ * No land application within one mile of a residential area, unless the proposed facility would be located in an established industrial park, in which case, no application within 1000 feet from any residential area_ * No application within 200 feet of property lines, or 100 feet if adequate on-site screening restricts views_ * No application within 300 feet from any inhabited building unless the applicant can justify otherwise. The Department may require larger buffer zones when circumstances warrant._ * No application in an area which may affect a state listed endangered or threatened species, unless in compliance with all statutes, rules, and regulations within the jurisdiction of the Mississippi Department of Wildlife, Fisheries, and Parks_ * No application in such a manner as to significantly and adversely impact the cultural resources listed in, or eligible for listing in, the National Register of Historic Places, unless such impact to those cultural resources may be appropriately mitigated_ * Without specific written consent of the person responsible for managing the property, no application with national forest land, national wilderness area, and national wildlife refuge areas, as designated by the appropriate federal agency, or within state wildlife management areas, state game management areas, and state natural areas, as designated by the Mississippi Department of Wildlife, Fisheries and Parks
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>Seasonal restrictions placed on sites located within 100-year flood plain as designated by FEMA FIRM.</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No application to saturated grounds_ * Application permitted only in a hydrologic section where the historic high water table is at a safe depth below the zone of incorporation_ * Land application of wastes must be conducted by incorporation into the soil, by injection below the land surface, or by other

	<p>appropriate means of application, as approved by the Department. Incorporation should normally be accomplished by applying the wastes uniformly and disking or plowing until the waste is adequately turned under the soil or thoroughly mixed with the soil. Incorporation must be accomplished during or immediately following application._</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Application only at an agronomic rate not to exceed the plant available nitrogen levels specified in Table 1 of Title 11, Part 4_ * Soil pH must be maintained at or above 6.5 unless otherwise authorized_ * The annual loading rate for cadmium must not exceed 0.45 pounds/acre/year_ * Cumulative loadings for certain metals based on soil CEC. See Rule 1.8, Table 2 of 11 Miss. Admin. Code Pt. 4, Ch. 1._ * pH is not inherently limited, but may be evaluated case-by-case if there is concern that application area soil pH cannot be maintained at or above 6.5.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	Yes
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	Yes
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much</i>	* For public contact sites, access shall be controlled to restrict unauthorized personnel during application and for 12 months thereafter_

<p><i>time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<p>*No crops that will be consumed raw by humans planted until at least 18 months have passed from the date of the last application_ * For crop grown for indirect human consumption, 30 days must pass between date of last application and the date the crop is planted_ * Animal grazing shall be restricted during land application operations and for 30 days thereafter</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>* Prior to land application, sewage sludges and other pathogen-containing sludges must be treated by a process to significantly reduce pathogens (PSRP) or by a process to further reduce pathogens (PFRP). These are very close to 40 CFR 503 Appendix B.</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>The cumulative (life-time) application of pollutants cannot exceed the levels specified in Table 2 of MAC Title 11, Part 4, which has more stringent limits than 40 CFR 503.13, depending on the cation exchange capacity of the soil.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>

<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>No formal plan required for biosolids, but loading rate calculations are required to be submitted prior to approval.</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>* Generally, an individual permit or a certificate of coverage of a general permit is required for the operation of a land application site_ * The land application of Class A biosolids may be managed through the state's Beneficial Use Program.</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Yes. MDEQ expects to formally add annual reporting requirements into the regulations for all permitted land application facilities to keep consistent with reporting requirements currently utilized in permit conditions. Additionally, MDEQ is exploring the</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>Yes. The land application of Class A biosolids may be managed through the state's Beneficial Use Program. See Mississippi Administrative Code, Title 11, Part 4, Chapter 9. This excludes the use and distribution of exceptional quality biosolids to from th</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No. Local land use and zoning ordinances are considered as part of the state permitting process and could influence siting criteria or permit conditions where applicable.</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If</p>	<p>Yes. "Land Application" means the incorporation of waste into the soil, the injection of waste below the land surface or other application of waste to the land for soil amendment or conditioning purposes or for biodegradation of the waste.</p>

so, please briefly describe.	
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Missouri Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Missouri Department of Natural Resources
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Links to regulations	Missouri Clean Water Law, Missouri Revised Statutes Sections 644.006.1-599:_ https://revisor.mo.gov/main/ViewChapter.aspx?chapter=644
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	While not a delegated state, Missouri can and has permitted biosolids land application governed under provisions of 10 CSR 20-6, particularly sections 20-6.010 (7)(A), 20-6.015(1)(B)(10), and 20.6.015(2)(A), which can be found here:_ https://www.sos.mo.gov/cmsimages/adrules/csr/current/10csr/10c20-6.pdf _ Standard Conditions Part III is incorporated in permits issued for all domestic wastewater facilities and biosolids land application facilities._ https://dnr.mo.gov/document-search/standard-conditions-mpdes-permits-part-iii-aug-1-2019
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	An organic fertilizer or soil amendment produced by the treatment of wastewater sludge._ This is the current definition, but the department is currently developing a revised definition._ Proposed definition: “Biosolids,” the product derived from the separation of solids from liquids at a treatment works treating domestic sewage and then further treated physically, biologically, and/or chemically. This does not include solids at the initial influent or headworks. Biosolids are also known as sewage sludge.
Biosolids classes	Class A biosolids means a material that has met the Class A pathogen reduction requirements or equivalent treatment by a Process to Further Reduce Pathogens (PFRP) in accordance with 40 CFR Part 503_ Class B biosolids means a material that has met the Class B pathogen reduction requirements or equivalent treatment by a Process to Significantly Reduce Pathogens (PSRP) in accordance with 40 CFR Part 503
Other Definitions	Standard Conditions Part III Section B – Definitions
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks	Standard Conditions Part III Section G – Land Application of Biosolids_ 6. d. Buffer zones are as follows:_

<p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> i. 300 feet of a water supply well, sinkhole, water supply reservoir or water supply intake in a stream;_ ii. 300 feet of a losing stream, no discharge stream, stream stretches designated for whole body contact recreation, wild and scenic rivers, Ozark National Scenic Riverways or outstanding state resource waters as listed in the Water Quality Standards, 10 CSR 20-7.031;_ iii. 150 feet of dwellings or public use areas;_ iv. 100 feet (35 feet if biosolids application is down-gradient or the buffer zone is entirely vegetated) of lake, pond, wetlands or gaining streams (perennial or intermittent);_ v. 50 feet of a property line. Buffer distances from property lines may be waived with written permission from neighboring property owner._ vi. For the application of dry, cake or liquid biosolids that are subsurface injected, buffer zones identified in 5.d.i. through 5.d.iii above, may be reduced to 100 feet. The buffer zone may be reduced to 35 feet if the buffer zone is permanently vegetated. Subsurface injection does not include methods or technology reflective of combination surface/shallow soil incorporation.
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>Standard Conditions Part III Section G – Land Application of Biosolids,_</p> <p>6. g. Biosolids may be land applied to sites with soil that are snow covered, frozen, or saturated with liquid when site restrictions or other controls are provided to prevent pollutants from being discharged to waters of the state during snowmelt or stormwater runoff. During inclement weather or unfavorable soil conditions use the following management practices: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> i.A maximum field slope of 6% and a minimum 300 feet grass buffer between the application site and waters of the state. A 35 feet grass buffer may be utilized for the application of dry, cake or liquid biosolids that are subsurface injected. Subsurface injection does not include the use of methods or technology reflective of combination surface/shallow soil incorporation;_ ii.A maximum field slope of 2% and 100 feet grass buffer between the application site and waters of the state. A 35 feet grass buffer may be used for the application of dry, cake or liquid biosolids that are subsurface injected. Subsurface injection does not include the use of methods or technology reflective of combination surface/shallow soil incorporation;_ iii.Other best management practices approved by the Department.
<p>Agronomic/Land-related</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>

Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p><i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	No
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	No
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	No
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	No formal plan required
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration</i></p>	Permitted

<i>of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	Undetermined
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	Yes. Septage is covered under Standard Conditions Part III, and industrial residuals are regulated under either General Permits or Site-Specific Permits.

Montana Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Montana Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	None provided
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	Biosolids management is conducted by US EPA, in accordance with 40 CFR 503. DEQ provides technical assistance only
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No

Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Unknown
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No sewage sludge incineration units in state
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions	No

<p>(e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. 17.50.801 to 17.50.820 ARM covers the land application of septage. DEQ's Solid Waste Management Section oversees these rules.</p>

Nebraska Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Nebraska Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	* Nebraska Administrative Code, Title 119, Chapter 4:_ http://dee.ne.gov/RuleAndR.nsf/RuleAndReg.xsp?documentId=8BEDCE09545A2FBF862567600057E987&action=openDocument_ * Neb. Rev. Stat. §81-1505 (8):_ https://nebraskalegislature.gov/laws/statutes.php?statute=81-1505#:~:text=(7)%20In%20adopting%20treatment%20standards,proper%20operation%20and%20maintenance%20thereof
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Bio-solids" means sewage sludge that is used or disposed through land application, surface disposal, incineration, or disposal in a municipal solid waste landfill.
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	Agronomic rate is defined as the application rate of nitrogen to meet the estimated nitrogen requirements of the crop being produced based on past or projected yields.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p><i>how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Agronomic /Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids</p>	<p>No</p>

can be applied?	
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic /land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p><i>and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	
<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>

<p><i>classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>CFR 503 with respect to pollutants ?</p>	
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>No formal plan required</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration</i></p>	<p>Unknown</p>

<p><i>of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe</p>	<p>No</p>

or provide links.	
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	No
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No

Nevada	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Nevada Division of Environmental Protection (NDEP)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	None provided
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	Land application appears to be addressed only by 40 CFR Part 503. NDEP does consider biosolids application a discharge to groundwaters of the state, so we issue our own groundwater discharge permits for the activity of biosolids land application, but we just reference the CFR rules in our permits.
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No

Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Unknown
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	No
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No

<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. NAC 444.654 Disposal of Special Wastes: Septic tank pumpings and raw sewage. (NRS 444.560): Septic tank pumpings and raw sewage must not be disposed of by land spreading, unless it is specifically determined and approved in writing by the solid waste</p>

New Hampshire	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	New Hampshire Department of Environmental Services
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	NH Administrative Code - Env-Wq 800 Sludge Management: https://www.des.nh.gov/sites/g/files/ehbemt341/files/documents/2020-01/Env-Wq%20800.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	Land application sites are regulated under site-specific permits. DES issues Sludge Quality Certifications (SQC) and Site Permits to regulate end use and disposal. There are four different types of permits or certifications required for the proper management of sludge or biosolids: Sludge Quality Certification, Sludge Hauler Permit, Sludge Facility Permit, and Biosolids Site Permit. * Residuals Management: https://www.des.nh.gov/waste/wastewater/sludge-and-septage * Manual of Best Management Practices for Land Application of Biosolids https://extension.unh.edu/resources/files/Resource005011_Rep7148.pdf
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means any sludge derived from a sewage wastewater treatment facility that meets the standards for beneficial reuse specified by the department. "Sludge derived from human waste" means sludge produced by the treatment of wastewater that contains human fecal material. Sludge is considered to be derived from human waste if any portion of the influent wastewater contains human fecal material.
Biosolids classes	"Class A biosolids" means biosolids that are class A with respect to pathogens under 40 CFR part 503.32(a)(3), and meet one of the vector attraction reduction requirements of 40 CFR part 503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8). "Class B biosolids" means biosolids that are class B with respect to pathogens under 40 CFR part 503.32(b) and meets one of the vector attraction reduction requirements of 40 CFR part 503.33(b)(1) through (b)(11). "Quality-certified sludge (QC sludge)" means sludge or a mixture of sludge that:

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Has received sludge quality certification pursuant to Env-Wq 809 or is a mixture of sludge for which each constituent sludge has received sludge quality certification; and_ o Contains nutrients or organic material, or both, that can be used:_ o To improve crop land or forested land; or_ o For reclamation._ <p>–</p> <p>The terms Class A and Class B defined same as 40 CFR 503. "QC Sludge" is used, but code states that it is not a class.</p>
Other Definitions	<p>"Agronomic rate" means the sludge application rate that is designed to: _</p> <p>(a) Provide the amount of nitrogen, phosphorus, or other nutrient(s) needed by the crop or vegetation; and _</p> <p>(b) Minimize the amount of nitrogen and phosphorus that passes below the root zone of the crop or the vegetation to groundwater or moves via run-off to surface water.</p>
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>No land application or stockpiling of QC sludge within the following buffer distances:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 250 ft: Rivers protected under RSA 483_ * 125 ft: Surface Waters not protected under RSA 483_ * 33 ft: Non-tidal Drainage Ditch_ * 400 ft: feet: Community Wells_ * 300 ft: Other Wells_ * 500 ft: Surface Drinking Water Source, Off-site Occupied Dwelling_ * 100 ft: Property Lines, On-site Occupied Dwelling_ * 25 ft: Public Roads other than Federal Interstate Highways_ * 10 ft: Federal Interstate Highways_ * 2 ft: Bedrock, Groundwater Depth
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	No QC sludge may be applied on frozen or snow-covered ground or when the ground is saturated due to precipitation or flooding.
<p>Agronomic/Land-related</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * QC sludge must be land applied at rates that conform to the approved nutrient management plan for the site permit pursuant to Env-Wq 806.07(h) and the annual updated plan required by Env-Wq 806.12(a)(5)._ * No QC sludge may be applied on agricultural land that has a slope greater than 15 percent, that is, a 15 foot rise in 100 feet._ * QC sludge spread on agricultural land that has a slope greater than 8 percent must contain a minimum of 15 percent solids or be subsurface injected._ * QC sludge must be spread uniformly over each field, at the rate specified in the approved nutrient management plan or the annual updated nutrient management plan, as applicable._

	<p>* QC sludge that is to be land applied must be processed to minimize visible or identifiable plastics or other non-biodegradable solids. _</p> <p>* No QC sludge must be applied on very poorly drained soils. _</p> <p>* For QC sludge not generated in New Hampshire, the rate of application must conform to the application rate allowed by the state of origin or Env-Wq 800, whichever results in the lower loading rate. _</p> <p>* For QC sludge not generated in New Hampshire, groundwater monitoring in accordance with Env- Wq 808 must be required for sludge management activities that would require groundwater monitoring in the state of origin. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Class A: _</p> <p>* If the biosolids are not certified as low metals under Env-Wq 809.03, the application rate may not exceed the annual application limits stated on the label required under Env-Wq 810.02;_</p> <p>* For class A biosolids not used for reclamation, land application rates may not exceed 200 pounds of nitrogen per acre unless recommended by a certified crop advisor. _</p> <p>* Land application of biosolids within a designated river corridor must comply with the requirements relative to set-backs and immediate incorporation into the soil specified in RSA 483:9, VI(c), RSA 483:9-a, VII(d), RSA 483:9-aa, VII(b), or RSA 483:9-b, VII(b), as applicable. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Other Than Class A Biosolids: _</p> <p>* Any QC sludge that contains class B biosolids and any QC sludge used for reclamation that is applied at rates exceeding 1,500 pounds of nitrogen per acre or that does not have a carbon-to-nitrogen ratio between 30:1 and 40:1 may be land applied only at a site permitted pursuant to testing constituents as per Env-Wq 806</p>
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits	No

to application rates?	
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	<p>Testing Constituents Required For All QC Sludge: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sludge must be analyzed for the constituents listed in Table 809-2, in accordance with the methods specified. _ * Testing for enteric viruses as specified in Table 809-2 required only for generators of class B biosolids requesting certification of the biosolids for reclamation uses. _ * The constituents required to be analyzed are specified in Table 809-2_ * Each year, the sludge quality certification holder must analyze sludge from its generating facility for the constituents identified in Table 809-2, sections A, B, D, and F, together with antimony, beryllium, silver, and thallium from section C, using the analytical methods and detection limits specified in the table._ <p>Post-Certification Testing Required For QC Sludge. _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The sludge quality certification holder must analyze the QC sludge from its generating facility at the frequencies specified in Table 809-3 for the parameters listed in Table 809-2, section E, and for the metals in Table 809-2, section C, except for antimony, beryllium, silver, and thallium, in accordance with the analytical methods and detection limits specified: _ * Table 809-3 provides testing frequencies, which are different than those prescribed in 40 CFR 503 _ * Each year, the sludge quality certification holder must analyze sludge from its generating facility for the constituents identified in Table 809-2, sections A, B, D, and F, together with antimony, beryllium, silver, and thallium from section C, using the analytical methods and detection limits specified in the table. _ * Generators of class B biosolids proposing to maintain certification of the biosolids for reclamation uses also must test for enteric viruses as specified in Table 809-2, section G.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Meeting vector attraction reduction by incorporation or injection is not allowed.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	Yes
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	More restrictive limits and additional pollutants than 40 CFR 503, as in Env-Wq 809.03 Criteria for Review.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	Yes

<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>No transport of sludge that is not QC sludge to a site permitted under Env-Wq 806.</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>Under the QC permit, must submit a management plan. The plan includes: _ _</p> <p>* An estimate of the maximum amount of nitrogen, or phosphorus if phosphorus is the limiting nutrient, that will be applied on an annual basis to meet the nutrient requirements of</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>Class A biosolids may not be stockpiled or applied within 35 feet of surface water or within 250 feet of the normal high water mark of a designated river_</p> <p>Water treatment sludge may be land applied only as a mineral component in a mixture of sludge or other organic residuals. Unmixed water treatment residuals must not be applied to agricultural land unless allowed by a permit; _</p> <p>NH has finalized regulations eliminating some application information, testing, and reporting requirements that have been shown to be unnecessary (e.g. testing for analytes never found at significant levels in biosolids), which may not be reflected above.</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

New Jersey	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	New Jersey Department of Environmental Protection
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	* New Jersey Administrative Code, N.J.A.C. 7:14A (especially subchapter 20):_ http://www.state.nj.us/dep/dwq/714a.htm _ * New Jersey Administrative Code, N.J.A.C. 7:14C (Sludge Quality Assurance Regulations):_ https://dep.nj.gov/wp-content/uploads/rules/rules/njac7_14c.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" is not defined. "Sewage sludge" means the solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue generated by the processes of a domestic treatment works. Sewage sludge includes, but is not limited to, domestic septage; scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes; and any material derived from sewage sludge. Sewage sludge does not include ash generated during the firing of sewage sludge in a sewage sludge incinerator or grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works.
Biosolids classes	"Exceptional quality" means, for a residual generated under a NJPDES permit, that the ceiling concentrations in 40 CFR 503.13(b)1, the pollutant concentrations in 40 CFR 503.13(b)3, the Class A pathogen requirements in 40 CFR 503.32(a), and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33(b)1 through 8 are met._ - Class A sludge conforms to 40 CFR Part 503.32(a)_ - Class B sludge conforms to 40 CFR 503.32 (b)
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means the whole residual application rate on a dry weight basis designed: _ 1. To provide the amount of nitrogen or other nutrients needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop or vegetation grown on the land; _ 2. To minimize the amount of nitrogen or other nutrients from residual and all other fertilizer sources that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the ground water or that runs off to surface waters; and _

	<p>3. To provide the amount of calcium or magnesium oxides capable of neutralizing soil acidity. _</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Marketable residual product" or "sludge-derived product" means any residual or material derived from a residual which has been prepared for land application of residual in accordance with a permit issued pursuant to N.J.A.C. 7:14A-20 and which, at a minimum, meets the pollutant concentrations in 40 CFR 503.13(b)(1), the Class B pathogen requirements in 40 CFR 503.32 and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8). _</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Sludge" means the solid residue and associated liquid resulting from the physical, chemical or biological treatment of domestic or industrial wastewaters. _</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Residual" means a solid waste that consists of the accumulated solids and associated liquids which are by-products of a physical, chemical, biological, or mechanical process or any other process designed to treat wastewater or any other discharges subject to regulation under the State Act. Residual includes, but is not limited to, marketable residual product, sludge and sewage sludge. Residual excludes screened vegetative waste and grit and screenings. _</p> <p>–</p> <p>"Letter of Land Application Management Approval" or "LLAMA" means the letter issued by the Department pursuant to N.J.A.C. 7:14A-20 and the Statewide Sludge Management Plan, containing a determination that use of residual or the operations at a residual land application site satisfy the requirements of the New Jersey Water Pollution Control Act, N.J.S.A. 58:10A-1 et seq., if operated consistently with the requirements stated within the letter.</p>
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State Regulatory Details

<p>Setbacks</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>The following buffer areas should be observed. However, the actual buffer areas may be made more or less stringent in the permit depending on the nature of the site, the recommendations of the NRCS, or the scope of the proposed project. _</p> <p>–</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No application of bulk residual within 200 feet of surface water, as defined in N.J.A.C. 7:14A-1.2_ * No application to land saturated with water to within two feet of the ground surface, where soil depth is less than two feet over bedrock formations, or that experiences seasonal flooding;_ * No application within 1,500 feet of public community water supply wells;_ * No application within 300 feet of public non-community or non-public water supply wells, unless a signed waiver has been obtained
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	<p>from the well and property owner(s) and approved by the Department;_</p> <p>* No application within 200 feet of occupied neighbor's buildings, unless a signed waiver has been obtained from the person(s) occupying the building(s);_</p> <p>* No application within 50 feet from property boundaries which are not part of the user site, unless a signed waiver has been obtained from the property owner(s);_</p> <p>* No application within 50 feet of farm irrigation wells and monitoring wells; or_</p> <p>* No application within 10 feet from a road or lane which is not a property boundary, excluding on-site lanes constructed for the movement of farm equipment, including residuals hauling and application equipment. Residuals application may take place up to but not upon on-site lanes.</p>
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Unless otherwise specified by the Department, bulk residual may not be applied during or after precipitation on ground where water is ponded, soils are saturated with water to within two feet of the ground surface, soil depth is less than two feet over bedrock formations, or land experiences seasonal flooding
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	A conservation plan or soil erosion and sediment control plan (as applicable) certified by the County Soil Conservation District or equivalent, unless waived by NRCS, is required. All details with regards to crops, application rates (N or P), and application methods are based on the Conservation Plan submitted and P index.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No

<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>Sludge must be analyzed for any of a number of characteristics prescribed by the permittee's NJPDES permit, including total solids, pH, total Kjeldahl nitrogen, ammonia, nitrate, calcium, phosphorus, water extractable phosphorus, potassium, metals and radium. For residual that is to be applied to the land, the frequency of monitoring for the pollutants listed in Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 of 40 CFR 503.13, for the pathogen density requirements in 40 CFR 503.32(a) and 40 CFR 503.32(b)(2) through (b)(4), when applicable, and for the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8), when applicable, is specified in Table 1 of 40 CFR 503.16(a), with some exceptions._</p> <p>– All generators are also required to test sludge in accordance with the Sludge Quality Assurance Regulations (N.J.A.C. 7:14C) which requires more extensive testing than provided for under 40 CFR Part 503.</p>
<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>

Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Sludge may not be applied to land if the concentration of pollutants in the sludge exceeds the ceiling concentrations in 40 CFR 503.13(b)1, and the pollutant concentrations in 40 CFR 503.13(b)3
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	* A permit is required for imported bulk or bagged exceptional or non-exceptional quality sludge._ * Trucks transporting Marketable Residual Products are exempt from hauling registration requirements. _
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	Nutrient Management Plans are required for all non-exceptional quality land application sites as part of the permit application.
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	The Department has broad authority to impose restrictions on a case-by-case basis.
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured?	Yes. Soil Remediation standards:_ https://dep.nj.gov/wp-content/uploads/rules/rules/njac7_26d.pdf

<p>If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. For septage, in accordance with N.J.A.C. 7:14A-20.7(f), domestic treatment works are preferred for management of septage, but land application is allowed if no other option. Currently no permits._ For other types of material: General permit is availa</p>

New Mexico	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	New Mexico Environment Department
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	None provided
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No

Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Unknown
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate	No

land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No

New York Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	New York State Department of Environmental Conservation (NYSDEC)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	New York Code Part 360 and 361: https://dec.ny.gov/regulatory/regulations/parts-360-366-and-369-solid-waste-management
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means the accumulated solids or solids resulting from treatment of wastewaters from publicly or privately owned or operated sewage treatment plants. Biosolids does not include grit or screenings, or ash generated from the incineration of biosolids.
Biosolids classes	Class A biosolids require additional pathogen reduction and vector attraction reduction criteria beyond 40 CFR 503. The acceptable methods can be found here: Part 361-3.7_ _ Class B sludge conforms to the definition in 40 CFR 503.32 (b)
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means the whole sludge application rate, on a dry weight basis, designed to provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop or vegetation grown on the land, and designed to minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the groundwater.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Section 361-2.5(b)(1) outlines restricts land application as follows:_ * No application within 50 feet of a property line_ * No application within 500 feet of a residence, place of business, or public contact area when waste is not injected, or 200 feet if it is. _ * No application within 200 feet of a potable water well_ * No application within 200 feet of surface water and State regulated wetland when waste is not injected, 100 feet if it is_ * No application within 25 feet of a drainage swale_ * Application is prohibited in areas where groundwater is within 24 inches of the ground surface at the time of application._ * Application is prohibited in areas where bedrock lies less than 24 inches below the ground surface
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes

<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>* Biosolids may not be applied on saturated soils or during significant rainfall events. Land application is prohibited on snow-covered or frozen ground except by direct injection below the land surface.</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>* Application rates must be based on Cornell University guidance or similar. _ * Application rates should not exceed the nitrogen need of the crop being fertilized. _ * The pH of the soil must be 6.0 or greater at the time the biosolids are applied. _ * The hydraulic loading must not exceed 16,000 gallons per acre in a 24 hour period. _ * Land application is prohibited on land with a slope exceeding 15 percent. Land application of waste with a total solids content of less than 15 percent is prohibited on land with a slope greater than 8 percent, unless incorporated within 1 hour of application along paths parallel to contour lines for the land._ * Land application is prohibited in special flood hazard areas unless approved by the department. _ * The land application rate must not exceed the lower of the agronomic rate or, for waste with neutralizing value, the application rate needed to achieve a soil pH value in an acceptable range for the crop grown._ * The department can restrict the application rate based on a nutrient other than nitrogen, such as phosphorus. The application rate must be sufficiently reduced to ensure appropriate application rates are not exceeded if supplemental fertilizer (including manure) will be applied to the site._ * In all cases, the waste must be incorporated into the soil within 24 hours after application, unless a cover crop would be damaged by incorporation and concerns regarding odor and run-off can be mitigated by other means approved by the department. If incorporation is used for vector attraction reduction, the period before incorporation is limited to six hours or less._ * Land application is permitted on all soil types that are capable of supporting the robust growth of the crop grown. The use of active farmland is sufficient to demonstrate compliance with this requirement. Otherwise, sufficient information must be provided to demonstrate compliance._ * Proper soil conservation practices and agricultural management practices must be used to minimize run-off and soil loss through erosion.</p>
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?</p>	<p>No</p>

Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	* The required parameters for analysis are found in Table 1 in section 361-3.9 and include total Kjeldahl nitrogen, ammonia, nitrate, total phosphorus and potassium, pH, total solids, total volatile solids, pathogens, and metals, including chromium and molybdenum _ * The minimum number of analyses, for each biosolids source is outlined in Table 2 and 3 in section 361-3.9.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	* Maximum concentrations of Pollutant Limits in mg/kg, dry weight can be found in 361-3.9 Table 6. These are more restrictive than 40 CFR 503.13
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	Yes
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows Truck transport of biosolids requires a permit under 6NYCRR Part 364.
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	* Fields may only receive biosolids once per year. _ * If the soil has received biosolids in the past two years, the residual nitrogen in the soil must be included in the nutrient loading calculations. The residual nitrogen must be subtracted from the nit
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	* A State Environmental Quality Review (SEQR) must be provided with the permit application. This process also requires a public notice to be printed and a public comment period of 15-30 days which may necessitate a public meeting if the department receives enough comments. _ * Permittees obtain approval from the department for each site on which Class B biosolids are applied in bulk prior to land application._ * Temporary field stacking of biosolids prior to land application is allowed for 30 days, under certain conditions
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next	Undetermined

<p>two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>Yes. We consider land application to be Class B. If you are interested in Class A (compost, etc.), those regulations are found in 361-3.</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Septage land application is regulated under 361-2.3(d). Compost and other processing facilities are regulated under 361-3.</p>

North Carolina	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	North Carolina Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	NC Administrative Code: 15A NCAC 02T Section - 1100 Residuals Management:_ http://reports.oah.state.nc.us/ncac/title%2015a%20-%20environmental%20quality/chapter%2002%20-%20environmental%20management/subchapter%20t/subchapter%20t%20rules.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biological residuals" means residuals that have been generated during the treatment of domestic wastewater, the treatment of animal processing wastewater, or the biological treatment of industrial wastewater.
Biosolids classes	No classes in definitions. The terms Class A and B are used in accordance with 40 CFR 503.
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" is defined as the amount of waste and other materials applied to meet the nitrogen needs of the crop, but does not overload the soil with nutrients or other constituents that cause or contribute to a contravention of surface water or groundwater standards, limit crop growth, or adversely impact soil quality. Nitrogen needs of the crop must be based on realistic yield expectations (RYE) established for a soil series through published Cooperative Extension Service bulletins, Natural Resources Conservation Service publications, county soil surveys, or site specific agronomist reports._ _ "Residuals" means any solid, semisolid, or liquid waste, other than effluent or residues from agricultural products and processing, generated from a wastewater treatment facility, water supply treatment facility or air pollution control facility permitted under the authority of the Commission.
State Regulatory Details	

<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>A substantial list of setbacks, too numerous to summarize here, are defined in section .1108. These are based on whether solid or liquid is applied and the method of application.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>No land application: _ * within the 100-year flood elevation unless the bulk residuals are injected or incorporated within a 24-hour period following the residuals land application event; _ * during precipitation events or within 24 hours following a rainfall event of 0.5 inches or greater in a 24-hour period;</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>No land application: _ * if the requirements specified by 40 CFR 503.14(a) cannot be met _ * if the application causes prolonged nuisance conditions; _ * if the land fails to assimilate the bulk residuals or the application causes the contravention of surface water or groundwater standards; _ * if the slope of the land is greater than 10 percent when bulk liquid residuals are surface applied, and if the slope of the land is greater than 18 percent when bulk liquid residuals are injected or incorporated; _ * if the land does not have an established vegetative cover crop unless the bulk residuals are incorporated within a 24-hour period following the residuals land application event or injected; _ * if the vertical separation of the seasonal high water table and the depth of residuals application is less than one foot; _ * if the vertical separation of the depth to bedrock and the depth of residuals application is less than one foot; or _ * if application exceeds agronomic rates except for dedicated sites where the applicant has specifically requested higher rates in an applications pursuant to Rule .1104(d) of this Section._ _</p> <p>An application requires a soils report and can be found in section .1104 d and c. _ A soils report is also required for new and expanding land application sites, as per section .1104, which includes the following parameters: acidity; base saturation (by calculation); calcium; cation exchange capacity; copper; exchangeable sodium percentage (by calculation); magnesium; manganese; percent humic matter; pH; phosphorus; potassium; sodium, and zinc.</p>

Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants</p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>

<p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	No
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	No
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	No required formal nutrient management plans. North Carolina does not currently manage or control the application of phosphorus in biosolids.
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	Permitted

<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>NC DEQ has a webpage specific to septage: https://deq.nc.gov/about/divisions/waste-management/waste-management-rules/septage and regulations: Septage Management Rules 15A NCAC 13B .0830-.0846</p>
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General Assessment Questions

<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations?</p>	<p>No</p>

Please provide names of these entities if so.	
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	Yes. Septage is regulated separately._ Composts are regulated separately if not more than 50% biosolids.

North Dakota	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	North Dakota Department of Health; however, EPA administers the biosolids program
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Links to regulations	None provided
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No

Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Unknown
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No sewage sludge incineration units in state
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate	No

land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	No

Ohio	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Ohio Environmental Protection Agency
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Ohio Administrative Code 3745-40:_ https://codes.ohio.gov/ohio-administrative-code/chapter-3745-40
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means sewage sludge or mixtures containing sewage sludge that have been treated for beneficial use.
Biosolids classes	<p>Exceptional quality biosolids_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Meet Class A standards for pathogens under alternatives 1, 2, or 6 in 40 CFR 503.32_ o were treated with one of the vector attraction reduction options outlined in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8) and_ o meet metals concentration limits outlined in Table 1 and 3 of 40 CFR 503.13_ <p>_</p> <p>Class A is defined in accordance with 40 CFR 503_</p> <p>_</p> <p>Class B biosolids _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o have been treated with one of the pathogen reduction methods outlined in 40 CFR 503.32 (b)_ o were treated with one the vector attraction reduction options outlined in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-10) and_ o meet metals concentration limits outlined in Table 1 and, as applicable, 3 of 40 CFR 503.13
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means a rate of application of nutrients from any source to the land or an amount of nutrients removed by crop based on:_ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Nutrient content of the biosolids to be applied;_ o Nutrient needs of the current or planned crops; and_ o Nutrient holding capacity of the soil.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	<p>Application of Bulk EQ and Class B:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Must maintain a 3 foot distance from bedrock_ * Must maintain a 33 foot distance from surface waters_ * Must maintain a 300 foot distance from a sinkhole or UIC class V drainage well if no grass buffer, but 100 feet with grass buffer_ <p>Application of Class B only:_</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * If surface applied, must maintain 300 feet from an occupied structure/school or private, potable water source; if injected or immediately incorporated, 100 feet._ * If surface applied, must maintain 1000 feet from a medical care facility; if injected or immediately incorporated, 300 feet_ * No application within the sanitary isolation distance a public water system, as established in rule 3745-9-04 of the Administrative Code_ * No application within an emergency management zone for a public water system using surface water or within 1500 feet of the intake where no such zone has been established._ * No application within the inner management zone of a community or non-transient, non-community public water system. Further restrictions if area is highly susceptible to contamination._ * No application within 300 feet of a drinking water supply well for a transient, non-community public water system._ Field Storage Bulk EQ and Class B:_ * Must maintain a 3 foot distance from bedrock_ * Must maintain a 100 foot distance from surface waters_ * Must maintain a 300 foot distance from a sinkhole or UIC class V drainage well_ * Can only be field stored for 90 days, provided best management practices are implemented. Regional storage facilities are allowed._ Storage Class B only:_ * Must maintain 300 feet from an occupied structure/school or private, potable water source_ * Must maintain 1000 feet from a medical care facility_ * Field storage prohibited if utilizing vector attraction reduction method options 9 & 10_ * Additional requirements for storage are outlined in OAC 3745-40-07 (D)(3)
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>Bulk EQ and Class B_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * No beneficial use on frozen or snow-covered ground. _ * No beneficial use on the surface of a beneficial use site when the top two inches are saturated. _ * For hydrological soil groups A, B, and C, cannot beneficially use class B or bulk exceptional quality biosolids during a precipitation event, or when the forecast indicates that there is at least a fifty per cent chance that 0.5 -inch of rain will occur within twenty-four hours after beneficial use unless injected, immediately incorporated, or can prove less than 0.5 inches actually fell_ * The same is true for hydrological soil group D, except the rainfall limit is 0.25 inches_ * _

	<p>* No application at a beneficial use site that is frequently flooded such that biosolids may enter surface waters of the state, except where allowed by NPDES permit. Same day incorporation or injection on areas that are frequently flooded during periods when flooding is expected.</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>* Soil test P indications_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o If Bray-Kurtz P1 < 40 ppm or Mehlich III < 58 ppm, then agronomic rate is calculated as either the nitrogen agronomic rate or a defined phosphate beneficial use rate_ o If 100 ppm > Bray-Kurtz P1 extraction > 40 ppm or 130 ppm > Mehlich III extraction > 58 ppm, then the agronomic rate is calculated as either the nitrogen agronomic rate or a multi-year phosphate agronomic rate_ o _ o If Bray-Kurtz P1 extraction > 100 ppm or Mehlich III extraction > 130 ppm, then the agronomic rate is calculated using the phosphorus index_ o For all beneficial use sites, beneficial of class B or bulk exceptional quality biosolids may be completed in accordance with the phosphorus index._ o Before application, soil P and pH must be re-measured if last results are older than 3 years._ <p>* Under defined circumstances, the agronomic rate may be exceeded during land reclamation projects using biosolids_</p> <p>* Ground slope can't be over 20% unless same day incorporation or injection is done or the field is established and managed in contour strips with alternate strips in cover crop, pasture, or vegetation._</p> <p>* The beneficial use of liquid biosolids must be at or below the agronomic rate for the reasonably expected yield goal of planned crops or crop rotation, or at or below the available water capacity of the upper eight inches of soil, whichever is less at the time of use._</p> <p>* Minimum soil pH for beneficial use of class B biosolids = 5.5. If < 5.5, liming material must be added such that the class B biosolids and soil mixture pH = 5.5 or greater._</p> <p>* Where there is subsurface tile drainage_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o application must stop if biosolids reach the subsurface drain outlet to surface waters_ o application rates must be less than or equal to 0.5 -inch or thirteen thousand gallons per acre per beneficial use event_ o Measures must be taken to keep liquid biosolids out of preferential flow channels _ o Before injecting liquid biosolids, soil must be tilled at least 3 inches below the injection depth. The biosolids can only be injected deep enough to cover them with soil._ o If tillage isn't an option, tiles outlet must be plugged and tile stops closed before or during beneficial use of biosolids. _ <p>* For soil P < 100 ppm Bray-Kurtz (130 Mehlich III), the nitrogen rate must be used if it is the most limiting rate calculated. Ohio EPA has</p>

	an online compliance tool available that may be used to determine the correct agronomic rate.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	For EQ biosolids, at least seven grab samples for pathogen reduction (either fecal coliform or Salmonella) must be taken and analyzed at least once per reporting period and all seven results shall meet the limits specified in OAC 3745-40-04(B)._ * Methods for analysis most comply with 40 CFR Part 136 or Table A-1 of Administrative Code 3745-40-09_ * Analyze and test frequency requirements are designated in 3745-40-09
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids</i>	* Class B biosolids may not be placed on any site that is not dedicated as an authorized beneficial use site_

<i>can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	<p>* Distribution of biosolids that are not exceptional quality is prohibited_</p> <p>* Only exceptional quality biosolids are permitted for use on a lawn or home garden_</p> <p>* No mixing of class B biosolids from different treatment works at an authorized beneficial use site, unless compliant with paragraph C of rule 3745-40-06 of the Administrative Code</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	* Special restrictions apply if biosolids subject to the cumulative pollutant loading rates have been beneficially used at the authorized beneficial use site since July 20, 1993.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	* Biosolids may be transferred to another treatment works provided that said treatment works has an NPDES permit or a management plan for the treatment, storage, transfer, or disposal of sewage sludge or biosolids, or the beneficial use of biosolids.
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	No formal plan required. For Class B and bulk EQ biosolids, the agronomic rate shall be calculated prior to beneficial use for each beneficial use site. The calculations shall be submitted with the Annual Sewage Sludge Report.
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	Ohio does not have delegation for incineration.
Other regulatory details	* Class A biosolids not defined_

<p><i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>* Odors must be minimized when beneficially using biosolids_ * The surface disposal of sewage sludge or biosolids is prohibited._ * Ohio does not have delegation for the land application of domestic septage.</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. *Ohio does not have delegation for the land application of domestic septage. Local health departments may have additional land application requirements. _ *Other organic residuals may be eligible for a Land Application Management Plan (LAMP) through</p>

Oklahoma Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Oklahoma Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Oklahoma Administrative Code Title 252, Chapter 606: https://www.deq.ok.gov/asd/rules-and-regulations/
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means primarily organically treated wastewater materials from municipal wastewater treatment plants that are suitable for recycling as amendments.
Biosolids classes	Class A biosolids meet the pathogen reduction requirements of 40 CFR § 503.32 (a) Class B biosolids meet the pathogen reduction requirements of 40 CFR § 503.32 (b) and the vector attraction requirements of 40 CFR 503.33
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	* Class B biosolids cannot be land applied within two (2) feet of the highest seasonal water table nor applied to the land within one hundred (100) feet of a stream or body of water_ * Class B biosolids cannot be land applied within two hundred fifty (250) feet of a public or private water supply
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	* No application can occur on land having a slope exceeding five percent (5%) but less than ten percent (10%) unless erosion or runoff controls are implemented for liquid biosolids. Land having a slope greater than ten percent (10%) may be utilized for land application of dewatered and dried biosolids only with DEQ approval._ * Sludge must be land applied in a manner to prevent surface runoff and to control objectionable odors and incorporated into the soil before the end of each working day. _ * Sludge or wastewater cannot be stored on, land applied to, or allowed to run off to wetlands or waters of the state._

	<p>* Any site with soil having a natural pH of less than 5.5 cannot be used for the land application of biosolids unless the soil pH is amended prior to application of biosolids._</p> <p>* Annual biosolids land application rate cannot exceed nitrogen and phosphorus rates for the crop grown and cannot be applied in rates that result in phytotoxicity._</p> <p>* Permit applications include soil samples for metals, pH, nitrogen, ammonia, nitrates, potassium, and phosphorus_</p> <p>* The DEQ cannot approve the land application of biosolids that contains heavy metals above the concentration ranges normal to biosolids or sludges with a demonstrated effectiveness on Oklahoma soils, unless the permittee provides a study on the effects of the biosolids on a variety of Oklahoma soils and crops found at the location of the proposed land application site._</p> <p>* The use of land application sites that overlie areas subject to karstification (i.e. sink holes or underground streams generally occurring in areas underlain by limestone, gypsum or dolomite), is prohibited, unless approved by the DEQ</p>
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	* Class B sludge management plans must include information on how biosolids will be transported from the point of generation to the use, land application or disposal site, including transfer and storage information and a map showing the location of source
Nutrient management plans	No formal plan required

State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program	
Incineration Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative	Permitted
Other regulatory details Any other information related to the land application of biosolids	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Approved sludge management plan required as part of permitting for application of biosolids (Class A or B)_ * Surface disposal is prohibited_ * Composted Class A biosolids are defined and regulated under 252:606-8-4_ * Only one land applier is allowed at a time from only one source facility or surface impoundment unless more appliers/sources are approved
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	No
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	No
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If	Yes. DEQ regulates composting facilities under OAC 252:515 "Management of Solid Waste".

so, please briefly describe.	
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Oregon	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Oregon Department of Environmental Quality_ Oregon Department of Agriculture
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	More than one agency
Links to regulations	* Oregon Administrative Rules Chapter 340, Division 50- Land Application Of Domestic Wastewater Treatment Facility Biosolids, Biosolids Derived Products, And Domestic Septage_ * Oregon Revised Statutes 568.900-933, establishing agricultural water quality management plans/rules, and OAR Chapter 603, Division 95
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means solids derived from primary, secondary, or advanced treatment of domestic wastewater which have been treated through one or more controlled processes that significantly reduce pathogens and reduce volatile solids or chemically stabilize solids to the extent that they do not attract vectors. This term refers to domestic wastewater treatment facility solids that have undergone adequate treatment to permit their land application. This term has the same meaning as the term "sludge" in ORS 468B.095, and the term "sewage sludge" found elsewhere in OAR 340.
Biosolids classes	Same as 40 CFR 503. "Exceptional Quality Biosolids" means domestic wastewater treatment facility solids containing trace pollutant concentrations which are below federal pollutant limits recognized under 40 CFR §503.13(b)(3) that have been treated by a Class A pathogen reduction process recognized under 40 CFR §503.32(a) and one of the vector attraction reduction procedures established under 40 CFR §503.33(b)(1)-(8)._ — The term Class A and B are used in accordance with 40 CFR 503
Other Definitions	"Agronomic Application Rate" means a rate of biosolids or domestic septage application which matches nutrient requirements for specific crop on an annual basis._ — "Biosolids Derived Products" means materials derived from composting domestic wastewater treatment facility solids or other processes, such as thermal drying, which result in a material which meets pollutant concentrations in 40 CFR §503.13(b)(3), the Class A pathogen requirements in 40 CFR §503.32(a) and one of the vector

	attraction procedures in 40 CFR §503.33(b)(1) to §503.33(b)(8). Biosolids derived products also include any soil amendments which, in part, contain biosolids meeting these criteria. Biosolids derived products are acceptable for distribution to the general public for immediate use.
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * When liquid biosolids or domestic septage are applied, the minimum depth to permanent groundwater should be four feet and the minimum depth to temporary groundwater should be one foot._ * Soil should have a minimum rooting depth of 24 inches. The underlying substratum to at least 24 inches should not be rapidly draining so that leachate will not be short-circuited to groundwater._ * No bulk Class B biosolids or domestic septage should be spread at the site closer than 50 feet to any ditch, channel, pond or waterway or within 200 feet of a domestic water source or well_ * Approving the application of biosolids or domestic septage on land that is in close proximity to residential areas demands certain measures be taken, as determined by the department on a case-by-case basis._ * Buffer strips should be provided along well traveled highways.
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	Yes
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Where a site has previously been amended with biosolids at soil improvement or reclamation rates, documentation of background soil nitrate-nitrogen (NO₃-N) must be submitted for Department approval prior to the application of additional biosolids_ * When biosolids will be applied above normal agronomic rates for the purpose of land reclamation, the Department may require that an evaluation for potential groundwater quality impacts be conducted_ * Biosolids imports must be applied at agronomic rates_ * Bulk biosolids or domestic septage applied to any Department authorized land spreading sites can't exceed the agronomic rate for the cultivar grown_ * Performance monitoring for residual soil nitrate is required when any biosolids applications exceed 2 out of 3 years at agronomic rates_ * Bulk biosolids or domestic septage must be applied using rates and methods which prevent runoff, erosion, leaching, nuisances, or the likelihood of groundwater contamination_ * Sites should be on a stable geologic formation not subject to flooding or excessive runoff from adjacent land. If periodic flooding

	<p>cannot be avoided, the period of application should be restricted and soil incorporation is recommended._</p> <p>* Runoff and erosion control measures should be constructed where needed._</p> <p>* Liquid biosolids or domestic septage should not be surface applied on bare soils where the ground slope exceeds 12 percent. _</p> <p>* Well-vegetated sites with slopes up to 30 percent may be used for dewatered or dried biosolids, or for liquid biosolids or domestic septage application with appropriate management to prevent runoff._</p> <p>* Sites with saline and/or sodic soils should be avoided</p>
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
<p>Composition testing</p> <p><i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>Nitrate-nitrogen, ammonia nitrogen, total Kjeldahl nitrogen (TKN), phosphorus, potassium, total solids, volatile solids, arsenic, cadmium, copper, lead, mercury, molybdenum, nickel, selenium, zinc, and pH must all be analyzed in samples as part of a required management plan (does not apply to septage management plans – only pH is required of alkaline stabilized septage)</p>
<p>Time restrictions</p> <p><i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<p>* Exceptional Quality biosolids and biosolids derived products may be used on indoor and outdoor ornamental plants, shrubs, trees, home gardens and lawns, and high public contact areas without restricting public access_</p> <p>* Controlled access to bulk Class B domestic biosolids and domestic septage land application sites is required for a minimum of 12 months following surface application of solids. Access control is assumed on rural private land._</p>

	<p>* Crops grown for direct human consumption should not be planted for at least 14 months after bulk Class B biosolids or domestic septage application. If the edible parts will not be in contact with the Class B biosolids or domestic septage amended soil, or if the crop is to be treated or processed prior to marketing such that pathogen contamination is not a concern, this requirement may be waived for root crops pursuant to § 503.32(b)(5)</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>* Land application requires the following conditions be met_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Pollutant concentration and cumulative pollutant loading limits required under 40 CFR §503.13 (but not for domestic septage)_ o One of the pathogen reduction standards established under 40 CFR §503.32_ o One of the vector attraction reduction standards required under 40 CFR §503.33_ o Management practices required under 40 CFR §503.14 and 40 CFR §503.32(b)(5)_ <p>* Biosolids derived products must meet_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o pollutant concentration and loading limits required under 40 CFR §503.13_ o federal Class A pathogen reduction standards pursuant to 40 CFR §503.32(a)_ o one of the vector attraction reduction standards required under 40 CFR §503.33(b)(1)-(8)_ <p>* Biosolids imports must meet_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o 40 CFR §503.13(b)(1), Table 1 pollutant ceiling concentration limits_ o one of the 40 CFR §503.32(b) Class B pathogen reduction standards_ o one of the 40 CFR §503.33(b)(1)-(8) vector attraction reduction standards_ o minimum biosolids quality requirements of the County, State, or Regional government where they are produced_ <p>* Domestic septage tank pumpings must be brought to at least pH 12 through alkaline addition for 30 minutes or more_</p> <p>* Domestic holding tank, chemical toilet, and vault toilet pumpings need to be mixed 1:3 with domestic septic tank pumpings before alkaline addition to raise the pH to 12 for 2 hours of mixing followed by at least 22 additional hours of reaction. Final pH must be at least 11.5.</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>

<i>requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	State requires facilities to develop and implement nutrient management plans which are included in the facility's biosolids management plan. Once these plans are reviewed and approved by the department they become enforceable permit conditions.
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	* BMPs are recommended in the code alongside regulatory requirements
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory	No

details that may potentially change	
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	Yes. Each land application site is issued a site authorization that identifies additional site specific requirements and restrictions. Only one municipality can apply biosolids on any given field.
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	Yes. Kalamath County requires major facilities to land apply only Class A biosolids. Minor facilities can land apply either Class A or Class B biosolids.
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.	Yes. Regulated similar to biosolids for nutrient management.

Pennsylvania	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Pennsylvania Department of Environmental Protection (DEP)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	PA Administrative Code - Title 25, Pa. Code, Chapter 271, Subchapter J: https://www.pacode.com/secure/data/025/chapter271/subchapJtoc.html
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	<p>The term "sewage sludge" is used through the regulation, but no formal definition is provided._</p> <p>Domestic sewage: Waste and wastewater from humans or household operations that is discharged to or otherwise enters a treatment works._</p> <p>The general permits define biosolids as: "Sewage sludge" as defined by Title 25 Pa. Code §271.1 that meets, at a minimum, the pollutant quality standards listed in Title 25 Pa. Code §271.914(b)(1), one of the Class B pathogen reduction alternatives listed in §271.932(b), and one of the vector attraction reduction options listed in §271.933 (b)(1)-(10)."²</p>
Biosolids classes	<p>Exceptional Quality biosolids (EQ biosolids) meet specific treatment standards and are therefore not subject to certain management practices, such as land application isolation distances. These may be licensed by PDA as a fertilizer or soil amendment. Application and storage of EQ biosolids are required to meet PA DEP General Permit (PAG-07), and/or an individual farm permit. User instructions, which include nutrient content and land application rates, are issued by the generator and must be followed._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Non-exceptional quality biosolids are referred to as biosolids in this document. Biosolids are covered by a General Permit (PAG-08) with a 30-day first land application notice to DEP, or an individual farm permit (PABIS). Farms receiving biosolids should have either a 30-day notice on file at DEP that includes farm maps and application areas or have an individual farm permit._</p> <p>–</p> <p>Residential Septage, effluent from septic tanks, falls under the biosolids regulations and requires a PAG-09 General Permit for land application. Residential Septage, for this document, will be considered as biosolids.</p>

Other Definitions	<p>Agronomic rate: _</p> <p>The annual whole sludge application rate (dry weight basis) designed to do the following: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, silvicultural crop, cover crop, horticultural crop or vegetation grown on the land. _ * Minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the groundwater. _
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks</p> <p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>Non-Exceptional quality biosolids may not be applied to agricultural land, forest or a reclamation site that is: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Within 100 feet or less of a perennial stream or within 33 feet of an intermittent stream; _ * Within 100 feet of the edge of a sink hole; _ * Within 300 feet from an occupied dwelling unless the current owner has provided a written waiver consenting to activities closer than 300 feet; _ * In an area without an implemented erosion and sedimentation control plan or a farm conservation plan; _ * Within 300 feet of a water source unless the current owner has provided a written waiver consenting to the activities closer than 300 feet; _ * Within 100 feet of an exceptional value wetland; and/or _ * Within 11 inches of the seasonal high water table, nor within 3.3 feet of the regional groundwater table.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Agronomic/Land-related</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>Exceptional quality sludge is exempted from the following regulations as per 25 Pa Code § 271.911(b)(1):_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sludge may not be applied to agricultural land on slopes that exceed 25 percent or to land reclamation sites on slopes that exceed 35 percent unless otherwise approved by DEP. _ * Sludge may not be applied unless the soil pH is 6.0 or greater prior to land application or the sludge application will create a soil pH of 6.0 or greater, unless otherwise approved by DEP. _ * Prior to the first application, the generator or applier must obtain a representative soil analysis for the regulated pollutants for each field on which sludge will be land applied. _ <p>The following regulations apply to all sludge (EQ not exempted as per 25 Pa Code § 271.911(b)(2)):_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sludge may not be applied at a rate that is greater than the agronomic rate, unless approved by DEP for land reclamation activities. _

	<p>* If the nitrogen available from the manure produced by animals at the farm satisfies the nutrient needs of the farm for realistic expected crop yields, the sewage sludge may not be applied at that farm, unless a management plan is implemented that allows for uses of the manure other than land application on that farm._</p> <p>* A person that operates under an individual or general land application of sewage sludge permit issued under this subchapter (25 Pa Code Chapter 271 Subchapter J) must comply with the EPA and the Department guidance documents on the land application of sewage sludge pertaining to conducting sampling and analyses, and calculating the agronomic rate and the cumulative pollutant loading rate._</p> <p>* Biosolids may not be applied to the land at a rate that is greater than the agronomic rate, unless a greater rate is approved for land reclamation. Agronomic rates must be calculated in accordance with the most current version of the DEP's Biosolids Training Manual. The Penn State Agronomy Guide, documents yields, or other applicable information sources that may be used to determine appropriate yields and nutrient needs for the purposes of calculation application rates. The source(s) used to calculate rates must be provided with the example calculation provided with the notice of intent for coverage or the 30-day notice on that farm._</p> <p>* A person may not apply sewage sludge unless the soil pH is 6.0 or greater prior to land application unless the Department allows the increase of pH by application of sewage sludge or other material in which case the soil pH shall be 6.0 or greater within 6 months following the application of sewage sludge, or unless otherwise approved in writing by the Department._</p> <p>* Sludge may not be applied to agricultural land on slopes that exceed 25 percent or to land reclamation sites on slopes that exceed 35 percent unless otherwise approved by DEP.</p>
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits	No

to application rates?	
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>See metals limits in 271.914. Same as 40 CFR 503 except inclusion of PCBs ceiling concentrations 8.6mg/kg and pollutant concentration 4 mg/kg.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows_ _ Biosolids stored on a site that is not being used for land application would need a DEP permit to be stored on that site._ _ Non-Exceptional quality biosolids general permit limits amount of biosolids sto</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>No formal plan required under 25 Pa Code 271; however, if the application site receives manure and that manure application is subject to the Nutrient Management requirements in 25 Pa Code 83, those same requirements must be followed.</p>

<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>A person that operates under an individual or general permit issued under this subchapter must comply with applicable sections of Chapter 285 (relating to storage, collection and transportation of municipal waste) prior to land application, unless the applicant proposes to store sewage sludge on drying beds or structures under a solid waste permit from the Department.</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage,</p>	<p>Yes. Septage is regulated by 25 Pa Code Chapter 271. Land application of other organic residuals is regulated by the Bureau of Waste Management under 25 Pa Code Chapter 271 or 25 Pa Code Chapter 291.</p>

composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.

Rhode Island	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Rhode Island Department of Environmental Management (DEM)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Rhode Island Administrative Rule - 250-RICR-150-10-3: https://rules.sos.ri.gov/regulations/part/250-150-10-3
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage" or "wastewater" means human waste, or wastes from toilets and other receptacles intended to receive or retain body waste, and any wastes, including wastes from human households, commercial establishments, and industries. "Sludge" or "sewage sludge" means residue, partially solid, or solid, treated or untreated, resulting from the treatment of sewage, including such residues from the cleaning of sewers, by processes, such as settling, flotation, filtration and centrifugation, that does not meet the criteria for a hazardous waste. Domestic septage is not considered sludge.
Biosolids classes	"Class A biosolids" means any treated sludge that meets the metals and pathogen limits established in § 3.32. Both sets of limits are stricter than 40 CFR 503. "Class B biosolids" means any treated sludge that does not meet the metals limits established in § 3.32 of but meets the metals limits established in § 3.33, which are the same as 40 CFR 503. "Class C biosolids" means any treated sludge that does not meet the metals limits established in § 3.33.
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means the sludge application rate that is designed to provide the amount of nitrogen or other nutrient(s) needed by the crop or vegetation and minimize the amount of nitrogen that passes below the root zone of the crop or the vegetation to the groundwater.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance</i>	Class A: _

must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.

* Distance to Buildings. No sludge may be land applied within 400 feet of any domestic, commercial or industrial structure not associated with the proposed land application project._

* Distance from Property Lines. No sludge may be land applied within 100 feet of a property line. This requirement will be met if consent from the adjacent landowner is received._

—
Class B:—

* No Class B Biosolids may be land applied within 50 feet of any body of surface water or within 100 feet of any body of surface water within the watershed of a public drinking water supply._

* No Class B Biosolids may be land applied within 50 feet of any private drinking water supply well or within 400 feet of any public drinking water supply well. _

* No Class B Biosolids may be land applied within 50 feet of a property_ line. This requirement will be waived if consent from the adjacent landowner is received. _

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For non-Class A Biosolids or any sludge that has not been treated by one of the Processes to Further Reduce Pathogens, the following apply:—

—
* Groundwater. A minimum of two (2) feet of soil is required between the lowest level of applied sludge and the seasonal high groundwater table as determined by a DEM-licensed Class IV soil evaluator in accordance with the procedures described in Part 6 of Chapter 3.13. In addition, a minimum of 3 feet of soil is required between the highest level of bedrock and the lowest level of applied sludge._

* Surface Water. No sludge may be land applied within 200 feet of any body of surface water. No sludge may be applied to land within the watershed of any surface water used as a public drinking water supply. _

* Drinking Water Wells. No sludge may be land applied within one 1,000 feet of any private drinking water supply well or within the Wellhead Protection Area for a public drinking water supply well. Land application of sludge must be in accordance with the Rhode Island Groundwater Protection Act of 1985, R.I. Gen. Laws Chapter 46-13.1 and any rules and regulations promulgated thereunder._

* Distance to Buildings. No sludge may be land applied within 400 feet of any domestic, commercial or industrial structure not associated with the proposed land application project._

* Distance from Property Lines. No sludge may be land applied within one 100 feet of a property line. This requirement will be met if consent from the adjacent landowner is received._

	<p>* Monitoring Wells. Groundwater monitoring must be of a type and frequency determined by the Director on a case by case basis and shall be the responsibility of the owner or operator._</p> <p>* Erosion Control. Soil erosion on all land application sites must be limited to conditions which meet Resource Management System Quality Criteria for soil erosion as defined in the USDA Natural Resources Conservation Service_</p> <p>* (NRCS) Field Office Technical Guide for Rhode Island. Erosion control methods on all land application sites must be consistent with practice standards and specifications in the NRCS Field Office Technical Guide for Rhode Island. Sediment and runoff must be controlled on all land application sites consistent with the measures within the Rhode Island Soil Erosion and Sediment Control Handbook, RI Department of Environmental Management, USDA Soil Conservation Service and Rhode Island State Conservation Committee, 1989.</p>
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<i>Agronomic/Land-related State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	* For non-Class A Biosolids or any sludge that has not been treated by one of the Processes to Further Reduce Pathogens, land application must be applied at an annual rate not to exceed the amount necessary to supply adequate available nitrogen for crop production using good agricultural or silvicultural practices or not to exceed the maximum annual rates recommended by the U.S. Department of Agriculture to achieve fertilizer benefits and soil improvement.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No

Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	* Class A Biosolids must be tested for the metals and the pathogens listed in § 3.32. Class B Biosolids and Class C Biosolids must be tested for the metals and the characteristics listed in § 3.33_ * For non-Class A Biosolids or any sludge that has not been treated by one of the Processes to Further Reduce Pathogens, testing may be required using the Toxicity Characteristic Leaching Procedure for the parameters listed in § 3.31.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	* Class C Biosolids may be used as cover material for solid waste landfills and land disposal sites under § 3.12(E). _ * For non-Class A Biosolids or any sludge that has not been treated by one of the Processes to Further Reduce Pathogens, sludge intended for land application must be treated by one of the Processes to Significantly Reduce Pathogens listed in 40 CFR 503 and must meet one of the Vector Attraction Reduction Requirements listed in 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	* Class A pollutant restrictions are stricter than 40 CFR 503_ * For non-Class A Biosolids or any sludge that has not been treated by one of the Processes to Further Reduce Pathogens, the maximum amount of sludge that can be applied to a land application site must be calculated using the procedure established

	in § 3.34. The amount of metals in the soil must be deducted from each calculation.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Packaged distribution means Class A Biosolids that are sold or given away in a bag or other container for application to the land. The container may not hold no more than 100 pounds of Class A Biosolids.
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	Any land application project must comply with Part 120-05-17 of this Title, as amended, or other rules and regulations pertaining to odors.
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Yes. Particularly in regards to PFAS and PFOA as part of EPA’s PFAS Risk Assessment that is expected to be released sometime at the end of 2024.
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven’t captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions	No

<p>(e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

South Carolina	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	South Carolina Department Environmental Services (SCDES)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	SC Administrative Rule:_ R.61-9.503 -Standards for the Use or Disposal of Sewage Sludge _ R. 61-9.504 Standards for the Use or Disposal of Industrial Sludge _ https://des.sc.gov/sites/des/files/Library/Regulations/R.61-9.503.pdf _ https://des.sc.gov/regulations/standards-use-or-disposal-industrial-sludge
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	The Department maintains broad discretion to apply regulations on a case-by-case basis. The Department may incorporate the requirements (either directly or by reference), for permits for the Use, treatment, and Disposal of Sewage Sludge (see R.61-9.503), or the Use and Disposal of Industrial Sludge (see R.61-9.504) into NPDES permit(s) that may be issued to the applicant. A separate Land Application permit (see R.61-9.505) may be issued by the Department for the activities covered under R.61.9-503 or R.61-9.504, unless an NPDES permit is required for the activity
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage sludge" is solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue generated during the treatment of municipal wastewater or domestic sewage in a treatment works. Sewage sludge includes, but is not limited to, domestic septage; scum or solids removed in primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment processes; and a material derived from sewage sludge. Sewage sludge does not include ash generated during the firing of sewage sludge in a sewage sludge incinerator or grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic or industrial sewage in a treatment works. See R.61-9.504 for Industrial sludge definition.
Biosolids classes	Class A and Class B used in accordance with 40 CFR 503.
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" is the whole sludge application rate (dry weight basis) designed: (1) to provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop, or vegetation grown on the land and (2) to minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the ground water and (3) to provide the amount of other organic and inorganic plant nutrients which promote crop or vegetative growth, such as calcium-carbonate equivalency.

State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Applications for permits are required in the form of a report prepared by a qualified Professional Engineer, qualified soil scientist, qualified agronomist, or other qualified individual. Permits include information that includes the time of year of the sludge application and how it relates to crop planting and harvesting schedule (if applicable), additional soil additives applied on the site, and a site monitoring plan.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Prior to land application, a permit must be submitted to the Department which requires analysis of total solids (mg/l) and volatile solids (mg/kg), nutrients (on a dry weight basis), Kjeldahl nitrogen, inorganic nitrogen (mg/kg), ammonia nitrogen (mg/kg), nitrate nitrogen (mg/kg), phosphorus (mg/kg), potassium (mg/kg), Calcium Carbonate Equivalency (if sewage sludge is alkaline

	stabilized), Pollutants (on a dry weight basis), all metals in ceiling concentrations (As, Cd, Cu, Pb, Hg, Mo, Ni, Se, Zn). Monitoring of PCB in accordance with 61-9-503 Appendix C.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows

<i>transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	A nutrient management plan is required.
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	No
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	Yes. TMDLs for Phosphorus. If there are any Drinking water regulation changes, i.e. MCL for Nitrate SCDHEC Regulation 61-58. Currently the MCL for Nitrate is the reasoning behind setting a maximum PAN for the land application of sludge and septage.
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.	No
4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If	Yes. The land application of septage is regulated under R.61-9.503. The land application of compost (R.61-9.503 process) is also regulated. The land application of Compost (non domestic/industrial wastewater) is regulated by our Bureau of Land & Waste M

so, please briefly
describe.

South Dakota	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	DANR - South Dakota Department of Agriculture & Natural Resources
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	South Dakota Administrative Rule 74:52:09:01:_ http://sdlegislature.gov/rules/DisplayRule.aspx?Rule=74:52:09:01
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Definition of biosolids is not defined in Rule but is defined in permit. Biosolids means any sludge or material derived from sludge that can be beneficially used. Beneficial uses includes, but is not limited to, land application to agricultural land, forest land, reclamation site or sale or given away to the public for home lawn and garden use.
Biosolids classes	Class A- EQ_ Class B_
Other Definitions	Sludge is not defined in Rule but is defined in permit. Sludge is any solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue generated during treatment of municipal wastewater or domestic sewage and/or a combination of domestic sewage and industrial waste of a liquid nature in the Treatment Works. Sludge includes but is not limited to domestic septage, scum or solids removed during primary, secondary, or advanced wastewater treatment, portable toilet pumpings, and sludge products. Sludge does not include grit, screenings, or ash generated during the incineration of biosolids.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Application rate limit to 6% slope if frozen, 3-6% slope have additional requirements if frozen.
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503_ * Biosolids application of 38% volatile reduction or injection or incorporate within 6 hours of application_

<i>under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	* Agronomic rates and nitrogen limits by crop planted using South Dakota State University E750 "Fertilizer Recommendation Guide" and annual soil testing
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p>Vectors</p> <p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	No
<p>Pollutants</p> <p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503.
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	No
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	No
<p>Transportation</p> <p><i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Nutrient management plans</p> <p><i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	Annual shallow soil sampling for phosphorus, nitrate, and pH. Every 5 years deep nitrate soil sampling. Agronomic rates are calculated every year for every field that will be applied to and crops planted using South Dakota State University EC750 "Fertiliz
<p>Incineration</p> <p><i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	Permitted
<p>Other regulatory details</p> <p><i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	According to the regulation, "The standards for the use or disposal of sewage sludge for surface water discharge permits are those in 40 C.F.R. Part 503" ²
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next</p>	Undetermined

<p>two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Tennessee Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Tennessee Department of Environmental and Conservation_ Division of Water Resources
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	TN Administrative Rule 400-40-15:_ https://publications.tnsosfiles.com/rules/0400/0400-40/0400-40.htm _ Biosolids state operating permits:_ https://www.tn.gov/environment/permit-permits/water-permits1/biosolids-state-operating-permit.html
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" are treated sewage sludge that have contaminant concentrations less than or equal to the contaminant concentrations listed in Table 1 of 40 CFR 503.13, meet any one of the ten vector attraction reduction options listed in 40 CFR 503.33, and meet either one of the six pathogen reduction alternatives for Class A listed in 40 CFR 503.32, or one of the three pathogen reduction alternatives for Class B listed in 40 CFR 503.32.
Biosolids classes	"Exceptional Quality Biosolids" or "EQ biosolids" are biosolids that meet the ceiling concentrations in Table 1 of 40 CFR 503.13 and the contaminant concentrations in Table 3 of 40 CFR 503.13; the Class A pathogen requirements in 40 CFR 503.32; and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8). EQ biosolids are exempt from the rules below as per 0400-40-15-.01 (b)._ _ Class A and B are used in accordance with CFR 503.
Other Definitions	The "Agronomic rate" is the lesser of the whole biosolids application rate (dry weight basis) designed in accordance with subparagraph (4)(d) of Rule 0400-40-15-.02:_ _ o To provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop, or vegetation grown on the land; and_ o To minimize the amount of nitrogen in the biosolids that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the ground water._ _

	"Annual whole biosolids application rate" is the maximum amount of biosolids (dry weight basis) that can be applied to a unit area of land during any calendar year.
State Regulatory Details	
<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>Non-EQ bulk biosolids must not be applied to agricultural land, forest, or a reclamation site unless all of the following setbacks are met: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 100 feet or more from surface waters of the State of Tennessee which are positioned down gradient of the application site. _ * 33 feet or more from surface waters of the State of Tennessee which are positioned up gradient for the application site. _ * 100 feet from all wells, water supply reservoirs, and active sinkholes.
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	Yes
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>For the purposes of determining the agronomic rate, the person applying biosolids must comply with all five of the following parts for non-EQ biosolids: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> _ 1. Determine crop yields and crop nitrogen (N) requirements based upon a recommendation of the farmer, a written recommendation from the University of Tennessee Extension, historical site yield data, or estimated average yields for the specified crops within the County in which the application site is situated. The average of the actual yields documented from the best three years during a 5-year cycle is typical and is recommended. _ _ 2. The following Mineralization Rates must be used as default values in calculating the agronomic rate unless actual mineralization rates have been determined and approved by state: _ _ Unstabilized Primary and Secondary Sewage Sludge 40%_ Alkaline Stabilized Sewage Sludge 30%_ Aerobically Digested Sewage Sludge 30%_ Anaerobically Digested Sewage Sludge 20%_ Composted Sewage Sludge 10%_ _ 3. Crop nitrogen requirements must follow Table 1 in 0400-40-15-.02. _ _ 4. Procedures for determining plant available nitrogen (PAN) as described in paragraph (12) Appendix .02-A must be followed and the whole biosolids application rate must provide no more than the

	<p>amount of nitrogen required by the crop or crops to be grown unless otherwise specified by the State Biosolids Coordinator._</p> <p>–</p> <p>5. In cases where the biosolids have substantial liming value, the agronomic rate must be the lesser of the whole biosolids application rate that provides crop nitrogen needs or required liming equivalent necessary to raise the soil pH to the value most conducive for productivity of the crop(s) to be grown. Since moderately alkaline soil ranges from 7.9 to 8.4, the upper limit for soil pH is 8.4.</p>
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	PCBs must be monitored at least once every five years unless otherwise specified by the State Biosolids Coordinator; A Toxicity Characteristic Leaching Procedure (TCLP) using SW-846 Method 1311 in accordance with 40 CFR 261.24 must be conducted at least once every five years unless otherwise specified by the State Biosolids Coordinator.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503	No

with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted

<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>No other information</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Texas	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Texas Commission on Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	Texas Administrative Code, Title 30, Part 1, Chapter 312: http://texreg.sos.state.tx.us/public/readtac%24ext.ViewTAC?tac_view=4&ti=30&pt=1&ch=312
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	Agronomic rate is based on nitrogen application
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	For non-class A bulk sludge or sludge-derived product:_ * 200-foot buffer zone required between site of application and surface water, if the sludge is not incorporated; for land application sites located in a major sole-source impairment zone this buffer zone must maintain a vegetative cover_ * 33-foot vegetative buffer zone required between site of application and surface water, if the sludge is incorporated_ * 150 feet buffer zone required between site of application and private water supply well_ * 500 feet buffer zone required between site of application and public water supply well, intake, spring or similar source, public water supply treatment plant, or public water supply elevated or ground storage tank_ * 200 feet buffer zone required between site of application and solution channel, sinkhole, or other conduit to groundwater_ * 750 feet buffer zone required between site of application and established school, institution, business, or occupied residential structure (some class AB is exempt)_

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 50 feet buffer zone required between site of application and public right-of-way and property boundaries (some class AB is exempt)_ * 10 feet buffer zone required between site of application and irrigation conveyance canal_ <p>These conditions can be removed or attenuated by approved agreements with landowners_</p> <p>—</p> <p>For non-class A bulk sludge or sludge-derived product:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * A seasonal high groundwater table must be not less than three feet below the treatment zone for soils with moderate or slower permeability (less than two inches per hour)._ * A seasonal high groundwater table must be not less than four feet below the treatment zone for soils with moderately rapid or rapid permeability (greater than two inches per hour and less than 20 inches per hour)._ <p>Case-by-case exceptions may be made.</p>
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	<p>For all classes of application:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sewage sludge may not be applied during rainstorms or during periods in which surface soils are water-saturated, and when pooling of water is evident on the land application site. Adverse Weather and Alternative Plans are required for some sites.
<i>Agronomic/Land-related State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	<p>For non-class A bulk sludge or sludge-derived product:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Sludge must be applied uniformly over the surface of the land (some class AB is exempt)_ * Sludge may not be applied to areas where permeable surface soils are less than two feet thick, except where exempted by the Director_ * Sludge may not be applied to areas having topographical slopes in excess of 8.0%, except where exempted by the Director_ * Where runoff of sludge from the active application area is evident, the operator shall cease further sludge application until the condition is corrected (some class AB is exempted)_ * Sewage sludge may not be applied on land within a designated floodway (some class AB is exempted)
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which	Yes

biosolids can be applied?	
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	* Land applied sludge and septage must be tested for pathogens, total solids, fixed solids, and volatile solids.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<p><i>prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>* Only Class A or AB bulk sludge may be applied to a lawn or home garden_ * Only Class A or AB bulk sludge may be sold or given away in a bag or other container for land application_</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent</p>	<p>No</p>

than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Has a Chromium limit
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	Yes
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of</i>	* For Class B sewage sludge only, a nutrient management plan prepared by a certified nutrient management specialist in accordance with the NRCS Practice Standard Code 590 is required.

<p><i>a biosolids application program</i></p>	
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>* Material derived from sewage sludge is treated much the same as the same quality bulk sludge from which it derived in terms of land application regulations_ * Storage of sludge at a beneficial land application site must not exceed 90 days_ – Staging sewage sludge and domestic septage may only occur for a maximum of seven days at a land application site. Up to an additional 14 days of staging sewage sludge will be allowed with the prior approval for reasons associated with application area flooding, saturated soils, frozen soils, or equipment failure.</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please</p>	<p>Yes. Based on legislation, land application of Class B sludge is prohibited on land that is located both in a county bordering the Gulf of Mexico and is within 500 feet or less from any water well or surface waters.</p>

describe or provide links.	
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>Yes. There are counties (about 5 that we know of) that may have ordinances against the land application of sludge or septage. The Agency may issue an authorization for Class A/AB, B or domestic septage, but a county ordinance can super cede that authoriza</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Domestic septage is authorized for beneficial land use as a registration. Contains same site management practices as a Class B sludge land application site._ Land application/marketing and distribution of compost material containing sewage sludge wi</p>

Utah	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Utah Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	* Utah Code Title 19, Chapter 5: Water Quality Act:_ https://le.utah.gov/xcode/Title19/Chapter5/19-5.html _ * Utah Administrative Code, R317-1-6_ https://adminrules.utah.gov/public/rule/R317-1/Current%20Rules?searchText=R317
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	Land application plans can be required as part of Utah's state NPDES (UPDES) permitting process, but the plans appear to be approved on a case-by-case basis. Regs are not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503.
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No

Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Unknown
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No sewage sludge incineration units in state
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Yes. Only what the EPA will develop regarding PFOA and PFOS.
2. Are there any other regulations in your state	No

<p>that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Septage is regulated through 40 cfr 503. The land application (non-sanitary, food processing wastes) and composting of other organic waste (manure with animal remains) are regulated through the UDEQ/Division of Waste Management and Radiation Control</p>

Vermont Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	VT Department of Environmental Conservation
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	https://dec.vermont.gov/sites/dec/files/wmp/SolidWaste/Documents/SWRule_final_.pdf
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	Vermont regulates biosolids and septage management under the Vermont Solid Waste Management Rules (a new version became effective 10/31/2020) (VSWMR) and has adopted more stringent standards for the "diffuse disposal" (the term used in the VSWMR for "land application") of biosolids (see Tables 2 - 5) than those required by Part 503. This report quotes sections of the 2016 report on VT and federal biosolid differences: https://dec.vermont.gov/sites/dec/files/wmp/residual/RMSWhitePaper20180507.pdf
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage sludge" is defined as the solid, semi-solid, or liquid residue generated during the biological treatment of sewage or septage in a treatment works (usually a municipal wastewater treatment facility), per the legal definitions from 40 CFR Part 503.9 (provided on pages 19 - 20 of this report). Sewage sludge (simply referred to as "sludge" herein), while it may have received some level of additional treatment, has not been tested and shown to meet the regulatory standards that allow it to be used as opposed to disposed, and is therefore differentiated in its use and meaning from the term "biosolids". "Biosolids" is defined as sewage sludge which has been subjected to a treatment process for the reduction of pathogens and has been shown to meet the applicable requirements for contaminant concentrations, vector attraction reduction (VAR), and pathogen densities, as necessary for the intended use, such that the material may be applied to the land under a site specific permit or marketed and distributed to the general public for unregulated use, as established under regulations. Sludge which has not been treated to "biosolids standards" may not be managed via application to the land.
Biosolids classes	Vermont recognizes two classes of biosolids, Class B) and Exception Quality (EQ) (same pathogen and VAR standards as EPA Part 503s) "EQ biosolids," or Exceptional Quality biosolids, is defined as sewage sludge or biosolids that have been subjected to an advanced pathogen reduction treatment process

	and meet the vector attraction, pollutant concentration, and pathogen indicator organism density standards such that they are no longer classified as a solid waste and may be marketed and distributed to the general public for use without a site-specific permit.
Other Definitions	Stablized septage: see VWRW 2020 for definitions. This residual waste is regulated similarly to class B biosolids in terms of pathogen and vector attraction reduction, contaminant levels, site-specific permits and set back/site prohibitions. Only domestic septage may be land applied.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Siting requirements specify the following minimum isolation distances:_ <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * 3 ft vertical separation from high seasonal water table or bedrock_ * 50 ft to waters, if injected, otherwise 100 ft_ * 300 ft to drinking water source not owned by applicant_ * 25 ft to property line, if injected, otherwise 50 ft_ * 100 ft to residences, schools, daycare facilities, hospitals, and nursing homes not owned by applicant.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Application practices and rates for biosolids and stabilized septage are strictly controlled and application of biosolids to frozen or snow covered ground, or where there is less than 36" of unsaturated soil, is prohibited.
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Application rate determined on the basis of representative sampling and analysis of the wastes applied, the crop nutrient requirements, other sources of nutrient used, and limited by other factors such as metals._ * Application of biosolids and/or septage must be incorporated into a nutrient management plan meeting the standards of the Vermont Required Agricultural Practices and the Vermont USDA NRC's Nutirent Management Plan 590 Standard. * Cadmium application limited to 0.45 pounds per acre annually, and 4.5 pounds per acre cumulatively._ * The pH of the soil in the zone of incorporation for all sites used for application of solid wastes must be maintained between 6.5 and 8.0 during the time of application._ * Application prohibited in the floodway and on the 100 year floodplain unless incorporated within 48 hours of application._ * Application prohibited at times when groundwater is within three feet of the zone of incorporation._ * Application prohibited in Class I and Class II Groundwater areas._ * Application prohibited in a watershed for a Class A stream or stream segment._

	* Application rates for biosolids and septage are strictly controlled. The WM Program has developed an Excel® based spreadsheet model (Application Rate Model) for calculating application rates based on both nitrogen and phosphorus.
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and</i>	Biosolids testing required for percent solids, pH, total Kjeldahl nitrogen, ammonia-nitrogen, nitrate-nitrogen, total phosphorous, water extractable phosphorus, total potassium, PCBs, metals (including: arsenic, cadmium, chromium, copper, lead, mercury, molybdenum, nickel, selenium, zinc and,

<p><i>chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>depending on method, silver and barium), per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, and pathogens. Frequency is established in the certification.</p>
<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Public access shall be controlled for the duration of the disposal, and for 12 months beyond the last episode._ * Domestic food source animals prohibited from grazing on disposal facilities for the duration of the project and 12 months beyond the last disposal episode._ * Sites amended by solid waste application may not be used for the production of crops for direct human consumption, for the duration of the project and 38 months beyond the last disposal episode._ * Feed crops grown on solid waste amended disposal facilities may not be harvested for a period of five weeks beyond the last disposal episode._ * Silage to be used as a feed crop, from solid waste amended sites may not be fed to domestic food source animals for a period of four months after the last application of waste.
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>* Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503. Note that state defines operational standards differently than federal usage, and the latter is used here.</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>

<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>More stringent pollutant concentrations standards for land application of biosolids (in mg/kg, dry wt): As 15, Cd 21, Cr 1200, Cu 1500, Pb 300, Hg 10, Mo 75, Ni 420, Se 100, Zn 2800. Includes PCBs (10mg/kg).</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>Current SW Rules: None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows._ _ Draft SW Rules: Likely to contain an out-of-state registry for Class A/EQ Biosolids entering Vermont to ensure the material meets the more stringent standards of either Vermont or the</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids</i></p>	<p>Application of biosolids and/or septage must be incorporated into a nutrient management plan meeting the standards of the Vermont Required Agricultural Practices and the Vermont USDA NRC's Nutirent Management Plan 590 Standard.</p>

<i>application program</i>	
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	No incinerators located in VT.
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	No
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	Yes. As of 2020 VSWMRs we require PFAS testing in biosolids, and in soils, groundwater and crops at permitted land application sites (Class B and septage).
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities,	No

<p>counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Septage, like sewage sludge and biosolids, is managed as a residual material per the Solid Waste Rules. Septage annual application rates (AAR) are determined using the EPA equation: $AAR = N/.0026$ and subject to the same metals standards, pathogen.</p>

Virginia	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2025
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Virginia Department of Environmental Quality
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	<p>* DEQ Code of Virginia § 62.1-44.19:3: https://law.lis.virginia.gov/vacode/title62.1/chapter3.1/section62.1-44.19:3/ _</p> <p>* Virginia Administrative Code, Title 9, Agency 25, Chapters 20, 31, and 32: https://law.lis.virginia.gov/admincode/title9/agency25/ _</p> <p>* DCR - Nutrient Management Training and Certification Regulations: https://law.lis.virginia.gov/admincode/title4/agency50/chapter85 _</p> <p>* Nutrient Management Standards and Criteria: https://www.dcr.virginia.gov/document/standardsandcriteria.pdf</p>
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	<p>Land application of biosolids is regulated by Virginia Pollution Abatement (VPA) permits and Virginia Pollutant Discharge Elimination System (VPDES) permits. DEQ retains broad discretion to implement more stringent requirements on a case-by-case basis. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Land application must be in accordance with a Nutrient Management Plan written by a Virginia certified planner. _</p>
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" means a sewage sludge that has received an established treatment and is managed in a manner to meet the required pathogen control and vector attraction reduction, and contains concentrations of regulated pollutants below the ceiling limits established in 40 CFR Part 503 and 9VAC25-31-540, such that it meets the standards established for use of biosolids for land application, marketing, or distribution in accordance with this chapter. Liquid biosolids contains less than 15% dry residue by weight. Dewatered biosolids contains 15% or more dry residue by weight.
Biosolids classes	<p>Class A and Class B treatment for pathogen control are identical to the CFR. _</p> <p>_</p> <p>Exceptional quality. Distribution or marketing provides for the sale or distribution of exceptional quality biosolids or mixtures of exceptional quality biosolids with other materials such that the</p>

	<p>mixture achieves the Class A pathogen control, vector attraction reduction and pollutant control standards. Distribution or marketing of Class A biosolids that have been mixed with inert materials may be approved on a case-by-case basis. Use of such mixtures for agricultural purposes shall be evaluated through proper testing or research programs designed to assess the suitability of the material for such use. Exceptional quality biosolids marketed as fertilizers or soil conditioners must meet the following conditions: _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> o The biosolids product must be registered with the Virginia Department of Agriculture and Consumer Services in accordance with the provisions of § 3.2-3607 of the Code of Virginia. _ o The biosolids product must be processed to meet Class A pathogen requirements as specified in 9VAC25-32-675 A. _ o The biosolids product must meet one of the vector attraction reduction requirements as specified in 9VAC25-32-685 B 1 through B 8. _ o The biosolids product must meet the ceiling concentrations specified in 9VAC25-32-356 - Table 2. _ o The biosolids product must meet the pollutant concentrations specified in 9VAC25-32-356 - Table 4. _ o Additional parameters may be required for screening purposes such as organic chemicals, aluminum (mg/kg), water soluble boron (mg/kg), calcium (mg/kg), chlorides (mg/l), manganese (mg/kg), sulfur (mg/kg), and those pollutants for which removal credits are granted.
<p>Other Definitions</p>	<p>"Agronomic rate" means the whole sludge application rate (dry weight basis) designed: (i) to provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop, or vegetation grown on the land and (ii) to minimize the amount of nitrogen in the biosolids that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the groundwater.</p>
<p>State Regulatory Details</p>	
<p>Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<p>Prescribed in 9VAC25-32-560.B.3.e.(1). Includes 10-400ft setbacks from adjacent features. _</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * The setback distance to occupied dwellings may be reduced or waived upon written consent of the occupant and landowner of the dwelling. _ * The department shall grant to any landowner or resident in the vicinity of a biosolids land application site an extended setback of up to 200 feet from their property line and up to 400 feet from their occupied dwelling upon request from their physician based on medical reasons. In order for an extended setback request to be granted, the request must be submitted to the department in writing on a form provided by the department. A request must be received by the department no later than 48 hours before land application commences on the field affected by the extended setback, and communicated to the permittee no later than 24 hours before land application commences on the field affected by the extended

	<p>setback. The department may extend a setback distance within 48 hours of land application if requested by the Virginia Department of Health in connection with the landowner or resident's physician._</p> <p>* Setback distances may be extended beyond 400 feet where an evaluation by the Virginia Department of Health determines that a setback in excess of 400 feet is necessary to prevent specific and immediate injury to the health of an individual._</p> <p>* The setback distance to property lines may be reduced or waived upon written consent of the landowner._</p> <p>* Publicly accessible sites are open to the general public and routinely accommodate pedestrians and include, but are not limited to, schools, churches, hospitals, parks, nature trails, businesses open to the public, and sidewalks. Temporary structures, public roads or similar thoroughfares are not considered publicly accessible._</p> <p>* A closed sinkhole does not have an open conduit to groundwater. The setback from a closed sinkhole may be reduced or waived by the department upon evaluation by a professional soil scientist.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>See DCR_ Nutrient Management Training and Certification Regulations:_ https://law.lis.virginia.gov/admincode/title4/agency50/chapter85 _ Nutrient Management Standards and Criteria:_ https://www.dcr.virginia.gov/document/standardsandcriteria.pdf</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>* Surface incorporation or extended setbacks may be required to mitigate malodors_</p> <p>* Soil must be sampled and analyzed prior to biosolids application to determine site suitability and to provide background data._</p> <p>_</p> <p>See DCR_ Nutrient Management Training and Certification Regulations:_ https://law.lis.virginia.gov/admincode/title4/agency50/chapter85 _ Nutrient Management Standards and Criteria:_ https://www.dcr.virginia.gov/document/standardsandcriteria.pdf</p>
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?</p>	<p>Yes</p>

Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Testing frequency as prescribed in 40 CFR 503, and the following parameters must be measured: percent solids, volatile solids, pH, total Kjeldahl nitrogen, ammonia nitrogen, nitrates, total phosphorus, total potassium, alkalinity as calcium carbonate, and metals.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503 for Class B_ _

<i>chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	For distribution and marketing of Exceptional Quality biosolids, biosolids pollutant concentrations must be below PC levels. 40CFR503 provides for applications not to exceed APLR if biosolids are above PC levels and distributed and marketed.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	A nutrient management plan prepared by a person who is certified as a nutrient management planner by the Virginia Department of Conservation and Recreation (DCR) must be prepared for all application sites prior to biosolids land application and approved b
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Permitted
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No other information
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Yes. DEQ has published a Notice of Intended Regulatory Action in response to 2024 Virginia legislative changes (Chapter 209 of the 2024 Acts of Assembly/HB870: https://townhall.virginia.gov/L/ViewAction.cfm?actionid=6561) which require the State Water Co
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No

<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>Undetermined. Virginia law allows localities to enact ordinances related to specific categories of biosolids storage. Land application may not be further restricted by localities._ See § 62.1-44.19:3.R. of the Code of Virginia_ https://law.lis.virginia.g</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Per https://law.lis.virginia.gov/vacode/title62.1/chapter3.1/section62.1-44.19:3/ _ A.4. The land disposal of lime-stabilized septage and unstabilized septage is prohibited.</p>

Washington	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Washington Department of Ecology
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	* Washington Administrative Code, Chapter 173-308_ * Revised Code of Washington, Chapters 70.95J, Chapter 90.48 is our WQ law, but we address biosolids under the Solid Waste Management Program. RCW 70.95J and WAC 173-308 are specific to biosolids management
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Biosolids" refers to sewage sludge or septage that has been or is being treated to meet standards so that it can be applied to the land Here is our definition. The significance of material in the process of being treated is kind of esoteric. "Biosolids" means municipal sewage sludge that is a primarily organic, semisolid product resulting from the wastewater treatment process, that can be beneficially recycled and meets all applicable requirements under this chapter. Biosolids includes a material derived from biosolids, and septic tank sludge, also known as septage, that can be beneficially recycled and meets all applicable requirements under this chapter. For the purposes of this rule, semisolid products include biosolids or products derived from biosolids ranging in character from mostly liquid to fully dried solids.
Biosolids classes	Class A and Class B, plus septage, same as federal rule.
Other Definitions	"Septage" is liquid or solid material removed from septic tanks, cess pools, portable toilets, type III marine sanitation devices, vault toilets, pit toilets, RV holding tanks, or similar systems that receive only domestic sewage. Septage may also include commercial or industrial septage mixed with domestic septage if approved. It is a class of biosolids._ – "Agronomic rate" is the biosolids application rate that provides the amount of nitrogen necessary for the optimum growth of targeted vegetation, and that will not result in the violation of applicable standards or requirements for the protection of ground or surface water as established under chapter 90.48 RCW and related rules including chapters 173-200 and 173-201A WAC.
State Regulatory Details	

Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Per state rule, Class B biosolids must not be applied to the land within one hundred feet (30.5 meters) of a well or surface waters unless approved in a permit issued by the department. The same limit applies to septage. We also have guidelines that are more stringent. We write those criteria into permit approvals, as appropriate.
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	<p>* All new land application sites where nonexceptional quality biosolids will be applied, must be tested for the pollutants listed in Table 3 of 40 CFR 503.13 to determine background levels._</p> <p>* Soil nutrient levels must be tested prior to each land application event, and background nutrient levels are used to calculate the agronomic rate in accordance with WAC 173-308-190, with certain exceptions for reclamation and research sites. Testing is generally done in the fall in order to evaluate past season success, and adjustments are made the following year if necessary._</p> <p>* Agronomic rate determinations must take into account nitrogen supplied from other sources such as manures, cover crops, and commercial fertilizers as well as biosolids.</p>
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing	* A biosolids sampling plan must be submitted to the department._

<p><i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>* Sampling and analysis protocols are delineated in WAC 173-308-140</p>
<p>Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>* When the potential for groundwater contamination due to biosolids application exists, the department may require groundwater monitoring or other conditions_ * Biosolids may not be applied to the land if they are likely to adversely affect a threatened or endangered species or its critical habitat as listed under either federal or state law_ * Only exceptional quality biosolids can be applied to a lawn or garden or sold or given away in a bag or other container _</p>
<p>Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>Transfers among facilities are permitted so long as certain quality and permitting information is conveyed.</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>A Site Specific Land Application Plan (SSLAP) is required for every site where non-exceptional biosolids are applied to the land, unless they are sent to a permitted beneficial use facility. This plan requires a number of details about methods/timing of</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>Septage is largely treated as a class B biosolid as per WAC 173-308-270</p>
General Assessment Questions	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>
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West Virginia	
Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	West Virginia Department of Environmental Protection (DEP)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	WV Administrative Rule - 33-02 Sewage Sludge Management Rule: https://apps.sos.wv.gov/adlaw/csr/readfile.aspx?DocId=21960&Format=PDF
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage sludge" means solid, semi-solid or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works. Sewage sludge includes, but is not limited to, domestic septage, scum or solids removed in primary, secondary or advanced wastewater treatment processes and a material derived from sewage sludge. "Sewage sludge" does not include ash generated during the firing of sewage sludge in a sewage sludge incinerator. "Sludge" means any solid, semisolid, residue or precipitate, separated from or created by a municipal, commercial or industrial waste treatment plant, water supply treatment plant or air pollution control facility or any other such waste having similar origin.
Biosolids classes	"Exceptional Quality Compost" means compost resulting from sewage sludge, which compost meets the Table 1 metal limits of this rule and which has been treated to achieve Class A pathogen reduction requirements in accordance with 40 CFR 503.32(a) and one of the vector attraction requirements in 40 CFR 503.33(b)(1) through (b)(8). — The terms Class A and B are in accordance with 40 CFR 503.
Other Definitions	"Agronomic rate" means the whole sewage sludge application rate, by dry weight, designed: (1) To provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop or vegetation on the land; and (2) To minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the ground water.
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks	Except as provided in subsection 3.2.b, sewage sludge must not be applied to land that meets any of the following conditions:—

<p><i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Land within 50 feet of surface water to include streams, springs, ponds, wetlands, or other collection points for surface water._ * Land within 200 feet of drinking water supply wells or other personal water supply._ * Land within 200 feet of an occupied dwelling._ * Land within 50 feet of a federal or state highway._ * Land within 100 feet of an adjacent property owner's property line._ <p>Some waivers are available for EQ sludge.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Weather-related and seasonal</p>	<p>Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503</p>
<p>Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i></p>	<p>Except as provided in subsection 3.2.b, sewage sludge must not be applied to land that meets any of the following conditions:_</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Land from which drainage leads into a sinkhole._ * Land that has been tested and determined to have a pH of less than 6.2, unless the pH is adjusted to 6.2 or greater._ * Land that has a slope greater than 15%._ * Land that has a seasonal high groundwater table less than 2 feet from the surface._ * Land that has less than 6 inches of soil over bedrock or an impervious pan._ * Land containing soil with surface permeability of less than 0.6 inches/hour or greater than 6 inches/hour._ * Other land determined by the director to be unsuitable for application of sewage sludge._ <p>Some waivers are available for EQ sludge._</p> <p>— If either exceptional quality compost is applied to land or Class A sewage sludge products that meet Table 1 metals limits and one of the vector attraction reduction requirements of 40 CFR 503(b)(1-8) are sold or given away in a bag or other container is applied to land, the slope cannot be greater than 15% nor can its drainage lead to a sinkhole.</p>
<p>Are there restrictions by soil type?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Are there restrictions on the method for</p>	<p>No</p>

applying biosolids?	
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	Yes
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	Yes
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Frequency of testing is different than CFR in lowest and highest production categories. Testing includes pH, % solids, organic nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus, calcium, magnesium, total nitrogen, ammonia nitrogen, pathogens, and metals.
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent	No

than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	The same pollutants as in 40 CFR 503 are regulated, but limits for chromium and molybdenum are also set. Table 1 limits are more strict than federal regulations, and Table 2 limits are the same as 40 CFR 503.13
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	Yes
Is there a chromium limit set?	Yes
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the</i>	None that are likely to impact phosphorus flows

<p><i>movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>No formal nutrient plan required unless under the WM Program</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>
<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>Land Application Permit Application Requirement must submit the following:_ * Soil analysis for all land application sites including but not limited to pH, potassium, phosphorus, nitrogen, all metals listed in Table 1 and any additional chemical analysis required by the director;_ * Information relative to the nitrogen content of the sludge(s) or product(s) derived from sewage sludge to be land applied</p>
<p>General Assessment Questions</p>	
<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that</p>	<p>No</p>

<p>may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>

Wisconsin Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Wisconsin Department of Natural Resources (IDNR)
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Natural Resources
Links to regulations	Wisconsin Administrative Code, chapters:_ Septage NR 113_ Biosolids NR 204_ Industrial Wastes Land spread for Beneficial Use: ss. NR 214.17 & 214.18_ Solid Waste chs. NR 502/518/538_ CAFOs Ch. NR 242_ Manure/Runoff Management: Ch. NR 151_ Nutrient Management: Ch. ATCP 50_ Fertilizer: Ch. ATCP 40_ http://docs.legis.wisconsin.gov/code/admin_code/nr/
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	Yes
Other regulator info	No other information
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	"Sewage sludge" or "sludge" or "biosolids" means the solid, semisolid or liquid residue generated during the treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works. Sewage sludge includes scum or solids removed in primary, secondary or advanced wastewater treatment processes and material derived from sewage sludge. Sewage sludge does not include ash generated during the firing of a sewage sludge incinerator or grit and screenings generated during preliminary treatment of domestic sewage in a treatment works.
Biosolids classes	"Exceptional quality sludge" means sludge that meets the class A requirements for pathogens, as specified in s. NR 204.07 (6) (a), the pollutant concentrations, as specified in 40 CFR 503.13 Table 3, and one of the pre-land application processes to reduce vector attraction, as specified in 40 CFR 503.33 (b)(1-8) or by an equivalent process approved by the department._ _ Class A sludge 1) has a maximum fecal coliform density of 1000 MPN/g TS or maximum Salmonella density of 3 MPN/4g TS and 2) uses one of 12 process options for pathogen reduction as defined in NR 204.07 (6)(a)(2). These expand upon the processes in 40 CFR 503.32 (a). If the material is bagged, distributed or land applied at a later time, it must be retested for pathogen regrowth._ _

	Class B sludge conforms to the definition in 40 CFR 503.32 (b)
Other Definitions	<p>"Agronomic rate" means the whole sludge application rate, on a dry weight basis, designed to provide the amount of nitrogen needed by the food crop, feed crop, fiber crop, cover crop or vegetation grown on the land, and designed to minimize the amount of nitrogen in the sewage sludge that passes below the root zone of the crop or vegetation grown on the land to the groundwater._</p> <p>"High quality sludge" means sludge that meets the monthly average pollutant concentration limits which are shown in 40 CFR 503.13 Table 3. This sludge is exempt from cumulative loading limits. (relates to metals only)_</p> <p>EQ : Exceptional Quality Sewage Sludge where high quality (metals), Class A pathogen treatment process and results at distribution, and appropriate vector attraction reduction method.</p>
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	<p>NR 204.07, Table B outlines a series of restrictions based on whether the sludge is incorporated, injected, or surface applied._</p> <p>Sites require approval for non-EQ sewage sludge. Depth to groundwater and bedrock . _</p> <p>Limitation to private and public wells.</p>
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	Yes
Weather-related and seasonal	<p>* Application of any class of bulk sludge on frozen or snow covered ground is prohibited unless the department grants a specific waiver. At a minimum, the department must ensure that sites or fields used must have slopes less than or equal to 2%, the application rate is less than 10,000 gal/acre, and application is not allowed within 750 feet of any surface water, wetland, or floodplain._</p> <p>* Sludge may not be applied on saturated soils, during significant rainfall events or in areas with ponded water or to areas which are subject to ponding._</p> <p>Requires 180 days of storage to provide opportunities for facilities to meet the winter prohibitions.</p>
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	<p>* Application rates must be based on UW extension bulletin A-2100 (see A2809 for proper reference) following a soil analysis conducted according to UW extension guidance or similar._</p> <p>* If more than 30% of the N needs of the crop are being met by the sludge, then either an accounting of the other sources of N must be made or documentation must be provided that the site is managed under an approved nutrient management plan._</p> <p>* Unless specific mineralization rates are determined by the permittee, the following mineralization rates are to be used in calculating the available organic nitrogen from initial sludge application and from carryover of previous years' application: 25%-12%-6% in years 1 through 3._</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Bulk sludge may be applied to all leguminous crops, except soybeans, at a volume sufficient to supply 200 pounds per acre of available nitrogen. If sludge is applied to soybeans, loading is limited to 140 pounds per acre of available nitrogen._ * Bulk sludge may not be applied on sites with soils which have a rapid permeability of greater than 6 inches per hour unless_ * The pH of the soil must be 5.5 or greater at the time the bulk sludge is applied unless the department determines the pH should be higher_ * If the soil at a site or field is classified as highly erodible on the United States Department of agriculture's county by county soil conservation service soil survey, additional application constraints may be imposed_ * Bulk sludge must be applied in a manner that minimizes soil compaction, prevents surface runoff and controls objectionable odors_ * Bulk sludge land application vehicles or equipment have to be moving at all times while sludge is being applied to ensure uniform application_ * Injection (requires 4-12 inches), Incorporation (requires a minimum depth of 4") GW/BR requirements must show at least 36" of soil_ * Ch. ATCP (DATCP) requires NM planning on all agricultural fields though ATCP 50 provides exemptions during the year of application, phosphorus is required to be accounted for during the nutrient management plan cycle
Are there restrictions by soil type?	Yes
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	Yes
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	Yes
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to	Yes

agronomic/land application restrictions?	
<p>Composition testing</p> <p><i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i></p>	<p>* Sludge must be analyzed for any of a number of characteristics prescribed by the permittee's WPDES permit, including NPK content. Minimum characteristics frequency of testing are defined in NR 204.06(2). Frequency is a function of amount applied. Note: additional testing is common._</p> <p>* Facilities with lagoon or other treatment systems which land apply sludge on an infrequent basis, such as every 10 to 20 years, must sample their sludge once every 5 years, and analyze it for the metals listed in Table 4 of 40 CFR 503.13. The department may require more frequent testing._</p> <p>* Class A sludge requires pathogen testing immediately after the Class A treatment process. Any Class A sludge that isn't immediately bagged, distributed or land applied must be tested for regrowth before such use.</p>
<p>Time restrictions</p> <p><i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i></p>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?</p>	No
<p>Operational standards</p> <p><i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i></p>	<p>* Only exceptional quality sludge may be applied to lawns and home gardens_</p> <p>* Bagged sludge given away or sold must meet Class EQ pathogen and vector reduction requirements, and either the high quality pollutant concentration limits in Table 2 or the ceiling concentration limits in Table 1 of 40 CFR 503.13. If the Table 2 requirements are not met, then maximum annual pollutant loading rates apply as per Table 4 of 40 CFR 503.13.</p>
<p>Vectors</p> <p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i></p>	Sludge may not be land applied unless one of the vector attraction reduction options in CFR 503.33 (b) is satisfied
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?</p>	No
<p>Pollutants</p>	* Sludge which has a PCB concentration greater than 50 mg/kg (dry weight) may not be applied unless a management plan is approved

<p><i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i></p>	<p>by the U.S. EPA region V administrator pursuant to 40 CFR 761.60 (a) (5) (iii). Sludge with a PCB concentration greater than 10 mg/kg (dry weight) must be injected or incorporated into the soil._</p> <p>* If the sludge contains radium-226, land application must terminate when the soil level of radium-226 equals or exceeds 2 pico curies per gram dry weight in the top 12 inches of soil. A number of other criteria are applied to radium-226-containing sludge as outlined in NR 204.07(3)(n)._</p> <p>* Sludge may not be applied to land if the concentration of pollutants in the sludge exceeds any of the ceiling concentration limits established in Table 1 of 40 CFR 503.13._</p> <p>* If bulk sludge is applied to land and the sludge does not meet the pollutant concentration limits in Table 3, then the limits in Table 2 apply. Bulk sludge that does not meet the Table 3 concentration limits may not be applied to sites where the cumulative pollutant loading limits in Table 2 have been reached. When bulk sludge that does not meet Table 3 limits is applied to land, the permittee must notify the department when any site reaches 90% of the allowable cumulative loading for any metal established in Table 2._</p> <p>* When sludge is not high quality, annual application rates need to be lower than a calculated rate as per NR 204.07 (5)(d)_</p> <p>* Molybdenum ceiling concentrations (i.e., minimum requirements) "High quality" limit deleted. No lifetime cumulative requirement.</p>
<p>Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?</p>	<p>Yes</p>
<p>Is there a chromium limit set?</p>	<p>No</p>
<p>Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i></p>	<p>* A permit is not required for imported bulk or bagged exceptional quality sludge, but submittal of a sludge management plan is required for importing bulk exceptional quality sludge. _</p> <p>* WPDES Permit is required if non-EQ sludge is imported and land-appl</p>
<p>Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i></p>	<p>If more than 30% of the N needs of the crop are being met by the sludge, then either an accounting of the other sources of N must be made or documentation must be provided that the site is managed under an approved nutrient management plan._</p> <p>Further, if t</p>
<p>Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i></p>	<p>Permitted</p>

<p>Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i></p>	<p>* The department may impose additional requirements on the use of bulk exceptional quality sludge, through the permit or sludge management plan, on a case-by-case basis if it is determined that misuse of the material is occurring and may have a deleterious impact on public health or the environment._</p> <p>* The quantity of sludge sold or given away in a bag or other container by the permittee to either commercial or domestic users both in-state and out-of-state must be reported._</p> <p>* Permittees obtain approval from the department for each site on which sludge is applied in bulk prior to land application, unless authorized to inspect and approve their own sites under s. NR 204.06 (6). When authorized to inspect and approve sites, sites are monitored by the department.</p>
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General Assessment Questions

<p>1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change</p>	<p>Undetermined</p>
<p>2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.</p>	<p>Yes. ATCP 50. Department of Agriculture, Trade and Consumer Protection relating to Nutrient Management Plans some exemptions when sewage sludge is applied, but requires all nutrients (P) to be captured over the rotation. ATCP 65.22. (DATCP). Limitation o</p>
<p>3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions (e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	<p>No. State statutes prevent local municipalities from restricting septage (s. 281.48) and sewage sludge (s. 283.82).</p>
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>Yes. Manures: CAFOs. See. Ch. NR 243, ATCP 50, NR 151_ Composts (Sewage Sludge): NR 204_ Composts (Solid Waste): NR 518 and/or NR 538_ Industrial: Liquid waste, sludges, by-product-solids (NR 214)</p>

Wyoming Regulator	
When was this last updated?	2019
Agency(ies) involved in regulation enforcement	Wyoming Department of Environmental Quality_ US EPA
Which departmental category is the regulating agency?	Environmental
Links to regulations	None provided
Is the state delegated for biosolids?	No
Other regulator info	Biosolids management appears to be conducted by US EPA Region 8, in accordance with 40 CFR 503
Definitions	
How biosolids are defined	Not defined by state
Biosolids classes	Not defined by state
Other Definitions	No other information
State Regulatory Details	
Setbacks <i>State regulations that indicate how much distance must lie between the site of land application and some feature, such as a water body or building.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to setbacks?	No
Weather-related and seasonal	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Agronomic/Land-related <i>State regulations that restrict land application under certain weather or seasonal conditions.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are there restrictions by soil type?	No
Are there restrictions to the depth at which biosolids can be applied?	No
Are there restrictions on the method for applying biosolids?	No
Are there nitrogen limits to application rates?	No

Are there phosphorus limits to application rates?	No
Are there pH limits to application rates?	No
Are there slope limits to application rates?	No
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to agronomic/land application restrictions?	No
Composition testing <i>State regulations that govern the physical and chemical tests that must be performed on biosolids before application.</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Time restrictions <i>Typically, state regulations that prescribe how much time must pass between the time of application and the time of some other event, such as harvest or public access</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to timing between application and harvesting crops?	No
Operational standards <i>State regulations that govern which classes of biosolids can be used for what purposes and at what time</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Vectors <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing the attraction of insects, rodents, and other pests to applied biosolids</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to vectors?	No
Pollutants <i>State regulations that extend beyond 40 CFR 503 requirements for reducing</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503

<i>chemical contaminants in applied biosolids</i>	
Are regulations more stringent than 40 CFR 503 with respect to pollutants?	No
Is there a chromium limit set?	No
Transportation <i>State regulations that restrict the movement of biosolids from one location to the next, but not including regulations on the type of transport or spill prevention and reporting</i>	Not more restrictive than 40 CFR 503
Nutrient management plans <i>State regulations that require the development of nutrient management plans as part of a biosolids application program</i>	No formal plan required
Incineration <i>Whether or not the state permits the incineration of biosolids as a management alternative</i>	Unknown
Other regulatory details <i>Any other information related to the land application of biosolids</i>	No sewage sludge incineration units in state
General Assessment Questions	
1. Do you anticipate changes in these regulations in the next two years? If yes, please list any bills or regulatory details that may potentially change	Undetermined
2. Are there any other regulations in your state that may affect land application of biosolids that we haven't captured? If yes, please describe or provide links.	No
3. Within your state, are there any jurisdictions	No

<p>(e.g., cities, counties, watersheds) that regulate land application of biosolids beyond state-level regulations? Please provide names of these entities if so.</p>	
<p>4. Is the land application of septage, composts, digestates, or other organic residuals (not biosolids or manure) regulated in your state? If so, please briefly describe.</p>	<p>No</p>